

School of Education and Social Sciences

Division of Education

**Headteachers' Leadership of School Improvement in Bangladeshi
Government Primary Schools: An Ethnographic Study**

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Philosophy degree in Education at the University of the West of Scotland.

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Declaration

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I hereby declare that, unless explicit reference is made to the contributions of others, this thesis represents the culmination of my own efforts work. I certify that this thesis has not been submitted previously and is not currently under submission for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution within the United Kingdom or abroad.

Name: Nasrin Sultana

Date: 23 June 2025

Dedication

I dedicate this work with all my heart to the most significant individuals in my life, my strongest support system: my parents, Md Abdul Haque Mia and Fatema Haque. I think of my father, whom I lost in 2021 while I was studying. His absence weighs heavily on me, and I often contemplate how proud he would be of my accomplishments today. My mother, who is dealing with dementia, adds to my emotional strain, as pursuing my PhD makes it challenging to fulfil her needs.

To my beloved sons: I am immensely grateful for my two sons, Junaed Saimon and Saif Umor, who have continuously supported me throughout my PhD journey. Their sacrifices are beyond words.

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Abstract

This study investigated headteachers' leadership in relation to the challenges and opportunities in improving government primary schools in Bangladesh. This study adopted educational ethnography as the research methodology with naturalistic data collected through ethnographic observations, informal conversations and document reviews. Purposive sampling was used to select headteachers from three primary schools in Dhaka City, which were given the anonymous codes School A, School B, and School C. Thematic data analysis was undertaken after completing data collection, and the findings were structured and presented thematically based on the research questions. The study's findings revealed that headteachers play an important role regarding school improvement in several ways, such as ensuring a quality learning environment, adequate funding and resources, high student attendance and academic success, active parental engagement, and well-prepared, trained, and motivated teachers. Headteachers did this through setting expectations for staff and pupils, engaging in instructional leadership, encouraging staff monitoring of attendance, sharing school vision, securing the active learning and financial support of parents and stakeholders, and overseeing teaching and learning to enhance classroom practices. Headteachers' enactment of power in leading school improvement was analysed using Foucault's concept of power, particularly focusing on subjectivity and ethics, governmentality, and disciplinary power. However, the findings revealed various challenges headteachers faced to ensure school improvement, including teachers' lack of motivation, parents' financial difficulties, complexities within the school managing committee, lack of parental support, and issues with education officers. Nonetheless, headteachers' resilience, commitment, strong leadership, shared school vision, and staff mentoring offer the potential to overcome these challenges and seize opportunities for school improvement. Based on these findings, the study concludes with recommendations for policymakers, headteachers, and other stakeholders (i.e., school communities and parents) towards enhancing headteachers' leadership in school improvement activities in Bangladeshi primary schools, along with suggestions for future research.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms List

ADPEO: Assistant District Primary Education Officer

ATEO: Assistant Thana Education officer

AUEO: Assistant Upazila Education Officer

BTPT: Basic Training of Primary Teachers

C-in-Ed: Certificate in Education

DPEd : Diploma in Primary Education

DPE: Directorate of Primary Education

DPEO: District Primary Education Officer

GoB: Government of Bangladesh

GPS: Government Primary School

HT: Head teacher

MoPME: Ministry of Primary and Mass Education

NFPE: Non-Formal Primary Education

NGO: Non-Governmental Organisation

PTA: Parent Teacher Association

SLIP: School Level Improvement Plan

SMC: School Managing Committee

TEO: Thana Education Officer

TR: Teacher Representative

UEO: Upazila Education Officer

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Chapter 1: General Introduction

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Little research has been conducted on school improvement leadership in new and emerging countries (Anderson and September, 2014); most studies have focused on the global North (Bernhardt, 2017; Day, Sammons and Gorge, 2022). Very little research has been conducted on leading school reform in developing countries (see Moroosi, 2019; Owen et al., 2020), and even less has been undertaken on improvement in primary schools in Bangladesh with a focus on headteachers' leadership. Over the past two decades, the government of Bangladesh has implemented several measures to enhance primary education, including the Compulsory Primary Education Act of 1990 (Hossain et al., 2017), Education for All (EFA) goals, Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Directorate of Primary Education, 2022), The National Plan of Action (NPA) I and II for EFA 2015 goals (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2003), The National Education Policy 2010 (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2010), Primary Education Development Programme, PEDP 1 and 2 (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2003), Primary Education Development Programme 3 and 4 (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023).

Although the government of Bangladesh has implemented several initiatives and policies to enhance primary education, challenges persist, particularly in ensuring the quality of education at this level (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023; Choudhury and Rahaman, 2015). While notable advancements have been made in improving access and promoting gender equality, student achievement in the classroom remains relatively low (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023; Choudhury and Rahaman, 2015; Ananda, 2021; Ahmed, 2021; Mousumi and Kusakabe, 2021). Many studies point to several challenges hampering the standard of primary education in Bangladesh, including poverty (Government of Bangladesh, 2020), funding constraints (Sarker, Wu, and Hossin, 2019), high student-teacher ratio (Paul, Islam, and Hossain, 2021; Kundu, and Chowdhury, 2022; Masoom, and Siddik, 2024; Ahmed, Adhikary, and Rahaman, 2024), inadequate teacher preparation (Masoom, and Siddik, 2024; Al Zaman et al., 2024; Al Nahar, Hira, and Milon 2024), and inadequate stakeholder support (Uddin, Akhter, and Hena, 2018; Kabir, Green, and Chowdhury, 2020; Numan, and Islam, 2021). Few studies have investigated headteachers' perceptions about improving educational quality and, more specifically, the headteacher's role within this.

Bangladeshi primary headteachers must engage and negotiate with education officials, school committee members, community leaders, staff, and other stakeholders to drive school improvement. Current literature has not sufficiently explored the approaches employed and the challenges encountered. Although the Directorate of Primary Education (DPE) has published numerous manuals, evaluation guidelines, and other documents to enhance primary education, headteachers' specific role and responsibility in driving these improvement activities and addressing the challenges they encounter have not been adequately explored in these documents. The limited research available leaves headteachers in Bangladeshi primary schools without sufficient research-informed strategies to effectively address and navigate school improvement challenges.

Concerning guidance for headteachers, the Headteachers' Leadership Training Manual (for trainers) emphasises the importance of effective leadership in schools (Directorate of Primary Education, 2023). It further notes that a headteacher's responsibility includes teaching and serving as an Academic Supervisor, Administrator, Mentor, Manager, Facilitator, and, finally, a leader who oversees all school improvement initiatives. This requirement of headteachers is also evident in the school inspection form known as the Primary School Inspection Report. Through this process, education officers supervise schools, and headteachers are held accountable for all activities that take place in the school. Despite limited focus in the literature, headteachers are generally seen as responsible for school improvements and challenges. Furthermore, little is known about how head teachers manage schools with limited resources, particularly when dealing with huge class sizes, poverty, and (sometimes) unmotivated teachers. Therefore, this research focuses on headteachers' leadership practices and their approach to challenges posed by initiatives for school improvement.

1.2 Aim of the Study

This ethnographic study aimed to investigate the leadership of Headteachers in the context of school improvement within Bangladeshi primary schools, with a specific focus on how they implemented and responded to school improvement initiatives.

1.3. Research Questions

Considering issue 1.1 above, to address these challenges, this study sought to address three research questions noted below:

RQ1: How do stakeholders explain the role of the headteacher in leading school improvement initiatives?

This research question aims to investigate stakeholders' perspectives on the role of the headteacher in driving school improvement initiatives. By considering the views of stakeholders, such as parents, teachers, headteachers, members of the school management committee, and government representatives, the research seeks to strengthen understanding of how stakeholders perceive the role of the headteacher in several crucial areas that promote school improvement.

RQ2: In what ways do headteachers experience the enactment of power in their leadership of school improvement?

RQ2 is analysed through Foucault's concept of power, including knowledge, subjectivity, governmentality, and disciplinary power (which encompasses hierarchical observation, normalising judgement, and examination). This chapter examines how headteachers in Bangladeshi government primary schools are both shaped by and participate in the enactment of power. Drawing on this theoretical lens, it explores how power is not merely held or exercised, but is experienced through institutional expectations, cultural norms, and policy pressures, as well as through the headteachers' own leadership practices, positions, and identities. This approach maps the complex interplay between individual agency and broader social, cultural, and institutional dynamics.

RQ3: What are the challenges and opportunities for Headteachers in leading school improvement initiatives?

This question aims to explore the challenges that head teachers face when directing school improvement activities and the opportunities that they recognise as supporting their drive for school improvement.

1.3 Personal Motivation

Before sharing my motivation for researching school leadership, I want to reflect on key memories that sparked my interest in this field. My journey in school leadership began in 2004 when I worked as a teacher at a government primary school in Bangladesh. Since 2004, I have been involved with school leadership but understood little about leadership theories and practices. I noticed my headteacher grappling with various challenges in school improvement, particularly when attempting to implement her leadership strategies and activities. She needed to compromise on various decisions related to school improvement with the education officers, political leaders and school managing committee members. I sometimes noticed that the headteacher was not quite happy with certain decisions, as she felt they might not be beneficial for the school's improvement. In addition, some teachers were highly unmotivated. Their lack of motivation disheartened me as a newly appointed teacher. They seemed only concerned when the headteacher monitored the classroom or education officers visited the school.

I began my headteacher role in 2007, which enabled me to engage directly in leadership activities. I successfully built a dedicated team of teachers and focused on classroom initiatives and other school improvement efforts. After excelling in this position, I was named divisional best teacher (Female) twice. I received a scholarship from the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education to support school leaders in pursuing an MSc in Education at a UK university. This experience allowed me to read numerous journal articles that enhanced my understanding of school leadership.

While reading research on school leadership, I became interested in knowing more about school leadership and how my new understanding might be applied in school settings. One of my lecturers recommended reading several leadership journals, such as Bush and Glover (2003, 2014), Northouse (2015), Raven (2008), and Shonhiwa (2016). It was interesting because this was my first experience engaging with academic literature related to school leadership. So, I dedicated a significant amount of time to these readings. I often spent late at night in the university library, immersing myself in leadership journals. I acknowledged many challenges that school leaders face and the strategies for navigating them. These, in turn, inspired me to begin researching school leadership in Bangladesh, to contribute at a policy level in Bangladesh

to help headteachers navigate the challenges they encounter as they seek to undertake school improvement initiatives.

The combination of my personal experience, dedication to the country's primary education growth, professional growth, and enhancement of my academic career has driven my passion for doing research in school leadership. My goal is to provide insights that can empower headteachers to navigate challenges and foster meaningful change in the school setting.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This study investigated the headteachers' leadership role in implementing school improvement initiatives in three Bangladeshi primary schools. Its significance is multifaceted, encompassing methodological, theoretical, and practical contributions to school leadership practices in Bangladeshi primary schools. Considering the discussion in section 1.1, this is, as far as I am aware, the first empirical study to examine headteacher leadership practices in the context of primary school improvement in Bangladesh using educational ethnographic research and applying Foucault's theory as a frame for analysis. In Bangladesh, literature often explores the challenges schools face, but few of them examine the headteachers' role in navigating those challenges. Instead, they articulate various stakeholders' roles in making school improvements. However, an in-depth study on headteachers' leadership in Bangladeshi primary schools has not yet been conducted.

Thus, this study is significant as it emphasises the headteacher's role and how stakeholders articulate the headteacher's role in school improvement. Including stakeholders like teachers, parents, school managing committee members, community leaders, and education officers is important because headteachers' leadership cannot occur in isolation; it is largely experienced, interpreted, and sometimes shaped by them. Listening to their perspectives reveals how headteachers' leadership is understood in daily school life and offers a more complete and realistic view of leadership practices. Existing literature focuses on traditional headteacher leadership models, such as transformational leadership (Islam, Rahman, and Islam, 2023), instructional leadership (Uddin, Akhter, and Hena, 2018; Ananda, 2021) and managerial and democratic leadership styles (Ali, 2011; Hoque, 2007), overlooking how headteachers are shaped by and participate in the enactment of power. However, this study uses Foucault's

theory to examine the power relations between headteachers and key stakeholders as headteachers implemented various school improvement initiatives.

In addition, many studies on school improvement use interviews, surveys, and case studies, which often provide limited opportunities to capture the in-depth, naturalistic details of headteachers' day-to-day interactions and lived experiences. However, the current study adopts an ethnographic approach to generate richer, more contextualised insights into school headteachers' leadership practices in natural settings. This decision was informed by international ethnographic research on educational leadership (Reeves et al., 2013; Zaharlick, 1992; Erickson, 1984; Wilson, 1977). These studies demonstrate how ethnographic approaches can generate strategies and actions to address challenges while advancing the broader aims of educational research, particularly the improvement of education and schooling. By conducting observations in natural settings, ethnographers can immerse themselves in the social context, thereby gaining a comprehensive understanding of social dynamics. Drawing on these studies, this research employs participant observation, informal conversations, and document review to explore how headteachers in Bangladeshi government primary schools experience and enact leadership in their everyday environments.

More practically, this research holds great significance as it offers in-depth insights into the daily experiences of headteachers experiences:- how they interacted with key stakeholders such as teachers, parents, SMC members, PTA members, the community, and the education officers to improve their schools; what challenges they faced in doing so; and how they navigated power as they sought to exercise their leadership in support of school improvement.

Moreover, beyond its methodological, theoretical, and practical contributions, this study offers valuable insights for school leadership practices and education policy in Bangladeshi primary education. By emphasising headteachers' daily interactions and strategies for managing power dynamics through stakeholder engagement, the findings can inform the development of training programs for headteachers. These programs can foster effective and sustainable school improvements. Over time, this can enhance headteachers' leadership abilities, leading to better teacher development and improved student achievement. Additionally, this research lays the groundwork for future studies and supports evidence-based interventions that strengthen educational leadership and governance in Bangladesh over the long term.

However, the current study's findings may be limited, as it involves participants from only three primary schools and therefore may not fully reflect the diversity and complexity of the broader educational landscape.

1.5 Structure of the Study

This study is organised into nine chapters. Chapter One presents the statement of the problem, the aim of the study and the research questions guiding the study. It also includes the researcher's motivation and the significance of the study.

Chapter Two provides the background of the study. It begins with a brief background on Bangladesh and its historical context of education, then focuses on the educational structure in Bangladesh. It then explains the various initiatives of Primary Educational Development Programmes (PEDP) and the School Level Improvement Plan (SLIP) to support primary school improvement. This is followed by a discussion of the formation and responsibility of the school managing committee, along with the association of parents and teachers. The following section offers an overview of the primary education management system in Bangladesh, detailing the training that headteachers and teachers receive, as well as the role and responsibilities of headteachers. The chapter concludes with a consideration of school infrastructure development and resource allocation.

Chapter Three is a literature review that critically analyses the empirical literature related to the study's topic and research questions. Besides the introduction and conclusion, the chapter is divided into seven sections. The first section focuses on challenges in school improvement. Secondly, it explores the headteacher's role in school leadership. Then, it examines headteachers and vision related to school improvement. Next, it describes the headteachers' role as an academic supervisor. The subsequent section describes headteachers' roles in ensuring the quality of the learning environment. This is followed by a discussion of literature concerned with the role of the headteacher in staff mentoring, then the final section examines headteachers and decentralisation of power and how these dynamic factors hinder school improvement initiatives.

Chapter Four presents the theoretical framework focusing on three levels of Foucault's power: Subjectivity and ethics, Governmentality, and disciplinary power.

Chapter Five presents the methodology of this study. It explains the study's philosophical assumptions before describing the research design and methodology (educational ethnography). Next, the chapter discusses participant sampling and offers a thorough explanation of the data collection methods and analysis processes. The chapter further highlights the researcher's positionality and outlines measures taken to enhance the research's trustworthiness and to address ethical concerns.

Chapter Six presents thematic findings for the first research question. It is structured into five sub-themes, each reflecting various aspects of the headteacher's role in leading school improvement initiatives. Each theme is discussed concerning the data collected and literature reviewed. The first sub-theme addresses the headteacher's role in ensuring and managing the quality of the learning environment. The second sub-theme explains the headteachers' role in securing funds and resources for school improvement. The third sub-theme highlights the role of the headteacher in ensuring a sustained focus on student attendance and academic success. The fourth sub-theme focuses on the role of headteachers in promoting active parental engagement in support of school improvement. The fifth sub-theme explores the role of the headteacher in ensuring teachers are well-prepared, trained and motivated for effective classroom practices.

Chapter Seven presents the findings in response to research question two. It analyses the data using Foucault's concept of power, specifically subjectivity, governmentality, and disciplinary power (which encompasses hierarchical observation, normalising judgment, and examination).

Chapter Eight presents thematic findings for the third research question. This chapter has two sections: challenges and opportunities for headteachers in leading school improvement initiatives. The challenges section is structured into five sub-themes. The first sub-theme identifies teachers' motivation/demotion and school improvement as the main challenge for headteachers. The second explores how parents' financial limitations impact students' performance, affecting headteachers' efforts. The third highlights a common challenge in Bangladeshi primary schools: inconsistent SMC member attendance at meetings and improvement activities. The fourth sub-theme indicates that a lack of parental support frustrates headteachers in reaching their goals. The fifth addresses power complexities involving

headteachers' engagement with government officials, whose misuse of authority undermines primary education and complicates improvement efforts.

The opportunities section includes three sub-themes. The first subtheme focuses on headteachers' resilience, commitment, and leadership, which are crucial for enhancing their schools. The second subtheme explains how a shared school vision creates opportunities for improvement. The final subtheme highlights the role of increased mentoring by headteachers in fostering staff accountability and dedication, ultimately creating opportunities for achieving teaching and learning outcomes.

The final chapter concludes the research and is organised alongside the introduction into six sections. The first section summarises the key findings and resulting recommendations. The second section details the study's contributions to knowledge. The third section examines the study's limitations. The fourth section outlines the study's implications. The fifth section highlights areas for future research. The final section shares the researcher's reflections on the PhD journey.

Chapter 2: Background and Context

2.1 Introduction

The system of education in Bangladesh is influenced by a complex blend of colonial legacy, traditional Bangladeshi culture, Islamic traditions, and global developments. According to Rahman et al. (2010), the current education system in Bangladesh is more or less an inheritance of the British colonial period. As Al Mahmud (2025) notes, although efforts were made after independence to promote Bengali and strengthen national identity, the British curriculum has had a lasting influence, making English a dominant language in education. According to Chowdhury and Sarkar (2018), the current formal education system in Bangladesh is broadly divided into two main types: general education and religious (madrasah) education.

Bangladesh's traditional education system has three main levels: primary, secondary, and higher education. This is rooted in conventional Bangladeshi culture, which continues to influence education by fostering a sense of community in schools, promoting values, and respecting stakeholders. It also expects schooling to reinforce national identity and social cohesion. Islamic traditions play a significant role in the education system, as evident in the madrasa network, the inclusion of religious studies in the national curriculum, and a focus on moral development. The history of Islamic education in Bangladesh dates back to the arrival of Islam in the region, with madrasas becoming key providers of education for Muslims from the 13th century onwards, significantly shaping the country's educational landscape (Al Mahmud, 2025).

According to Mousumi and Kusakabe (2021), alongside the mainstream system, a parallel network of religious schools exists for students pursuing Islamic studies. There are two main types: Alia Madrasas, which are state-supported, and Qoumi Madrasas, which are privately funded through national and international donations. Primary-level education in madrasas is called Ebtedayee. Finally, the sector is being reshaped by global developments, including international agendas such as Education for All and the Sustainable Development Goals. These global forces directly informed the National Education Policy of 2010, which was adopted to ensure universal education for all and align with international commitments such as the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Similarly, the Constitution of Bangladesh (1972), Article 17, underscores the state's responsibility to eradicate illiteracy within a legally specified timeframe and to establish a mass-oriented, uniform, and universal education system. Together,

these approaches connect education to societal needs and reflect the ambition to develop a well-trained, motivated, and responsible nation.

The National Education Policy in Bangladesh was adopted in 2010 to provide universal education for all and fulfil the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). The Constitution of Bangladesh (1972), Article 17 declares that to eradicate illiteracy within a legally specified timeframe, the Constitution established a mass-oriented, uniform, and universal education system. This approach connects education to societal needs, aiming to develop well-trained and motivated individuals. Following this regulation, the primary education of Bangladesh has achieved significant improvements in terms of student enrolment and gender parity through a variety of schemes (Sommers, 2013). However, the inadequate quality of teaching and learning in the classroom remains evident in overall education (Islam, 2018). Furthermore, the bureaucratic administration system in Bangladesh hinders policy implementation, particularly in relation to school improvement initiatives (Mullick, Deppeler, and Sharma, 2012; Prodhon, 2016; Mousumi and Kusakabe, 2021).

This chapter examines the efforts at school improvement in establishing Bangladesh's primary education through the various interventions undertaken by the Bangladesh Government in collaboration with international donors. The chapter begins with a brief overview of Bangladesh and its historical context in education. It then focuses on the educational structure in Section 2.4. The chapter discusses various educational development programmes in primary education in section 2.5. Section 2.6 explores the School Level Improvement Program for government primary schools, referred to as 'SLIP'. This is followed by a discussion of the formation and responsibilities of the school managing committee, along with the association of parents and teachers in support of school improvement initiatives (2.6.1). Section 2.7 then provides an overview of the management system in primary education in Bangladesh. Section 2.8 briefly discusses the training received by head teachers and teachers in Bangladesh. After that, 2.9 explores infrastructure development and resource allocation, which are significant elements for ensuring a child-friendly environment in primary education in Bangladesh. The final section (2.10) provides a summary of the chapter.

2.2. Bangladesh: Brief Historical Context

Fig. 1: Map of Bangladesh

Bangladesh ranks as the eighth most populous country globally, covering an area of 1,47,570 square kilometres. It is bordered by India to the north, west, and northeast, Myanmar to the southeast, and the Bay of Bengal to the south (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Bangladesh, 2025). According to the most recent figures, the population of Bangladesh is 165,158,616 (Ministry of Planning, 2022). Until 1947 Bangladesh was a part of the larger Bengal region in Northeast India. Following its 1947 independence from Britain, Bangladesh was a part of Pakistan's territories until 1971, when it became independent. By the beginning of

1952, the Language Movement took a serious turn; however, East Pakistan (Bangladesh) students and intellectuals demanded that Bangla be made one of the state languages.

Following significant controversy and sacrifices related to the language issue, East Pakistan's conclusive demand was for Bangla to be recognised as the official language on February 21, 1952. Since then, February 21 has been annually observed to honour the martyrs of the Language Movement. On November 17, 1999, UNESCO adopted a resolution designating February 21 as International Mother Language Day (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2003).

2.3 Education in Bangladesh

The government of Bangladesh announced in 1973 that all of the nation's primary schools would be nationalised. After independence, the first Education Commission in Bangladesh was established to develop an education policy led by eminent scientist and educationist Dr. Qudrat-e-Khuda (Ministry of Education, 2010). In May 1974, the Khuda Commission proposed a modern, science-oriented education policy, which the government subsequently approved.

However, this policy was never implemented due to the political turmoil in 1975, which led to the assassination of the country's founder (Ministry of Education, 2010). In the following decades, six more education-related policies and reports were created, but none of their recommendations were fully implemented due to political unrest and conflicting government agendas (Ministry of Education, 2010; Rahman, 2020). As a result, no national education policy was successfully enacted in Bangladesh for the next four decades, with the most recent Education Commission in 2010 being the only attempt to establish a national education policy (Ministry of Education, 2010).

To achieve the goal of universal primary education, the government of Bangladesh implemented several initiatives, as reflected in Article 17 of the People's Republic of Bangladesh's constitution to establish “establishing a uniform mass oriented and universal system of education and extending free and compulsory education to all children to such stage as determined by law” (Directorate of Primary Education, 2015, p.1). This goal was then included in government policies, programs, and initiatives (Directorate of Primary Education, 2015). Prior to this, the 1990 World Conference on Education for All (EFA), held at Jomtien, Thailand, led a remarkable basic educational improvement in Bangladesh (Latif, 2005). A significant portion of education policy and practice in the 1990s drew from the Primary Education Compulsory Act of 1990, which was enacted by Parliament in 1993 (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2003). The Act upholds several principles, such as ensuring that no child is denied an education and that disparities in primary education related to gender, family, income, ethnic or cultural differences, or geographical inaccessibility are removed (Choudhury and Rahaman, 2015).

As part of this policy thrust, a separate ministry-level division, the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (MOPME), was established in 1992 (Latif, 2005) to ensure the quality of primary education. Recognising the strategic challenges of realising EFA goals, the Government of Bangladesh has adopted various development projects, including the Primary Education Development Program in Bangladesh (PEDP) (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2003). Since 2010, education policy has been driven through four iterations of Bangladesh's primary education development programme (PEDP). This is outlined in detail in Section 2.5.

2.4 Structure of the Education System in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, the education system is structured into three broad levels: primary, secondary, and higher education (Prodhan, 2016). However, when broken down further, primary education includes both pre-primary and primary stages, while higher education consists of higher secondary and tertiary levels. Overall, the system consists of five stages: pre-primary education, primary education, secondary education, higher secondary education, and tertiary education (Directorate of Primary Education, 2011).

The Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (MoPME) and the Directorate of Primary Education (DPE) are responsible for Bangladesh's primary education administration system (Directorate of Primary Education, 2011). These comprise government or public primary schools, non-government or private primary schools, Bangla-medium and English-medium kindergarten schools, and Madrasah primary schools (Ministry of Education, 2010). The majority of primary schools in the country are government-operated, where most students pursue their studies in government primary schools (Directorate of Primary Education, 2011). However, Madrasah primary schools enrol a large number of students, while English Medium schools are limited in number and are mainly located in towns and divisional cities (Prodhan, 2016). The government provides the majority of the funding for primary schools (Directorate of Primary Education, 2011), but the local School Managing Committee (SMC) supervises all government primary schools (Mousumi and Kusakabe, 2021) and works with headteachers in various school improvement activities (Saha, 2023).

The Directorate of Primary Education (2011) notes that the responsibility for secondary and higher education in Bangladesh lies with the Ministry of Education, which also oversees madrasahs and other religious schools. The private sector works in collaboration with the government to provide much of the secondary and tertiary education. Secondary education extends over seven years and is organised into three stages: junior secondary (Grades VI–VIII), secondary (Grades IX–X), and higher secondary (Grades XI–XII). Students sit for the Secondary School Certificate (SSC) examination at the end of Grade X and the Higher Secondary School Certificate (HSSC) at the end of Grade XII.

The secondary education sector is dominated by non-government schools, which operate under government regulations and receive state support, while government schools make up only a

small proportion. In addition to the general education stream, secondary education is also available through madrasahs and technical or vocational institutions (Government of Bangladesh, 2020).

According to the Government of Bangladesh (2020), higher secondary courses are provided by non-government colleges. These programmes are either attached to secondary schools or integrated within degree-level institutions. Similar to the secondary sector, non-government colleges receive substantial government support, particularly in the form of teacher salary subsidies and funding for infrastructure.

Beyond the higher secondary level, tertiary education is provided through colleges and universities, with programmes typically lasting from two to six years. Colleges offer both bachelor's passes and honours degrees, while universities provide a wider range of undergraduate and postgraduate programmes. Colleges are affiliated with the National University, whereas universities function as autonomous institutions under the University Grants Commission (Directorate of Primary Education, 2011).

Aside from these mainstream streams, the Directorate of Primary Education (2011) notes that Bangladesh also has two types of Islamic faith-based madrasah education institutions. In addition to traditional mosque-linked maktabas, which teach the Quran and religious practices to young children who often attend regular primary schools, government-supported Aliya madrasahs offer a full range of education from primary to tertiary levels. The Qawmi madrasah system also provides pre-primary to tertiary programmes but does not receive government support or supervision.

Bangladesh has made significant progress in recent years, particularly in increasing primary school enrolment, especially for girls (Government of Bangladesh, 2020). Between 1980 and 1995, the net enrolment rate rose from 62% to 79%, while girls' enrolment increased from 47% to 73% (see Table 1), showing a narrowing gender gap (Chowdhury et al., 2002). Since then, enrolment and gender parity have continued to improve.

Table 1: Primary enrolment rate in Bangladesh, 1980- 1995 (figures represent percentage of the total population)

Year	Boys	Girls	Total
1980	76	47	62
1985	67	55	61
1990	76	64	70
1995	84	73	79

Source: Chowdhury et al., 2002

According to World Bank data reported by CEIC (2021), the Gender Parity Index (GPI) for primary school enrolment in Bangladesh reached 1.018 in 2021, meaning that the number of girls enrolled slightly exceeded that of boys. This represents a major shift from the early 1970s, when the GPI was only 0.486, indicating severe gender disparity at that time. The data also shows that gender parity in primary education steadily improved over the decades, peaking at 1.093 in 2020 before stabilising around equality in 2021 (CEIC Data, 2021). By 2023, the Annual Primary School Census reported that total enrolment from pre-primary to grade five reached nearly 19.7 million students, with 51.4% of them being girls (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023). These consistent trends demonstrate that since 1995, Bangladesh has achieved almost full gender balance in primary education enrolment. In addition, it revealed that the total number of working teachers (altogether government and non-government primary schools) was 650,293, out of which the total number of female teachers was 62.6% (407,055). In 2023, there were 384,513 government primary school working teachers, out of which 65.5% were female (251,782).

Table 2: Teachers number by school's type

School's Type	Teacher (Male)	Teacher (Female)	Total Teacher	(%) Female
Government Primary Schools	132,731	251,782	384,513	65.5
Private School	9,484	17,362	26,846	64.7
Ebtadayee Madrasa	13,246	5,853	19,099	30.6
Kindergarten	65,769	106,636	172,405	61.9
NGO Schools	1,528	5,468	6,996	78.2
Attached to High Madrasa	9,198	2,079	11,277	18.4
Primary Sections of High Schools	7,497	10,037	17,534	57.2
Shishu Kalyan Trust School	305	681	986	69.1
Other NGO Centres	216	2,850	3,066	93.0
Others	3,264	4307	7571	56.9
Total	243,238	407,055	650,293	62.6

Source: Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2023).

This study focuses only on government primary schools.

2.4.1 Pre-Primary education

The most recent education policy from 2010 focuses on introducing pre-primary schooling to help children begin their formal education and prepare for school. To achieve this goal, a one-year pre-primary program should be implemented for children aged five and older, with plans to expand it to include children aged four and up in the future (Ministry of Education, 2010). The Fourth Primary Education Development Programme (PEDP4) prioritises early learning to boost overall enrolment and the development of children in primary education (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023). In line with this goal, in 2014, a one-year Pre-Primary Education (PPE) program for 5-year-old children was implemented in government primary schools. And according to the Annual Primary School Census, 2023 report, about 3.4 million pre-primary pupils are enrolled nationwide (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023).

Table 3: Student Enrolment (Pre-primary) Covered in 2023

Schools' Type	Number of pre-primary students in different types of Schools		
	Boys	Girls	Total
Government Primary School (GPS)	818,921	877,752	1,696,673
Private Schools	66,976	66,770	133,746
Ebtadayee Madrasa	37,041	34,699	71,740
Kindergarten	612,108	585,312	1,197,420
NGO Schools	60,114	59,468	119,582
Madrasha attached Primary Sections	20,664	19,433	40,097
High Schools attached Primary Schools	57,211	61,050	118,261
Shishu Kalyan Trust School	2,161	2,228	4,389
NGO Learning Centres	24,796	26,724	51,520
Others	32,204	30,647	62,851
Total	1,732,196	1,764,083	3,496,279

Source: Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2023).

2.4.2 Two Years Pre-primary Education in Bangladesh

The Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (MoPME) (2023) has launched a two-year pre-primary education program (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023) to align with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This initiative aims to ensure that all children receive quality pre-primary education by 2030.

2.4.3 Primary Education

Bangladesh has committed to achieving Universal Primary Education following Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4). The aim is to guarantee that every child obtains an exceptional basic education by 2030 (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023). Consequently, Bangladesh's primary education system is designed to maximise the enrolment of all children in the primary school age group, which is around 6 to 10 years old (ibid). Although Bangladesh has significantly improved gender equality and enrolment success, many students continue to drop out, resulting in quality education remaining a significant issue (Directorate of Primary Education, 2020). Sustainable improvement Goal 4 (SDG4) highlights the need for consistently improving quality primary education by increasing children's access to quality classroom instruction and learning (ibid).

Table 4: Number of Schools (Pre-primary to Grade Five), 2023

Schools' Type	Number of Schools	Schools (%)
Government Primary School (GPS)	65567	57.2
Private Schools	6134	5.4
Ebtadayee Madrasa	4425	3.9
Kindergarten	26461	23.1
NGO Schools	3307	2.9
Madrasha attached Primary Sections	2909	2.5
High Schools attached Primary Schools	1892	1.7
Shishu Kalyan Trust School	203	0.2
NGO learning Centres	2237	2.0
Others	1495	1.3
Total	114,630	100.0

Table 5: Student Enrolment (Grade One to Grade Five), 2023

Schools' Type	Number Of Enrolled primary students in different type of Schools		
	Boys	Girls	Total
Government Primary School (GPS)	4,371,781	4,917,361	9,289,142
Private Schools	352,412	351,730	704,142
Ebtadayee Madrasa	312,053	299,062	611,115
Kindergarten	1,892,342	1,783,613	3,675,955
NGO Schools	206,076	210,503	416,579
High Madrasha attached Primary Sections	218,834	222,268	441,102
High Schools attached Primary Schools	329,254	356,520	685,774
Shishu Kalyan Trust School	12,448	13,509	25,957
NGO Learning Centres	108,095	116,889	224,984
Others	73,707	68,949	142,656
Total	7,877,002	8,340,404	16,217,406

Source: Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2023).

2.4.4. Primary Education in Class 6 to 8

The National Education Policy 2010 stated that primary education should continue to Grade 8. Accordingly, within 65,567 government primary schools, following the most recent national education policy of 2010, 696 primary schools have already launched sixth, seventh and eighth grades in their school (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023).

Table 6: Government Primary Schools students' enrolment (Grade 6 to Grade 8)

	Schools' number	Boys	Girls	Total
Total	655	39126	54013	93139

Source: Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023

However, the above data highlights the substantial gender gap in favour of female students remaining enrolled in primary education.

2.4.5 Advancing Gender Equity within Inclusive Education in Bangladesh

Inclusive education represents a holistic approach aimed at creating educational systems that are more adaptable to the diverse needs of all learners. According to UNESCO (2025), this approach emphasises gender equality, works to eliminate discrimination within the learning environment, and ensures that no individual is left behind. Although significant development has been made over the past ten years, millions remain deprived of their right to education, and learning opportunities are still unevenly distributed. Worldwide, one in every five children, youth and adolescents is wholly excluded from educational access. Factors such as poverty, geographical location, language, gender, disability, religion, ethnicity, and displacement or migration status persist in dictating and restricting opportunities (UNESCO, 2025).

The key idea of inclusive education is to include all children and marginalised students in regular classrooms in a uniform educational system (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023). Like many other countries, Bangladesh has also taken many initiatives to improve schools by promoting inclusive education (ibid). Bangladesh has made significant progress in removing gender gaps in primary education (Asian Development Bank, 2010). The APSC 2023 indicates that pre-primary to grade five, the percentage of girls' enrolment is 51.4%, demonstrating a significant reduction in the gender disparity between boys and girls (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023). Bangladesh has also embedded within all policy initiatives and international declarations a commitment to inclusive education to ensure equal access to all children regardless of educational circumstances. Moreover, the constitution of

Bangladesh, Articles 17 and 28 (3) clearly state that the country should ensure education for all children without creating discrimination.

According to Article 17, the country will adopt effective initiatives to launch a consistent, mass-oriented, and global education system to ensure all children get free and compulsory education, which will be established by law (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2000). Further, Article 28(3) of the Constitution stipulates that all citizens, regardless of their religion, colour, race, background, gender, place of birth, or any disability, shall have equal access to any resort or public place for entertainment or to admission to any educational institution within the country (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2000). Ensuring access for all children in the mainstream education system is central to improving primary education. In addition, Bangladesh has started the journey towards IE by enacting the Compulsory Primary Education Act 1990 and promising to accomplish the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) (United Nations, 2008), which also articulate the rights of all children to access mainstream education. The recent Bangladesh National Education Policy 2010 and the Second Primary Education Development Program (PEDP-2) also promote inclusive education (Ahmed and Douse, 2019).

2.5 Primary Education Development Programme (PEDP)

As mentioned in section 2.3, the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (MOPME) was established in 1992 as a separate ministry-level division to ensure the quality of primary education and achieve the Education for All (EFA) goals (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2003). The Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (MOPME) has launched several initiatives in basic education, including the Primary Education Development Programs (PEDP) 1, 2, 3, and now 4, all aimed at fulfilling the relevant EFA Goals.

According to the Directorate of Primary Education (2015), this national program (PEDP) is dedicated to enhancing primary education through various initiatives that began with PEDP-1 (1997-2003). The first Primary Education Development Programme (PEDP1) comprised about 27 separate projects, each funded independently by one of the eight participating Development Partners (DPs) or the Government of Bangladesh (GoB). Each project operated with its own implementation unit alongside the government system (Ahmed and Douse, 2019). PEDP I (1997-2003) focused on enhancing key areas such as enrolment, completion, quality, and monitoring (Directorate of Primary Education, 2011). Although PEDP-1 did not involve long-

term initiatives (Directorate of Primary Education, 2015), some projects within PEDP-1 successfully met their targets and intended outputs. However, it was widely acknowledged that their overall impact was minimal, as they failed to tackle the policy and systemic challenges critical for improving quality (Ahmed and Douse, 2019).

The Second Primary Education Development Programme (PEDP-II), which ran from 2004 to 2011, was a subsector initiative with the Directorate of Primary Education (DPE). It focused on implementing four key components: administrative development and building capacity; improving schools and classrooms' teaching and learning quality; schools' physical infrastructure development; and providing necessary support for equitable access (Directorate of Primary Education, 2011 and 15; Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2003). The Government of Bangladesh and 11 external development partners financed PEDP II, with the Asian Development Bank (ADB) leading the initiative (Ahmed, 2011). The primary aim of PEDP II was to alleviate poverty by ensuring universal primary education and promoting sustainable development, aligning with the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) (Directorate of Primary Education, 2011).

According to the Directorate of Primary Education (2011), the first component of PEDP II aimed to build greater management capacity at the central and school levels. To enhance organisational capacity, this program includes providing staff professional development training to train the staff. This component also covers supervising and evaluating by the Upazila Primary Education office, which, with support from the Upazila Resource Centre, aims to reduce students' absenteeism, increase contact hours, and establish additional single-shift schools. The second component of PEDP II aimed to enhance all the schools' teaching and learning quality to meet the Primary School Quality Level (PSQL) criteria. This component includes activities like SLIP implementation, SMC training, in-service teacher training, and recruiting headteachers and teachers to meet this goal. Component three also involves building classrooms to decrease class sizes, providing safe drinking water and toilet facilities, and maintaining equipment to ensure all children have equal access. Component four aimed to enhance management strategies that encourage children who have never attended formal education or have dropped out of primary school due to poverty, disability, or other reasons to enrol in schools. These activities involved making the curriculum more relevant and providing stipends to students.

PEDP3 began immediately after the conclusion of PEDP2, with oversight and management provided by GoB line agencies. Its components were integrated into the DPE's work programme, guaranteeing ongoing support and a greater chance of sustainability (Ahmed and Douse, 2019). PEDP 3 is the flagship sub-sector program to improve primary education in Bangladesh and has played a crucial role in fostering positive changes (Choudhury and Rahaman, 2015). According to the Directorate of Primary Education (2015, p. vi & vii), the goal of PEDP3 was to confirm "quality education for all our children" and the overall goal was to set up "an efficient, inclusive and equitable primary education system delivering effective and relevant child-friendly learning to all Bangladesh's children from pre-primary through Grade V primary." PEDP 3, launched in 2011 and concluding in 2017, focused on six key result areas: (i) improved Learning Outcomes, ensuring all children achieve subject-specific and grade-appropriate skills in the classroom, (ii) ensuring access and participation for all children to pre-primary and primary education in various educational settings, including formal, non-formal, and madrasah (religious school) (iii) reducing all forms of disparities- such as gender and regional variations - in participation, completion, and learning outcomes, (iv) encouraging decentralisation at both the Upazila and school levels, (v) Improving the effectiveness of budget allocation, and (vi) enhancing Programme Planning and Management. Under PEDP 3, a separate division was established to run Second Chance Education, new positions for the Leadership training centre, and resource personnel for the Primary Teachers Training Institute (PTI), implementing the Diploma in Primary Education course (DPED). PEDP 3 also took initiatives to implement Each Child Learns (ECL) to tackle the issues related to quality teaching and learning for classroom practices. ECL sought to enhance the teaching methods employed by teachers and create a robust framework to hold teachers accountable for each child's learning, thus leading to notable improvements in overall classroom and school performance. Furthermore, throughout the PEDP-3 period, a coordinated timetable was followed to enhance, test, revise, and implement the curriculum, teachers' guides, and textbooks for every subject across all primary grades nationwide.

The Fourth Primary Education Development Program (PEDP4) reflects the Government of Bangladesh's commitment to achieving universal primary education (Directorate of Primary Education, 2023). Sponsored by the Bangladesh Government and supported by various development partners, this initiative spans the fiscal years 2018-2019 to 2022-2023. PEDP-4

builds upon and continues the efforts of PEDP-1, PEDP-2, and PEDP-3, which collectively aim to ensure quality education for every child in Bangladesh's primary schools- from pre-primary to primary five via a competent, equitable and inclusive education system (Directorate of Primary Education, 2023). This development project was planned to be implemented over five years (2018/19–2022/23) and covered one year of pre-primary and primary one to five. The Directorate of Primary Education (2018) states that PEDP4 aims to provide quality primary education for all children in Bangladesh. This goal is pursued through needs-based infrastructure development and three key result areas: (a) high-quality teaching and learning, (b) all children's equitable access and spontaneous participation in education, and (c) best management, good governance, with adequate financing. The goal of the first component of PEDP4 was to enable all students to get the necessary grade-level competencies outlined in the curriculum to employ quality classroom teaching-learning in nationwide schools. The second component focuses on creating learning environments that facilitate the involvement of every child in all communities while ensuring educational continuity. The third component aims to establish effective governance, good management, and sufficient funding of the primary education, allowing for the delivery of quality education that is inclusive, efficient, and equitable.

2.6 School Level Improvement Plan (SLIP)

The Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2023) outlines the School Level Improvement Plan (SLIP) guidelines for government primary schools. SLIP is a development initiative at the school level in Bangladesh, embodying the aspirations and expectations of the local school community. Additionally, SLIP serves as the foundational document for primary education and is a key development tool at the school level.

According to the Directorate of Primary Education (2015), SLIP is a school-level improvement plan created and carried out by the headteacher in collaboration with the SMC, PTA, and school community to make the school successful. SLIP seeks to tackle the school-related challenges associated with classroom learning results and completion rates at the primary education level (Directorate of Primary Education, 2022). To fulfil this goal, the Directorate of Primary Education has taken several initiatives, including decentralising primary education through the SLIP by encouraging local stakeholders to participate spontaneously in school improvement activities (Directorate of Primary Education, 2015).

The aim of SLIP (School Level Improvement Plan):

SLIP aims to provide integrated, balanced, and high-quality primary education by establishing its own fund through the collection of local resources, alongside government SLIP grants, with the active participation of the local people.

The Objective of SLIP

The primary aim of the SLIP is to advance and execute a plan at the school level alongside the participation of schools' stakeholders for the comprehensive advancement of primary education. According to the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2023), the overall objectives of the SLIPs are given below:

1. Ensuring quality primary education by improving the school's teaching and learning environment.
2. To ready children for entry into primary school via pre-primary education.
3. To create a non-discriminatory and balanced primary education environment through integrated education.
4. Developing schools as child-friendly institutes.
5. Decentralisation of planning and management activities at the school level.
6. Formulating and implementing realistic and need-based plans at the school level.
7. Building capacity in planning, implementation and school management for all stakeholders at the school level.
8. Involving teachers, students, parents, guardians, and the people of the school catchment area in school development activities.
9. Establishing close relationships between the local community and the school and creating a sense of ownership towards the school.
10. Ensuring the desired overall development of the school through a combination of locally collected resources and the slip grant.
11. Reducing the harmful effects of disasters on students, teachers, schools, and the education sector through disaster preparedness and response activities
12. Continuing educational activities during disasters and post-disaster periods.

The Stakeholders in the School

The Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2023) notes that the school stakeholders at primary schools are Headteachers, Teachers, Students, Parents, Former Students, School Community People, the School Managing Committee (SMC), Parents Teachers Association (PTA), Working and Retired government officials of the school area, Officers and employees of primary education departments, Social and Political Leaders, and Local Government Representatives.

Table 7: SLIP Formulation Team

Serial	Stakeholders	Title
1	Headteacher	Chairman
2	One member nominated by the SMC	Member
3	One member nominated by the PTA	Member
4	An educational enthusiasm who is the highest donor at the school	Member
5	A female teacher nominated by the ATEO/AUEO	Secretary

Source: The Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2023)

According to the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2023), the SLIP team's scope of work is:

1. Analysing the school's current situation, identifying issues, and determining immediate solutions.
2. Evaluating the needs for upgrading the school to meet the desired standards.
3. Estimating costs based on identified needs and identifying potential funding sources and amounts.
4. Engaging local community members in developing the SLIP and fostering strong connections between them and the school.
5. Motivating local philanthropists and organisations to contribute to school development initiatives.
6. Drafting the school development plan (SLIP).
7. Submitting the prepared SLIP to the SMC meeting for preliminary approval.

SLIP implementation:

According to the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2023),

1. The school's SMC will implement the SLIP approved by the Upazila/Thana Education Officer.
2. To implement the SLIP activities, the appropriate person will be identified, including the headteacher, assistant teacher, SMC member, and one or more PTA members to implement the program and specific responsibilities in writing.

3. A copy of the plan must be sent to the individuals designated by the headteacher.
4. The headteacher must collect the local donations with the SMC chairman and members.
5. Responsible persons must implement the assigned responsibilities promptly.
6. The monthly meeting of the SMC should review the progress of the SLIP implementation.
7. The SMC must take necessary measures to resolve problems arising during implementation and ensure timely implementation.
8. The headteacher should display a copy of the slip instructions on the notice board in the school office for everyone to see.
9. The head teacher must present the progress report on implementing the SLIP at the PTA's bimonthly meeting. The funding source must be mentioned at the meeting and included in the SLIP.

Table 8: Social Audit Committee (SAC) Formulation Team

1	PTA Chairman	Chairman
2	A member nominated by PTA chairman	member
3	A local donor/ educational enthusiasm	Member
4	A member from SMC (Excluding the member of the SLIP team)	Member
5	A female teacher associated with the school nominated by ATEO/AUEO (Excluding SMC members)	Secretary

Source: The Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023

Scope of work of the Social Audit Committee:

The Social Audit Committee will audit and evaluate the SLIP activities implemented by the SMC after implementation. The following items will be verified during the audit, and three copies of the audit and evaluation report will be prepared in the particular form.

1. Whether the tasks included in the plan have been completed correctly.
2. Whether the money has been spent in the specified sectors included in the plan.
3. Whether the vouchers related to the expenditure are appropriate or not.
4. Whether or not the vouchers related to the expenditure were at market rates or not.

Guideline for issuing SLIP grants:

1. The school will maintain a savings account at Sonali Bank or a state-run scheduled bank, titled 'School Level Improvement Plan (SLIP).

2. This account will be operated with the joint signatures of the headteacher and the school's SMC chairman.
3. If the school's SMC president is absent for an extended period for valid reasons, the accounts will be managed with the joint signature of an assistant teacher from the concerned school, nominated by the Upazila/Thana Education Officer in his stead. In this case, approval must be obtained from the Upazila/Thana Education Officer.

The main goal of SLIP is to empower SMCs to enhance their accountability and provide leadership consolidation (ibid). Although the SMC play a vital role in implementing the SLIP activity, the PTA also has an important role by encouraging the local community to take part in the school improvement initiatives. Both the SMC and the PTA play significant roles in collecting funds from the local community. Each school receives funding from the government known as the SLIP grant, which is disbursed by Upazila Education Officers and overseen and monitored by the SMC and SLIP team (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023). According to the Directorate of Primary Education (2022), on average, in 2019-2020, every school received a SLIP grant of more than 50,000 BDT (minimum 50,000 BDT and maximum 150,000 BDT). The SLIP committee and the SMC have the freedom and authority to purchase need-based teaching learning material; however, they must follow the centralised instructions and ensure consent from the upazila/Thana Education Officer (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023).

2.6.1 School Management Committee and the Parent-Teacher Association Guidelines

2.6.1.1 School Management Committee (SMC)

The national education policy emphasises decentralising existing primary schools by significantly empowering the SMC to increase its effectiveness (Ministry of Education, 2010). According to the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2019), the government primary schools' school management committee will consist of eleven members, including the chairman. The chairman and vice-chairman will be appointed among these eleven members, except the head teacher and the teacher representative from the relevant primary school. However, a minimum of a Bachelor's degree is a requirement for the chairman to be nominated.

The responsibilities of the committee's member secretary will be carried out by the ex-officio head or acting head teacher.

Table 9: School Managing Committee (SMC) Formulation Team

1.1	School Headteacher /Acting Headteacher	Secretary
1.2	One Educational Enthusiastic Female Guardian (Minimum SSC Pass)	Member
1.3	One Educational Enthusiastic Male Guardian (Minimum SSC Pass)	Member
1.4	One Landlord/Heir of the Landlord (if any) of the school.	Member
1.5	One Teacher of any Government/Private Secondary School near the concerned Primary School in the same Upazila	Member
1.6	One teacher representative - member selected from among the teachers at the concerned primary school.	Member
1.7 & 1.8	Two female guardians were selected from among the guardians	Member
1.9 & 1.10	Two male guardian members were selected from among the parents	Member
1.11	Member of Union Parishad / Municipal Commissioner/councillor of City Corporation.	Member

Source: Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2019.

The Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2019) stated in section 2.9 that if any member of the School Management Committee is absent for three consecutive meetings without notifying the chairman in writing or is incapacitated by death or any other reason, his membership shall be deemed cancelled. Section 2.13 states that the meeting of the SMC shall be held on any day of the last week of every English month after class teaching activities or on holidays, and section 2.14 states that at least six members need to be present in the meeting to fulfil the meeting quorum.

According to the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (2019), SMCs have several duties and responsibilities, including making sure that teachers and students attend class regularly, overseeing school activities, preventing students from being physically punished, working with the headteacher to implement School Level Improvement Plan (SLIP) projects, and approving school expenses. To promote accountability, learning quality, and equal access, the SMC's primary goal is to increase locals' involvement in school management by increasing awareness of roles and responsibilities and decentralising specific authority and resources at the school level (ibid).

2.6.1.2 Parent-Teacher Association (PTA)

The 2010 National Education Policy emphasises the need for parental involvement in primary school activities, particularly encouraging female guardians to participate in the Teacher-

Parent Association so that the committee’s activities function more actively (Ministry of Education, 2010).

Table 10: Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) Formulation Team

1	One member elected by the general members of the concerned Primary School’s PTA	Chairman
2	One member elected by the general members of the concerned Primary School’s PTA	Vice Chairman
3	Headteacher (ex-officio) of the concerned Primary School	Secretary
4	One teacher is elected by the general members from among the teachers.	Member
5-7	The general members elect three male guardians from among the guardians of their respective school.	Members
8-10	Three guardians, exclusively female, are elected by the general members from within the cohort of guardians representing the respective school members.	Members

Source: Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2000

According to the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education's (2000) PTA Committee forms, every school, including teachers, parents, and guardians of children aged 3 to 12 in school catchment areas, are considered members of the PTA. The PTA working committee comprises 10 members, including two teachers and eight parents (at least three mothers). The key role and responsibilities of the PTA include assisting the teachers with child surveys, assisting schools in promoting enrolment and enhancing students’ attendance lowering the dropout rate, and fostering positive relationships between the school’s community and the teachers (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2000).

The PTA also supports the school administration and teachers in planning guardians' meetings, collecting donations and facilitating children's admission (Haque, 2018). However, the researcher found that community members' participation did not increase as anticipated, highlighting that decentralisation in primary education was limited (Mullick, Deppeler, and Sharma, 2012). Education Sector Plan (ESP) fiscal years 2020/21-2024/25 states that the centralisation of all government primary education activities and their local implementation under central direction has led to a lack of local participation in the development and implementation of plans (Government of Bangladesh, 2020).

2.7 Management System in Primary Education in Bangladesh

Bangladesh operates two educational ministries: The Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (MoPME) oversees primary education, while the Ministry of Education (MoE) manages secondary and higher education. The country features one of the most centralised education systems globally, serving nearly 40 million students, supported by 200,000 institutions and around one million educators and staff members (Government of Bangladesh, 2020). The Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (MOPME) is the ultimate management authority for primary education in Bangladesh (Directorate of Primary Education, 2016). MOPME is actively involved in policy implementation, although the Directorate of Primary Education carries other responsibilities, such as school supervision and development initiatives (Directorate of Primary Education, 2018).

According to Moyer (2014), primary schools were governed by the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (MoPME) until 1981, when the ministry was reformed, establishing a separate administrative sector called the Directorate of Primary Education (DPE). The vision of the Department of Primary Education (DPE) is to provide quality primary education for all children. The mission of the DPE is to guarantee integrated and high-quality primary education for all children by enhancing accessibility to primary education and improving its quality. Additionally, the key objectives of DPE comprise the expansion of universal and non-discriminatory primary education and the advancement of Primary Education Management. The Directorate of Primary Education (DPE), which was founded in 1981, transferred all accountability for school development to the District and Upazila subordinate offices. DPE is dedicated to enhancing instruction and learning in its primary schools through its field offices, including Thana/Upazila education offices, District Primary Education Offices, and Upazila Resource Centres (Directorate of Primary Education, 2016).

Every Upazila/ Thana office in Bangladesh is responsible for implementing school improvement initiatives through Upazila/Thana education officers (UEOs/TEOs). In his study, Saha (2023) notes that the UEOs have administrative duties, such as supervising the schools and setting up monthly coordination meetings with all head teachers at government primary schools in their Upazilas. The UEO also distributes textbooks and instructional materials to all primary schools. The UEO/TEO also oversees the pupils' stipend distribution program, monitors the yearly primary exams at the Upazila level, and performs performance reviews of

AUEOs and other Upazila Primary Education Office staff. Additionally, they collect data via ATEO/AUEO from headteachers regarding primary school improvement and management, create development plans for schools and teachers, and submit them to the district primary education office. They also prepare an annual budget for the primary education officers and teachers at the start of the fiscal year, send pension and gratuity award proposals to the district education office, and draw and allocate primary school teachers' salaries and other benefits. The Upazila/ Thana Education Officer is directly in charge of inspecting the schools. The Upazila/Thana Education Officers (UEOs/TEOs) include Assistant Upazila/Thana Education Officers (AUEOs/ATEOs) to assist head teachers in implementing all rules and regulations of school improvement.

Saha (2023) noted that all government primary schools in Bangladesh receive a fixed amount of funding from the SLIP (School Level Improvement Plan) project via the Upazila Primary Education Office. This funding is intended to enhance school facilities and cover regular expenses. The UEOs oversee the project's financial management. They routinely review bills, vouchers, school registers, financial reports, and balance sheets, while also gathering reports from Headteachers about the use of project funds and school expenses to ensure transparency and accountability in financial management by the headteacher.

However, the Upazila Resource Centre (URC) also serves as a key support mechanism, particularly by involving and providing various training for headteachers and assistant teachers to improve their leadership and teaching quality, allowing them to improve their skills and the school (Manzoor Ahmed, 2011).

2.8 Headteachers' and teachers' training for improving primary school education

The Directorate of Primary Education, overseen by the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, has launched several training programs to improve teachers' instructional strategies and classroom management. The national education policy strongly emphasises giving educators the training they need to implement successful teaching techniques. As a result, the education policy emphasises that newly hired teachers will acquire a Certificate in Education (C-in-Ed) or a Bachelor of Education (BEd) training within three years of their recruitment (Ministry of Education, 2010).

Additionally, it said the Directorate of Primary Education, through Upazila Resource Centre, will take appropriate steps to increase the scope of their in-service training. Furthermore, training abroad will be organised based on availability and necessity.

2.8.1 Induction Training

According to the Annual Sector Performance Report, all recently hired teachers, including pre-primary teachers have received a seven-day induction training for the newly enrolled 4+ students (Directorate of Primary Education, 2022). This training addressed key topics such as classroom management, communication abilities, child development, creating supportive learning environments, and teaching strategies. The Directorate of Primary Education (2022) reports that in 2020 under PEDP3, 30,540 pre-primary teachers were hired, and 25,603 pre-primary teachers received induction training for successful classroom teaching and learning.

2.8.2 Headteachers' Leadership Training

According to the Ministry of Education (2010), the primary role and responsibility to supervise the school depends on the headteacher's effectiveness. Thus, the national education plan emphasises providing special training for the headteachers in primary schools for effective supervision (Directorate of Primary Education (2015). Along with the ATEOs/ AUEOs, all the head teachers in primary schools will provide academic supervision training and continuous mentoring to enhance teachers' classroom teaching and learning (Directorate of Primary Education 2011).

According to the Directorate of Primary Education (2015), to improve children's classroom learning, the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education emphasises that head teachers should be more active in providing adequate academic supervision. Primary school head teachers in Bangladesh have a variety of obligations, including administrative and organisational duties, supervision, and financial responsibilities (Directorate of Primary Education, 2019). To ensure that head teachers are well-equipped to carry out their tasks, Bangladesh's Ministry of Primary and Mass Education initiated 21 days of leadership training under PEDP-3 (ibid).

The Headteachers' Leadership Training Module states that the goal of headteachers' leadership training is to make the overall development of the school under the leadership of the head teacher. It also clarifies the key objectives of training, such as developing the leadership

qualities of the head teacher to enable them to apply academic leadership activities to school improvement, assist in the implementation of mentoring processes for the development of teachers' skills in schools, to be personally motivated towards the teaching profession and to help motivate other teachers to participate in school development activities, skilled in building relationship with SMC, PTA, Alumni and all sections of people of the catchment area.

The Directorate of Primary Education (2022) states that leadership training following the PEDP4 standard is expected to be provided to all headteachers. It indicates that headteachers' leadership training has expanded significantly since 2012, with around 80% of headteachers (78.2% female and 77.2% male) receiving leadership training by 2020 (ibid).

2.8.3 The Role and Responsibilities of Headteachers in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, the Directorate of Primary Education refers to the institutional head of a primary school as "headteacher" or "Head Teacher". This terminology is found in various government documents, including the Third Primary Education Development Programme (PEDP3), the Education Sector Plan (ESP) for the fiscal years 2020/21 – 2024/25, the Annual Primary School Census (APSC) 2023, and the Annual Sector Performance Report (ASPR) 2021 (Directorate of Primary Education, 2011; Government of Bangladesh, 2020; Ministry of Primary Education, 2022, 2023). According to UNESCO (2024), the terms 'principal' and 'headteacher' are used in the most recent National Education Policy 2010 (Ministry of Education, 2010) and the Ministry of Education's circulars to refer to both primary and secondary school heads. The CPD Framework and Action Plan 2019 explored that headteachers at primary schools in Bangladesh are regarded as academic leaders who perform various duties, such as classroom management, peer mentorship for teachers, supervision, and teaching (Directorate of Primary Education, 2019). Headteachers' roles closely align with the concept of instructional leadership, which emphasises their managerial role in setting clear goals to enhance classroom teaching and learning by engaging in hands-on supervision, supporting teachers' professional development, and continuously monitoring educational activities in the school (Hallinger, 2005). Clearly, these responsibilities necessitate that the principal, as an instructional leader, possess expertise in classrooms, coach teachers and engage in professional dialogue to generate ideas and strategies that drive school improvement (Southworth, 2002). The 2019 Continuous Professional Development program under PEDP-4 defined headteachers' expectations for creating a supportive classroom teaching and learning environment that may successfully

motivate and assist teachers in the classroom. It highlights the requirements for headteachers to create expectations and objectives towards creating the school's shared vision for the development of the school (UNESCO, 2024).

The 2023 Headteachers Leadership Training Manual (for trainers) outlines various duties and responsibilities of headteachers in Bangladesh, categorised into six groups: administrative and organisational, academic, supervisory, financial, cluster training, and school-based development plan (Directorate of Primary Education, 2023).

Administrative and organisational responsibilities and duties:

1. The Headteacher shall maintain all records, registers and school files.
2. The teaching staff and managing committee members will help conduct the annual survey of school-going children in the school area and maintain a permanent child survey register.
3. Encourage the parents to send their children to school.
4. To guarantee consistent daily attendance of children at school by collaborating with teaching staff, managing committee members, and parents.
5. Prepare and implement the yearly lesson plan and design weekly timetables to guide classroom instruction accordingly.
6. The school will host an annual meeting for prize distribution, sports, and Parents' Day celebrations.
7. Inform all concerned stakeholders, including teachers, students, and parents, about government orders and laws
8. In cooperation with the school's managing committee members, he will regularly take measures to preserve and secure the schoolhouse, furniture, and other resources.
9. Necessary reports and returns will be regularly prepared and sent to all concerned.
10. Issue pupils' transfer certificates.
11. Make arrangements for the students to participate in the Primary Education Final Examination/Scholarship Examination.
12. To take timely measures to form a managing committee in the school and perform the duties of member secretary.
13. The formation of teacher-parent associations and their functioning will be ensured.
14. The textbooks and other supplies provided by the government will be distributed with the approval of the managing committee.

15. Ensure the cleanliness of school classrooms, schoolyards, toilets, etc., as well as the school environment.
16. Arrange at least two monthly sessions with teachers to review improvement targets and record the decisions in the register.
17. After signing the Annual Confidence Report (ACR), the teachers will be sent to the assistant upazila/ Thana Education Officer within the stipulated time.
18. Leave, transfer, and other teacher applications will be sent to the higher authorities with comments.
19. At least once a month, arrange the managing committee meeting and implement the decisions taken in the meeting.

Academic responsibilities and duties

1. Monitor whether the students are progressing or not by providing effective instruction to the teachers.
2. Ensuring teachers have the necessary knowledge and skills through professional development to deliver quality education to students.
3. To supervise the assessment and evaluation process of the school.
4. Ensuring students are supported for institutional success.
5. Engaging parents and the community to accelerate student achievement.
6. Ensuring the provision of resources to support student learning.

Supervisory responsibilities and duties

1. Encourage parents to send their primary school-age children to school regularly.
2. Teachers will ensure regular school attendance.
3. Providing necessary support to teachers to improve the quality of education by regularly observing the teaching-learning activities of at least two classes in writing every day.
4. Ascertaining whether teachers prepare or collect daily lesson plans and teaching materials before lessons.
5. To ensure that the teachers correctly perform their duties and responsibilities.
6. All observations will be raised and discussed in regular fortnightly meetings, and development activities will be jointly undertaken.
7. To arrange the development and maintenance of the school library.

Financial Responsibilities and Duties

1. Maintain a cash book and stock register to use government and locally collected funds, furniture, educational materials, and other resources properly.
2. Prepare the monthly salary bills for schoolteachers and other employees and submit them regularly to the Assistant Upazila/ Police Station Education Officer.
3. Perform duties and responsibilities as assigned by the Government/Department/Upzilla Parishad occasionally.

Responsibilities and duties in the case of cluster training

1. The teachers will be informed of the day, date, and topic of the sub-cluster training in due course. Make all arrangements for sub-cluster training programs, such as seating, educational materials, etc.
2. On the day of the training, the Head Teacher will attend and ensure the attendance of other teachers.
3. Teachers cannot usually be granted casual leave on training days.

Responsibilities and duties related to the school-based development plan

1. SMC will ensure the formation of a Teacher-Parent Association.
2. A planning committee will be formed with the help of the SMC.
3. The teachers, students, members of the teacher-parent association and the local people will arrange to display the information related to the development plan and its implementation.
4. Take initiatives to involve local people in planning and implementation.
5. He will encourage the public to fund a portion of the budget for the plan.
6. Prepare expenditure vouchers accurately and maintain records.
7. Given the plan's implementation, the expenditure statement and vouchers will be prepared and sent to the upazila office.
8. (All teachers will work as a team.) The teacher will seek assistance from other teachers to carry out the mentioned duties.

2.9 Infrastructure development and resource allocation

School improvement is closely connected with infrastructure development and resource allocation. The fourth Primary Education Development Program (PEDP 4) emphasises the country's infrastructure development, which consists of three major components, including 'Equitable access and participation'. The key objective of this component is to ensure that all schools in the country have a child-friendly learning environment to support students' effective participation and continue with quality education (Directorate of Primary Education, 2018).

According to the Directorate of Primary Education (2022), Bangladesh has significantly improved primary school infrastructure and WASH blocks, including designated pre-primary classrooms, well-maintained classrooms, separate toilets for girls and boys, and safe drinking water. These improvements have helped to reduce students' classroom ratios, extend contact hours, reduce absenteeism, and strengthen school organisation and management capacity. As a result, these measures have contributed to higher student enrolment, reduced dropout rates, and improved completion of the primary cycle. Several infrastructure projects were updated and approved under the PEDP4 need-based infrastructure plan, including the construction of 335 classrooms, of which 8,588 are currently underway, out of the 50,500 more classrooms that are planned to be built; 10,500 HT rooms; and 155 constructions, of which 1,524 are presently underway, out of the 5,000 boundary walls that are projected.

Furthermore, according to ASPR (2017), German Technical Assistance (CPEP) provided funds for developing education in remote areas of Bangladesh by rehabilitating the selected government primary schools and building new public primary schools. It also emphasised strengthening the teacher training centres and the objectives of CPEP for Bangladesh's primary education.

In Bangladesh, primary schools are established by the local community, and all school activities are designed according to the community's demands (Sommers, 2013). Headteachers, along with the SMC and PTA, celebrate several programmes, such as annual sports, cultural programmes, prize-giving ceremonies, national day celebrations, football tournaments, and mothers' gatherings for students' wellbeing, and also fulfil the school improvement plan, such as collecting funds. Every school receives a fixed amount of SLIP funding (detailed in section 2.6). In addition to SLIP funds, field data collected through informal conversations with the

headteachers of School A (Pseudonym) and observation of the school's income and expenditure register indicate that headteachers of government primary schools in Bangladesh also receive supplementary government funds to support school improvements (Field data, School A, 2023).

The Thana/upazila education office allocates these funds to the headteachers' accounts in the following manner:

1. Headteachers at schools with one to six teachers received BDT 7200 (£50) annually. In comparison, those at schools with more than six teachers received BDT 8400 (£60) annually to cover miscellaneous costs, referred to as contingency bills. Headteachers spent this money on essential classroom teaching and learning materials, including markers, pens, pencils, chalk, dusters, registers, coloured pencils, art papers, and expenses for photocopying or scanning services.
2. Each headteacher was allocated BDT 5000 to 10000 (£35 to £70) annually for decorating and purchasing toys and sports items for the pre-primary classroom.
3. To celebrate national days, such as Independence Day, Victory Day, National Children's Day, and Mourning Day, the allocation given to the headteacher is BDT 2000 (£15).
4. At the beginning of the year, a budget for the transportation of textbooks from the Upazila/Thana education office to the school is allocated to each school's headteacher for BDT 800 (£6).
5. Each school's headteacher is provided with BDT 2000 (£14) to organise football and annual sports competitions.
6. Every school headteacher receives a cheque covering the electricity and land tax bills.
7. When a school requires significant repairs or renovations, funding is allocated through government contracting agencies and the Local Government Engineering Department (LGED) based on estimates. In these instances, the funding amounts range from BDT 500,000 to 2,000,000 (£3571-£14286).

Therefore, school improvement cannot be successful without the cooperation of local people. Due to this, the headteachers' role is to launch such links between the community and their school to develop school infrastructure to ensure a child-friendly school environment.

2.10 Conclusion

The chapter provided the current research background, beginning with describing Bangladesh's history of independence, area, population, and language movement. It then briefly describes the education system, focusing on various goals in government policies, programs, and initiatives to develop it. It then describes the education structure, highlighting primary education in Bangladesh. Section 2.5 details PEDP programmes 1, 2, 3, and the newly introduced PEDP 4, significantly enhancing Bangladesh's primary education. Next, it detailed SLIP guidelines for government primary schools. SLIP serves as a locally developed enhancement strategy, implemented by the headteacher in partnership with the SMC, PTA, and the broader school community to ensure the success of school improvement efforts. Furthermore, it examines the main stakeholders, including the SMC and the PTA, and their roles and responsibilities in supporting primary education. Subsequently, this chapter emphasises the management systems in primary education, highlighting the roles and responsibilities of the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, the Directorate of Primary Education, District Primary Education Offices, Primary Teachers Training Institutes, Upazila/Thana Education Offices, and Upazila Resource Centres in enforcing rules and regulations related to school improvement. It offers a concise overview of several training programs aimed at improving head teachers' leadership skills and enhancing teachers' classroom teaching and learning abilities. The chapter ended with a discussion on infrastructure development and resource allocation, which are closely tied to school development.

Chapter 3: Literature Review

3.1. Introduction

This chapter provides a review of relevant literature related to debates around headteachers, school leadership and school improvement. In searching the literature pertinent to the review, several keywords and phrases were used, such as ‘headteachers and school improvement’, ‘headteachers and effective school leadership’ and ‘headteachers and school improvement challenges and the names of countries, especially to find relevant research in developing countries. The purpose of reviewing the literature of developing countries was that Bangladesh is a developing country; considering the same socio-economic background, there might be resemblances in how the headteachers in these countries behave, practice and apply their roles. Furthermore, the lack of relevant literature in Bangladesh required reviewing international sources to achieve a thorough understanding of the roles and practices of local headteachers.

Since limited published articles and journals from the previous five years specifically addressed school improvement in Bangladesh, I widened my search to include studies done in the Bangladeshi general educational context. I did this by focusing on "any time" and "any type" studies pertinent to the research questions and topic. This study excluded only research unrelated to the current study's research questions. Moreover, while exploring the definition of leadership and various leadership roles, the literature focuses primarily on the literature of the global North, acknowledging that school improvement has been the focus of much research within literature from the global North (Bernhardt, 2017; Day, Sammons and Gorge, 2022; Leithwood, Harris and Hopkins, 2019) while much less research has been undertaken into the leadership of school improvement in new and emerging countries (Moroosi, 2019).

The study searched relevant literature using search engines such as Google Scholar, ProQuest, JSTOR, ERIC, SpringerLink, Sage and Taylor & Francis Online. Besides the introduction and conclusion, the chapter is divided into seven sections. The first section explores the broader school improvement challenges faced by government primary schools in Bangladesh and a similar developing country context. Although they were not always connected directly with the headteacher's role, these school improvement challenges provide essential background and help frame the complex environment in which school headteachers operate. The second section examines the role of the headteacher in school leadership. This is followed by a discussion of headteachers and their vision for school improvement. Next, it describes the headteachers' role

as an academic supervisor. The subsequent section describes headteachers' roles in ensuring the quality of the learning environment. This is followed by a discussion of literature concerned with the role of the headteacher in staff mentoring, then the final section examines headteachers and decentralisation of power and how these dynamic factors hinder school improvement initiatives.

3.2 School Improvement Challenges

School improvement is a complex process, especially in developing countries like Bangladesh. Many studies have explored different challenges that schools face, such as a lack of funds or poverty, large class sizes, a lack of stakeholders' support, and poor teachers' professional development, which are the main factors impeding school improvement. These challenges create two significant concerns in primary education: dropout and repetition, and the establishment of the quality of classroom education (Kono, Sawada, and Shonchoy, 2018). In developing countries, especially schools in rural areas, there is frequently a lack of resources and a high turnover rate among teachers. This results in many young, inexperienced teachers, which undermines the provision of quality education (Hardman and Sandi, 2024).

These problems are often discussed at the system or policy level and may not directly mention the role of headteachers. However, these challenges still affect how schools work and what kind of leadership is possible at the school level. Even though headteachers are not always the focus in this part of the literature, it is essential to understand their working environment. These issues create barriers that can limit or shape what headteachers can do to improve their schools.

A study by Bhuttah et al. (2020) highlighted various challenges facing primary schools in Pakistan, such as the quality of education, equal opportunity, high dropout rates, and low student participation and completion. The primary issues identified included escalating poverty, a shortage of teachers, inadequate educational quality, uncommitted and incompetent teachers, an overloaded curriculum, outdated teaching methods, insufficient monitoring, an ineffective assessment system, and corruption. Qureshi and Kalsoom (2022) emphasised that insufficient teacher competencies significantly affect the low quality of education in schools. Kalsoom (2017), in her doctoral research, highlighted key challenges in school improvement in Pakistan, particularly the connection between teacher education and the lack of standardised professional development. Her study specifically investigated the status of Education for

Sustainable Development (ESD) in teacher education, revealing that while some ESD-related content and processes were present in policy documents and curricula, there was no comprehensive standard or dedicated course on ESD. This limited integration of ESD, alongside insufficient standards for teachers' professional development, subpar teacher education programmes, and inadequate subject knowledge among teachers, contributed to poor teacher performance. Consequently, in a subsequent publication, Qureshi and Kalsoom (2022) connected the low quality of classroom education to the ongoing issue of inadequate teacher competencies, arguing that without strengthening teacher education and embedding ESD more systematically, the quality of schooling in Pakistan remains compromised.

Additionally, Jabeen, Ali, and Ahmad (2023) pinpointed challenges within Pakistan's public secondary schools, including poorly trained and unmotivated staff, an ineffective supervisory system, and large class sizes. Their study also highlighted that many students come from low-income families, which complicates their ability to cover educational expenses.

According to Bush (2022), headteachers face numerous challenges when striving for school improvement in various regions worldwide. Since the early 21st century, these challenges have been highlighted in educational leadership literature (Tintoré et al., 2022). Bush (2022) notes that headteachers face significant challenges such as balancing leadership accountability for teaching and learning, and handling pressures from families and broader society. Additionally, Bush (2022) noted that in Perak state, in Malaysia, there are 253 schools primarily located in remote rural areas. The headteachers at these schools encounter significant challenges, such as inadequate building infrastructure, limited budgets, and high educator turnover rates. However, the headteachers acted as teaching leaders who were passionate, instructionally driven, strategic thinkers, and eager learners.

Thus, headteachers' roles continue to be challenging. To tackle these concerns, Adu (2016) emphasises the importance of robust headteacher leadership and the engaged participation of the community, including parents, in enhancing public schools. Nevertheless, many developing countries often have a shortage of research on how headteacher leadership and community involvement influence educational results. This absence has resulted in a dependence on global research recommendations concerning school effectiveness and improvement to inform policy decisions in developing nations to enhance public education (Adu, 2016).

According to Chaudhary (2023), inadequate funding is a significant challenge encountered by the Indian education system, resulting in limited resources to meet quality infrastructure (such as classrooms, sanitation, pure drinking water, libraries, and laboratories) and teachers' job satisfaction. The author also highlighted that the lack of parental engagement, especially in rural areas, the shortage of skilled and qualified teachers and poverty hinder the quality of education.

Anwer, Kayani, and Jabeen (2018) reported on a study in Pakistan that examined the relationship between the leadership abilities of school headteachers and various school outcomes, as well as the challenges faced by headteachers in secondary schools. The study indicated that headteachers encounter numerous obstacles to enhance their schools, including insufficient accountability within the school discipline system, overload of administrative responsibilities, overcrowded classrooms, students' weak performance in science and mathematics, inadequate socioeconomic backgrounds of parents combined with minimal parental involvement, a shortage of qualified teachers, lack of practical assessments, and high student dropout rates. They also discovered that most challenges involve improvements in classroom teaching and learning and the professional development of teachers, which headteachers encounter in school improvement initiatives. In another study conducted in Pakistan, Dinler (2024) highlighted various challenges that headteachers encounter in the school improvement process, including administrative bureaucracy, inadequate physical infrastructure, and limited resources that impede improvement plans.

Although Bangladesh has achieved great strides in primary education, particularly in enrolment and gender equality, the quality of education is still debatable (Ahmed, 2021; Mousumi and Kusakabe, 2021). In Bangladesh, primary education faces several obstacles that prevent overall educational quality from being attained. This component of the literature study examines and evaluates the difficulties.

Most government primary school students in Bangladesh come from slums or low-income families (Cameron, 2011). A recent study by Mallik (2025) in her doctoral thesis also examined how all the participants' teachers in Bangladesh believe that parents' poor economic condition is a significant barrier to ensuring quality primary education. This study highlighted how some parents could not provide their children with meals, clothing, and learning materials. Findings

showed that the poor socio-economic situation led those families to send the children to child labour, and some children were required to assist their parents with domestic chores. Thus, poverty hurts student enrolment and attendance, resulting in dropouts.

Mallik (2025) also noted that a head teacher from a school with strong community participation reported that students arrived at 9:15 a.m. and had to remain until 4:15 p.m. With only a 30-minute break, they had insufficient time to return home for lunch as their residences were far from their school. Due to economic hardship, they were unable to procure food from the school premises, which hindered their ability to concentrate on their studies.

Sommers (2013) and Masoom and Siddik (2024) also assert that poverty negatively impacts children's health through nutrition issues, which subsequently impairs their ability to concentrate on their studies, thereby obstructing academic achievement. In numerous rural schools in developing countries, student absenteeism is a significant issue as parents' financial difficulties require child labour to support the family's income, mainly at harvest time (Hardman and Sandi, 2024). Due to economic challenges, most parents find it difficult to pay for daily necessities, often leading to children's absences and dropping out of school (Cameron, 2011; Sarker, Wu, and Hossin, 2019). Azizuddin (2014) highlights that the Primary Education Stipend Project in Bangladesh aims to support students from poor families by covering their monthly expenditures. He states that this project began in January 2003 with the goal of assisting over 5.5 million children across roughly 65,000 schools. This program gives Tk. 100 (about US\$1.3) monthly to a family with one student and Tk. 125 per month to a family with multiple students (Hossain *et al.*, 2017).

Sommers (2013) notes that the earning members of poor families in Bangladesh are often forced to migrate to different locations in search of seasonal work, which creates unsettling situations for children's education. Moreover, other research discusses how economic challenges faced by families worsen students' studies and create a problematic environment for schools to achieve meaningful school improvement (Shohel, 2014; Rahaman, 2016; Sarker *et al.*, 2019; Al Zaman *et al.* 2024). In addition, Sommers (2013) found in his ethnographic study that, despite Bangladesh's government's pledge to provide free primary education to ensure education for all, most of the cost of primary schooling falls on parents, an unbearable burden for many. These costs may include children's private tuition, exam fees (three times), and essential supplies, including uniforms, school bags, water bottles, lunch boxes, pens,

notebooks, and lunch or snacks during school hours. The optional (but standard) charge for private tuition fees to boost pupil attainment adds a burden for poor parents.

Existing research also highlights that Bangladesh's primary schools encounter a high teacher-student ratio and large class sizes. It is acknowledged that a high teacher-student ratio and big class sizes directly affect classroom teaching and learning in all schools since teachers cannot effectively support every student in the classroom (Shekh and Nurul, 2005). Al Nahar, Hira, and Milon (2024) identify several challenges to successfully implementing the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) program in Bangladeshi primary education, emphasising overcrowded classrooms.

Using a case study design, Numan and Islam (2021) examine how primary schools in Sylhet, Bangladesh, experience high-quality education, with an emphasis on the classroom teaching and learning process. The study reveals that public school teachers are less focused on delivering quality education, whereas Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee (BRAC) schools excel in providing better teaching and learning. This is attributed to the teachers' careful classroom practices and the use of subject-based lesson plans during teaching. The study identified several vital indicators that indicate lower classroom teaching and learning quality in government primary schools, including high student-to-teacher ratios and large class sizes. In contrast, BRAC schools have modest class sizes and a logical teacher-student ratio, which confirms robust instructional practices.

In a recent study, Ahmed, Adhikary, and Rahaman (2024) conducted a mixed-method study in Bangladesh. He observed that the current methods of learning and teaching science in the classroom were primarily focused on the teacher, resulting in minimal active participation from students and few opportunities for practical activities and discussions. Significant obstacles to effective science teaching included large class sizes and a lack of adequate materials to address the requirements of these classes.

Paul, Islam, and Hossain (2021) investigate a study to assess the connection between the literacy rate and the ratio of teachers to students in the classroom. Among many other factors, the study emphasises that essential influences such as teachers' skills and motivation and external influences such as class size and the teacher-student ratio have a significant relationship to students' classroom achievement. The study found that small class sizes allow teachers to spend more time with each student, directly impacting their learning and academic

success. Furthermore, an earlier study conducted by Asadullah (2005) in a secondary school in Bangladesh discovered that class size significantly affects students' achievement because big class sizes may lead to poor-quality classroom instruction. The research highlighted that one of the key challenges to school improvement in Bangladesh is a lack of adequate support from the larger community the School Managing Committee (SMC) and parents (Islam, 2021; Ullah, 2021; Hasnat and Kabir (2024)

Islam (2021) carried out a qualitative study to illustrate the situation of parental involvement with a government primary school in Dhaka, Bangladesh. The study revealed that only influential parents can participate in SMC and PTA. The study's findings revealed that incorporating parents is difficult work since parents lack encouragement, and their hectic schedules prevent them from communicating with the schools. The study discovered that the majority of parents did not communicate with teachers. Only a few guardians maintain frequent communication.

In a recent qualitative case study, Hasnat and Kabir (2024) examine the actions, issues, and opportunities for rural parents' involvement in Bangladeshi secondary schools. This study investigates how parental socioeconomic status affects their involvement behaviours in Bangladeshi rural secondary schools and discovered that parental involvement initiatives related to school yearly events resulted in limited individual interactions with parents. It also highlights that the absence of parental literacy and poverty hampered frequent participation efforts. Furthermore, due to their hectic schedules, parents and teachers have limited opportunities to actively participate in the educational system for the betterment of the learners.

Taken together, the reviewed studies reveal that challenges to school improvement in the contexts of developing countries, including Bangladesh, Pakistan, India, and Malaysia, face similar problems. A consistent theme is the impact of poverty, which not only restricts families' ability to provide children with learning materials or regular meals (Mallik, 2025; Sommers, 2013) but also fuels absenteeism and dropout (Cameron, 2011; Hardman & Sandi, 2024). These financial constraints intersect with systemic shortcomings, including overcrowded classrooms, high teacher-student ratios, and inadequate infrastructure (Chaudhary, 2023; Ahmed et al., 2024; Asadullah, 2005). Another essential point is headteachers' effective leadership (Bush, 2022; Adu, 2016); headteachers are seen as key to school improvement, but a lack of resources,

government bureaucracy, and weak support from parents and communities limit their work (Anwer, Kayani, and Jabeen, 2018; Islam, 2021; Hasnat & Kabir, 2024). This synthesis makes it clear that school improvement cannot be addressed without also tackling broader social and economic challenges.

In summary, the challenges discussed in this section highlight the difficult conditions under which many schools in Bangladesh and other developing countries are trying to improve. These challenges, although not always directly connected to the role of headteachers, significantly impact the way schools operate and the types of leadership that are possible. Understanding these wider problems is crucial because they shape the working environment of headteachers. The following sections will focus more closely on how headteachers lead school improvement in these challenging contexts, including their roles in setting vision, supervising teachers, supporting staff, and managing change at the school level.

3.3. Headteachers and School Leadership

According to Daniëls, Hondeghem, and Dochy (2019), school leadership involves a process in which headteachers exercise deliberate influence over stakeholders who are often closely involved with school development activities. The authors state that the school leader's constant concern in educational leadership should accomplish the organisation's objectives by providing effective instruction and learning for student success. They also claim that research on school leadership has been criticised for concentrating solely on students' cognitive outcomes, which include, among other things, instruction and independent study; supportive and communication-oriented process-oriented techniques, such as project and group work; and reflexive methods, which include techniques like supervision and feedback.

For Leithwood, Harris, and Hopkins (2020), headteachers significantly influence classroom teaching, learning, and student achievement as school leaders. They note that effective school leadership is widely recognised as the second only to classroom teaching and learning in securing school improvement through leaders' influence on teachers' motivation. This view is also supported by Sigurardóttir and Sigursson (2016), who note that it is nearly impossible to enhance students' classroom achievement without talented leadership. Moreover, Day, Sammons, and Gorgen (2020) assert that school leadership significantly influences school improvement by fostering high-quality classroom teaching and learning. They also emphasise the importance of school leaders' effective leadership in improving the teaching and learning environments and adjusting vision and strategy based on demands. Karmacharya (2023) states

that an overall educational institution's success mainly depends on the principal's or the school administration's role. His/her attitudes and institutional vision are the fundamental tools for the sustainable improvement of his/her institution. Thus, the principal's primary concern is to ensure a positive learning atmosphere for the pupils. Leithwood, Sun, and Schumacker (2020) further state that effective leadership can enhance teacher commitment to securing good pupil academic achievement and moral development. The authors acknowledge that school leadership significantly impacts student success when leaders encourage parents to support their children and classroom activities.

Effective school leaders (e.g., headteachers) collaborate with teachers to improve school performance. Sehgal, Nambudiri, and Mishra (2017) note the importance of headteachers in promoting collaborative practices, recognising that collaboration improves teacher self-efficacy. They note that teachers' thoughtful behaviours, motivation, esteem, and sense of security are all positively influenced by headteachers who promote positive collaboration. Moreover, Bush and Glover (2016) underline the significance of the school's headteachers' leadership in maintaining effective teamwork between the headteacher, the senior leaders, and the teachers.

Effective headteachers employ various leadership strategies (both formal and informal) to influence the teachers, students, SMC members, and parents to build relationships, collaboration, and trust to make the school effective (Fairman and Mackenzie, 2015). Day, Gu, and Sammons (2016) state that successful head teachers use leadership styles, including transformational as well as instructional leadership, to accomplish and sustain long-term change in their schools. As the authors explain, instructional leadership underscores the significance of defining unambiguous educational aims, evaluating teachers' classroom instruction, and providing the necessary instruction to promote student outcomes. In contrast, transformational leadership always emphasises the school vision by motivating staff to improve the quality of classroom instruction and learning. Furthermore, the authors highlight that an effective school administrator employs transformational and instructional leadership styles at the right moment and for the right reason.

Hardman and Sandi (2024) note that effective headteachers are instructional leaders, managers, problem-solvers, and community interfaces. Evidence from international comparisons shows that many countries increasingly view headteachers as instructional leaders supporting

teachers' learning, rather than solely as administrators (Vaillant, 2015; Mourshed et al., 2010). However, in developing countries, this emphasis on instructional leadership is less evident, even though the headteacher's role in school improvement has grown (Hardman and Sandi, 2024). Consequently, continuous professional development in leadership skills is essential for management teams to strengthen instructional leadership and foster community engagement. Headteachers play a significant role in unifying the instructional activity at school within a particular frame (Danai, 2021). Maskey (2023) examines the leadership role of headteachers, emphasising that their actions contribute to the effective operation of schools and students' academic success. He notes that headteachers in Kathmandu's community schools take on multiple roles, such as instructional, administrative, and monitoring tasks, to enhance school improvement.

According to Tahira and Haider (2020), five key elements in support of school improvement include an effective instructional guidance system, skilled staff capacity, a strong parent-community relationship, a student-centred learning environment, and the effective role of the headteacher in driving forward school improvement initiatives. The authors also state that the headteacher plays a crucial role in setting goals, managing time, effectively utilising instructional and non-instructional resources, involving the community and family, and sharing best practices for school improvement.

Owen et al. (2020) point to the fact that there is limited research focusing on headteachers' roles in school improvement initiatives in developing countries. The authors state that effective leadership is significant for school improvement, and leaders in developed countries continuously enhance their professional learning to improve classroom teaching and learning and student outcomes. These authors conducted a case study to determine essential success criteria for implementing an instructional leadership program in Kiribati, a developing country. The study highlighted how schools in developing countries can function efficiently by using an instructional leadership strategy that includes workshops and coaching, classroom supervision, student discipline, parental involvement, the establishment of effective professional development programs, and finally, support for classroom teaching and learning to increase the capacity of school headteachers and instructors.

While also highlighting the lack of research on headteachers and school improvement in developing countries, Oduro et al. (2007) focused their study on leadership challenges

impacting the work of headteachers in developing countries. They suggested that headteachers in developing countries should develop their leadership skills to ensure quality education, as they are under pressure to achieve the Millennium Development Goals. According to Tai and Kareem (2020), school leaders can enhance pupil achievement by refining their leadership skills through ongoing professional development that updates their abilities and knowledge. Thus, headteachers should interpret and apply leadership practices in varied ways, depending on the type of school they manage.

In Bangladesh, school leadership's complex and crucial components have received little attention (Salahuddin, 2016). Researchers have recognised the key roles of school headteachers in exercising leadership and improving schools (Hossain *et al.*, 2021; Tasnim, 2021; Ananda, 2021; Hossain, 2021). Effective school headteachers are expected to act as managers, problem-solvers, and instructional leaders who bridge between the school and the broader community they serve (Hardman and Sandi, 2024). Headteachers' effective leadership shapes teachers' efficacy and attitudes, ultimately enhancing the school's outcomes (Jamil, Sewani, and Muhammad, 2024). As an instructional school leader, the headteacher must provide effective leadership to implement all school improvement programs, including improving classroom teaching and learning, ensuring up-to-date learning materials such as teaching aids, textbooks, etc (Mosiori and Thinguri, 2015). Schools improve best under the direction of a principal who exhibits effective leadership skills, as this leadership is the main factor influencing a school's improvement (Wiyono *et al.*, 2023). According to Kanwal *et al.* (2021), school headteachers play a significant role in improving the quality of schools by shaping the school culture. The authors reveal that head teachers in Rahim Yar Khan District in Pakistan effectively fulfil their roles; however, some areas, such as school cleanliness, teacher appreciation, and disciplinary rules, have been overlooked.

Ananda (2021) conducted a qualitative study in Bangladesh to investigate the experiences of Government Primary School Head Teachers' use of instructional leadership in schools to implement the curriculum successfully. The study found that all headteachers agreed on the importance of instructional leadership dimensions, including developing a school improvement vision, decision-making for coordination, supervising classroom teaching, supporting teachers, monitoring student progress, promoting professional development, and engaging with stakeholders. They emphasised collaboration to achieve collective goals and maintained shared decision-making and responsibilities with assistant teachers, SMC, and PTA members.

Additionally, their leadership ensured a safe environment by regularly monitoring student progress and supervising teacher performance to uphold their instructional leadership role.

Uddin, Akhter, and Hena (2018) conducted a quantitative study on the relationship between headteachers' instructional leadership and school effectiveness in Bangladesh. They found a strong correlation between headteacher efficacy and school achievement. The results showed that headteachers' leadership positively influenced student achievement, classroom atmosphere, teaching quality, and overall academic success. Khan and Gupta (2024) in the Indian setting examine the association between instructional leadership and teachers' self-efficacy, which is positively associated with educators' job satisfaction. The study's findings highlight that instructional leadership enhances educators' self-efficacy as well as job satisfaction through defining the school objectives, collaborating with staff, aligning instruction, and setting school goals. These goals unite the staff, directing them toward the school mission and shared accomplishment. The study also emphasises that instructional leaders monitor teachers' classroom teaching and learning and provide constructive feedback to ensure active student engagement. The instructional leaders also offer praise and involve the community to promote school-wide professional advancement.

Rahman et al. (2023) conducted a qualitative study investigating how headteachers use transformational leadership to implement digitisation in Bangladeshi primary schools. The study's findings demonstrated that, as transformational leaders, all headteachers have the vision to digitalise their schools. Most head teachers stressed the significance of involving the school community to achieve the vision. As transformative leaders, some principals enthusiastically encourage and motivate teachers and students to adopt digital technology. Tasnim (2021) conducted a mixed-methods study investigating headteachers' leadership roles in Bangladeshi primary schools. The findings revealed that head teachers' leadership roles aligned with educational quality and standards. The study showed that while one school survived because of the outstanding leadership of the head teacher, the other two barely survived. It highlighted that an effective school leader is both visionary and a lifelong learner, enabling them to excel in providing high-quality education.

Hossain et al. (2021) conducted a qualitative study in Bangladesh on how headteachers' leadership styles impact primary schools. The findings reveal that effective leadership boosts school performance by fostering strong stakeholder relationships, ensuring regular teacher

attendance, and supporting active SMC and PTA. Other factors include good infrastructure, a child-friendly environment, competency-based lessons, adequate teaching materials, effective classroom management, and technology integration. The notion of quality primary education is the fundamental goal and expectation of the Bangladeshi government (Kamal and Chowdhury, 2019). Kamal and Chowdhury (2019) investigated the role of headteachers in ensuring effective classroom teaching and learning in government primary schools in Bangladesh and found headteachers play the key role in ensuring a joyful learning environment in schools by providing the teachers with classroom teaching and learning materials and guides them to use the materials, monitors and supervise their activities as well. In addition, the study found that students engaged highly when teachers used relevant teaching materials such as pictures, charts and practical lessons in science classes.

Salahuddin and Conner (2015) conducted a study on urban principals in Dhaka, Bangladesh and gave contextual information on how four secondary school headteachers in Bangladesh lead their schools. To investigate the headteachers' practice of school leadership and their thoughts on how they should divide leadership, particularly decision-making and responsibilities within their schools, this case study highlighted those four principals recognised for employing different leadership styles depending on time, circumstance, and context. They believed no single leadership style was effective in every circumstance to make a school effective.

Islam (2016) examines the concept of teacher leadership in his review paper, its significance, and its potential to enhance secondary schools in Bangladesh. The study, which is primarily supported by policy papers, literature, and guidelines, argues that teacher leadership is essential to educational development programs. York-Barr and Duke (2004) define teacher leadership as teacher agency demonstrated through building relationships, removing obstacles, and mobilising resources across the organisation to enhance students' educational experiences and outcomes. Muijs and Harris (2006) conceptualise teacher leadership as a set of collective practices focused on relationships within the school, emphasising teachers' capacity to lead teaching and learning both inside and beyond the classroom. However, in Bangladeshi secondary schools, leadership is often viewed as a position rather than an action, which poses a significant challenge when implementing school improvement initiatives (Islam, 2016).

Overall, the reviewed literature consistently highlights the centrality of headteachers in shaping teaching, learning, and school improvement. Across diverse contexts, effective school leadership emerges as a multidimensional practice that blends instructional, transformational, and collaborative approaches. Furthermore, scholars agree that leadership effectiveness depends not on a single style but on the flexible application of multiple strategies according to context (Day, Gu, & Sammons, 2016; Salahuddin & Conner, 2015). While studies in developed countries often emphasise structured instructional leadership and sustained professional learning, research from developing contexts, particularly Bangladesh, points to headteachers' multiple and overlapping roles as instructional leaders, managers, and community mediators. Despite these differences, the common thread is that schools improve most when leadership fosters a positive culture, motivates teachers, and engages parents and communities. At the same time, there is still a lack of research on how headteachers in developing countries manage these challenges, highlighting the need for further studies in such contexts.

3.4. Headteachers and School Vision

Vision is often recognised as central to leadership. Bush and Glover (2014) suggest that effective leaders create a school vision rooted in their professional and personal values. They regularly share this vision and motivate their team and other stakeholders to adopt it. It promotes a better future for the organisation and encourages others to commit to working towards its objectives. Thus, vision is a means of influencing school development (Hallinger and Heck, 2002). It is the school heads who shape the school vision and identify how to achieve that vision. Minadzi and Nyame (2016) state that the most effective school headteachers concentrate on their school's development by establishing a clear mission or purpose. Therefore, the headteachers consult with the relevant stakeholders and draw plans to guide the implementation of the school's goals and visions (Mosiori and Thinguri, 2015). These goals and vision must align with the national educational goals.

Bush and Glover (2003) emphasise 'vision' as an essential aspect of effective school leadership, especially headteachers' application of transformational leadership. Bush and Glover (2014) highlight that transformational leaders are popular due to their strong focus on vision as a key leadership characteristic. Effective leaders are expected to collaborate with staff and other stakeholders, fostering greater commitment to the organisation's goals, which are inherently tied to the overarching vision. Research shows that transformational leadership positively impacts student outcomes (Bush and Glover, 2014), the key component for school

improvement. However, if the vision is not shared, leaders may not properly engage stakeholders, resulting in resistance to school improvement actions (Kools and Stoll, 2016). Successful school leaders always establish a specific shared vision that outlines short-term objectives. They also cultivate positive relationships with all parties involved, including parents, staff, and students, and allocate resources to support the vision (Leithwood, Harris, and Hopkins, 2020).

Hallinger and Heck (2002) argued that vision serves as a means of influence in school improvement. They emphasised that personal vision encompasses the values that shape a leader's perspective on the world, including their approach to education. Mombourquette (2017) explored how personal and school-based visions influence the student learning experience. He conducted semi-structured interviews with 27 primary, middle, and high school principals in Alberta, Canada. The study discovered that principals of high-achieving schools consistently expressed visions and objectives that stemmed from personal views on different school programs and student learning in the classroom. Similarly, principals in low-performing schools did not define personal ideas or a vision for school improvement. Furthermore, the findings of this study demonstrated that both new and experienced school leaders require effective leadership and a clear vision for the betterment of schools' future.

There is some academic literature related to vision and leadership in Bangladesh. Morshed (2016) emphasises that head teachers play a crucial leadership role in articulating the vision, although this research relates to integrating ICT education in Bangladeshi secondary schools. This study found that the participant headteachers and their staff created a school-specific vision for successfully adopting technology in education. However, to implement and determine the vision properly, headteachers must communicate with the teachers and agree on the vision with stakeholders.

Ali (2011) conducted a qualitative investigation of the leadership ideas, approaches, patterns, and contemporary practices employed by head teachers in four private secondary schools in both rural and urban regions of Bangladesh. The findings of this study demonstrate that Bangladeshi school leaders hold a strong vision for school reform. To fulfil their vision, they employ democratic and management leadership philosophies to run their schools. The findings also reveal that the school leaders emphasise enhancing their professional growth inside the

school to improve classroom teaching and learning. Their main goal is to ensure students' achievement and school enhancement.

Salahuddin (2016) investigated the leadership style of a creative and inventive headteacher in a secondary school in Bangladesh through a case study. The study showed that his leadership articulated a strong vision: to make his school the top institution in the district within ten years. To carry out this goal, he effectively articulates and encourages stakeholders such as teachers, parents, and the larger community to improve students' classroom learning. This study included the objectives the headteacher set for carrying out his/her vision, including providing extra attention to students in grades five, eight, and ten who take public exams, offering special classes for slow learners, interacting with the parents of students who struggle academically, paying close attention to teachers' preparation in the classroom, and improving classroom supervision.

Further, Kabir, Green, and Chowdhury (2020) investigated headteachers' duties and responsibilities in 20 primary schools in a Bangladeshi upazila and discovered that a strong school vision set by the headteacher is crucial for attaining the quality of primary education in Bangladesh. The study also found that Primary School Head Teachers play an important role in implementing goals through effective learning and teaching preparation and active participation from the larger community.

Taken together, the literature makes it clear that vision is a powerful driver of school improvement and a defining part of effective leadership. A strong visionary headteachers do more than state a mission; they involve teachers, parents, and the broader community so that the vision becomes shared and actionable. Studies from Western contexts often highlight the link between transformational leadership and vision, showing how a clear and shared purpose boosts teacher commitment and student outcomes. Research from Bangladesh reflects similar themes but also indicates how vision is closely tied to practical challenges such as exam performance, technology integration, and community involvement. What stands out across contexts is that vision is not compelling if it remains only as words or statements; it must be communicated, agreed upon, and supported with fundamental strategies and resources. At the same time, the literature on vision in Bangladesh remains relatively limited, underscoring the need for further research on how school leaders in resource-constrained settings create, share, and sustain visions for long-term improvement.

3.5. Headteachers and School Supervision

In education, supervision combines the concepts of excellence, ‘super’, and ‘vision’ to define the ongoing observation, mentoring, and oversight of educators and students aimed at enhancing teaching quality (Haque et al., 2024). Academic supervision is a key aspect of the headteachers’ role and authority to improve the quality of teachers' classroom teaching and learning (Susanti, Wardiah, and Lian, 2020). As an academic supervisor, the principal is the chief leader in his/her school and is responsible for observing, fostering, and improving the classroom teaching and learning (Amelia et al., 2022). The supervisory system is an essential stakeholder in the educational system, guiding the teachers and assisting them in improving themselves (Ozcan, 2020). Therefore, academic supervision aims to support teachers in boosting their professional skills. Supervisors are in a good position to help the teaching teams improve their methods of instruction (Garver and Maloney, 2020). Furthermore, by maintaining close contact with the instructors and spending significant time in the classrooms, supervisors can get insight into the students' needs and cultural backgrounds, allowing them to respond with the best pedagogy. Thus, supervision immerses teachers in instructional conversation to improve classroom teaching and learning and increase pupil achievement (Garver and Maloney, 2020).

Sunaryo (2020) illustrated how academic supervision can immediately impact and shape teachers' attitudes in overseeing the educational process. First and foremost, the teacher's degree of skill, interests, requirements, professional maturity, and other personal traits must be considered while establishing and implementing an academic supervision program. Second, the supervisor's conduct in assisting teachers in improving their skills needs to be thoroughly planned, including the start and end periods of the development program. Third, the ultimate goal of academic supervision is to enable teachers to support their students' learning better. Academic supervision aims to support teachers in enhancing their skills to achieve the established learning objectives. The author highlights the need for academic supervision to foster the development of four competencies: social, professional, educational, and personality.

A study by Noor and Sofyaningrum (2020) in Indonesia examined how the principal's academic supervision can help teachers advance their careers and increase student learning outcomes. The study finds that the supervision uses the process (planning, execution, reporting, and follow-up outcomes) as a monitoring guide. Nevertheless, because of the principal's overwhelming workload, not all the procedures in the guidelines are implemented correctly.

Another study in Indonesia by Ahmad and Saefurrohman (2020) reveals that the school headmaster employed a mix of direct, indirect, and collaborative methods for academic supervision. Direct supervision involved the headmaster actively listening and providing examples to help teachers resolve learning issues. Instead of merely identifying deficiencies, indirect supervision is accomplished through private conversations, where the headmaster assists teachers in addressing challenges, allowing them to share their concerns openly. The collaborative supervision model significantly improved teacher performance and received overwhelmingly positive feedback. This method is shaped to the teachers' needs, creating a comfortable environment for supervision. In Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, research by Hoque et al. (2020) shows a strong positive link between directive supervision and both teachers' performance and attitudes. Additionally, their study investigates three supervisory models: directive, nondirective, and collaborative supervision. Directive supervision focuses on enhancing the classroom instruction of new teachers, and collaborative supervision involves teachers contributing solutions to challenges. In contrast, nondirective supervision encourages teachers to address their classroom difficulties independently.

In Bangladesh, Haque et al. (2024) explore the legal elements of secondary education supervision mainly relying on secondary literature. This study finds that supervision in secondary education is divided into two types: internal and external. The headteacher oversees internal surveillance, which involves secure, professional coordination between the headteacher and teachers to maintain a conducive learning environment. The study also emphasises the duties of a supervisor, such as assisting teachers in carrying out classroom tasks efficiently and using instructional leadership to evaluate students' development. Supervisors ensure teachers assess classroom teaching and learning and use information from reliable sources to evaluate students' progress.

Alam, Haque, and Banu (2021) examine the significance of academic supervision in increasing the quality of primary education in Bangladesh. The study points out that supervision in Bangladesh is classified into internal and external categories. The authors explore the importance of internal supervision given by the head teacher, who works tirelessly with teachers to improve their classroom teaching and learning actions through attentive face-to-face observation.

However, Amelia et al. (2022) argued that although principals' academic supervision is significant to enhance school improvement, they still encounter several difficulties, especially time constraints, as principals hold various school development responsibilities, so supervision cannot be implemented effectively. Apart from this complication, the implementation of supervision is also limited by another difficulty: teachers' attitudes. Many teachers lack the enthusiasm to improve their professional skills and show a lack of mindfulness toward the principal's appeals, which hinders their ability to follow the principal's directions and guidance. As a result, increasing expertise does not significantly affect teachers' classroom teaching and learning. The authors discovered that although the principal, as an academic supervisor, is vital in improving the student learning environment, it has not been implemented effectively.

Overall, the literature highlights that academic supervision is a central responsibility of headteachers, as it directly supports teachers' professional growth and improves classroom teaching and learning. While different models of supervision, such as directive, nondirective, and collaborative, are discussed across contexts, most studies agree that adequate supervision requires close interaction with teachers, encouragement, and tailored guidance. Research from Indonesia and Malaysia shows that collaborative and supportive supervision is especially effective in boosting teacher performance. At the same time, Bangladeshi studies emphasise the importance of internal supervision led by headteachers to strengthen teaching quality. However, supervision is not without challenges: principals often face heavy workloads, time pressures, and varying levels of teacher motivation, which can limit the impact of supervision. Taken together, these findings suggest that supervision works best when it is supportive, context-sensitive, and embedded in everyday school practices, but there is still a need for more research on how headteachers in resource-constrained settings can overcome these practical barriers.

3.6. Headteachers and the Learning Environment

The goal of every school is to ensure effective classroom teaching and learning (Mosiori and Thinguri, 2015). To achieve this goal, the headteacher plays a central role in implementing policies and coordinating contributions from stakeholders such as parents, teachers, members of the school managing committee, community members, and education officers (Shanko, 2020). Stakeholders' contribution is vital in enhancing classroom teaching and learning, the school environment, and community engagement. Leadership styles also significantly affect

students' learning, especially in schools facing challenges (Minadzi and Nyame, 2016). A strong headteacher, often viewed as a catalyst for change, can significantly improve the quality of education by engaging both teachers and students in effective classroom teaching and learning (Shanko, 2020).

Riaz and Sultan (2017) carried out a study to investigate the leadership situation of headteachers in Pakistan. They found that successful school leadership highlighted how effective headteachers prioritise enhancing students' teaching and learning outcomes. The study highlighted headteachers' roles in providing physical facilities such as music centres, computer labs, wood, electrical, and agriculture workshops to provide effective classroom teaching and student learning. The study emphasised that school headteachers view parents as vital stakeholders and encourage their active participation in school improvement initiatives. According to Sumarsono et al. (2016), parents' participation in enhancing the quality of education encompasses various aspects, including donations to support education, development of school buildings, classroom decoration, supply of learning aids, and funding of extracurricular activities.

Effective school leaders build influence through personal relationships with key stakeholders, such as teachers, politicians, education officials, guardians, and parents (Mosiori and Thinguri, 2015). They actively involve parents and the local community in school development to foster mutual growth for both the school and the community (Hardman and Sandi, 2024). Wiyono et al. (2023) state that optimal success in schools' educational processes depends on the principal's effective leadership, which requires support from all stakeholders: internal resources, parents, and the community. The authors highlighted that headteachers must continuously adapt to changes, enabling them to enhance the behaviour and interactions among organisational members within and outside the school. In addition, improving the quality of the educational process involves boosting the effectiveness of organisational interactions, particularly with stakeholders, which significantly influences the advancement and development of the school organisation.

In the context of both public and private primary schools, Salam's (2015) MPhil Thesis explores the quality of primary education in Bangladesh. The study reveals that despite inadequate classroom teaching and learning materials, schoolteachers and students are essential

in ensuring quality teaching and learning. Although teachers are considered key actors, public teachers rarely deliver quality education in line with education policy expectations. In contrast, private schools' teachers try hard to ensure quality despite facing many challenges. Public schools still follow traditional teaching methods, which lack students' engagement in classroom interaction. Conversely, the private schools' teaching-learning strategies appear engaging and participatory. Notably, Salam's study does not examine the role of headteachers in shaping the learning environment or supporting teachers in these practices. This gap is significant, as leadership is often central to ensuring quality by guiding pedagogical practices, motivating teachers, and fostering an engaging classroom environment.

In Bangladesh, research revealed that the quality of the learning environment is central to improving primary schools. In the context of Bangladeshi government primary schools, Islam (2018) in his doctoral research investigated the current situation of primary teaching and learning, teachers' classroom activities and how these influence the quality of primary education. The study's findings emphasised that the classroom teaching and learning practices in Bangladeshi primary schools were unsatisfactory. The findings revealed several factors that influence the quality of teaching and learning, including the classroom atmosphere. For instance, he discovered a building home in a depressing shape at Dhuldir-Hat Government Primary School, with only damaged bamboo barriers separating the classrooms within. It was pretty challenging to teach a sound lesson in those schools. Teachers are sometimes obliged to negotiate with each other to maintain classroom discipline and a sound learning environment. The research also found that the inside of some schools had damaged plaster. In addition, children in some schools felt uncomfortable due to the unavailability of good and usable toilets. The study underlines how important the school environment is to teachers when giving lessons. Even though they are not directly related to classroom activities, the researcher concluded that primary school infrastructure, classroom appearance, layout, tidiness, and regularity substantially impact teaching. Whilst this study recognises that the learning environment can significantly impact the quality of teaching and learning, it did not consider the role of the headteachers in securing improvements concerning this.

In a different study, Sommers (2013) employed blended ethnography to examine both qualitative and quantitative data gathered from participant observations and interviews with the headteachers, education officers, and NGO education officials. This paper examines how

Bangladesh's primary education system integrates to ensure education for all, highlighting specific aspects of access and quality in impoverished rural areas area. This study found that PEDP-3's initiatives for increasing participation and improving access for disadvantaged and poor children include extending pre-primary education, enhancing physical school facilities, and developing inclusive policies. Nonetheless, the study asserted that while all these actions are critical in addressing the injustices and inequalities present in the present system, accomplishing these objectives will necessitate national commitment and accountability in addition to a readiness to put in time and welcome modifications at local and regional levels. However, this study did not consider the role of headteachers in securing improvements in this area.

It recognises that achieving quality teaching and learning goals requires a focus on national involvement, along with a commitment to invest time and accept change at the local community level, involving stakeholders like parents, guardians, teachers, community leaders and education officials. Rahman, Rahman, and Rahman (2019) examined how the classroom environment affects English teaching and learning in a primary school in Bangladesh. The findings revealed that many classroom settings were inadequate, negatively impacting the quality of education and student performance. Additionally, most schools faced shortages in instructional materials, appropriate seating, classroom lighting, and adequate ventilation.

Meje (2012) conducted a qualitative study examining the effects of physical infrastructure and classroom environments on student learning. The findings indicate that challenges such as overcrowded classrooms, insufficient restroom facilities, and the absence of appropriate playgrounds are common across all communities in Bangladesh. The research highlights that physical infrastructure significantly influences educational outcomes in both rural and urban Bangladeshi schools. Alam et al. (2023) demonstrate that primary school facilities, such as playgrounds, multimedia-equipped classrooms, libraries, outdoor play equipment, teaching aids, and health services, can improve students' academic performance. The study suggests that the government, Education Officers, the School Managing Committee, school communities, and the Parent-Teacher Association work together to improve the quality of primary education by upgrading the school environment through these instructional facilities.

When classrooms are vibrant, teachers and officials are well-trained, and communities and parents support the schools, children can reach their full potential (Anderson and September, 2014).

These themes align with a systematic review by Masino and Niño-Zarazúa (2016), reinforcing that interventions, particularly supply-side interventions, emphasise elevating student achievement by addressing infrastructure and organisational shortcomings, such as enhancing physical structures, offering appropriate teaching materials, and hiring and training additional teachers.

Overall, the literature shows that the learning environment plays a critical role in shaping the quality of teaching and student outcomes. Strong leadership from headteachers, together with the involvement of parents, teachers, and the wider community, is often highlighted as key to creating supportive and effective school environments. Studies from Pakistan, Indonesia, and Bangladesh all underline the importance of having adequate facilities, teaching materials, and active stakeholder participation in enhancing classroom learning. At the same time, many studies highlight the reality that schools in Bangladesh often face serious challenges, such as poor infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, and a lack of teaching resources, which directly hinder the quality of learning. While some research highlights the positive influence of headteachers in engaging stakeholders and fostering better environments, several studies overlook their specific role in addressing these issues. This suggests that more attention needs to be given to how headteachers, especially in resource-constrained contexts, can actively lead improvements in the learning environment alongside wider national and community efforts.

3.7. Headteachers and Staff Mentorship

Mentoring greatly enhances professional development in schools, fostering improved practices that ultimately promote teachers' learning to benefit students in the classroom (Bush et al., 2018; Hymans, 2019). Mentorship plays a crucial role in leadership, as every leader with followers must engage in mentoring and coaching (Apambilla et al., 2024). It primarily involves a relationship between two people, with one being more experienced (Mentor) shares their skills, guidance, and information with the less experienced person (Mentee) in their newly gained position (Thornton, 2015; Crisp and Alvarado-Young, 2018; Gimbel and Kefor, 2018). The key advantages of mentoring practices to boost school improvement include consistent

teacher engagement, student enrolment, discipline management, teachers' training, healthy competition, utilisation of teaching guides, and the integration of audio-visual aids in classroom teaching and learning (Munir and Amin, 2020). It is a powerful strategy for helping, motivating, influencing, guiding, and engaging mentees to improve their professional abilities and recognise their full potential (Thornton, 2015). Thus, the mentoring relationship exists between mentor and mentee, usually face-to-face over a long period, to help the mentee's academic, professional, and personal growth (Gimbel, and Kefor, 2018).

Shanks et al. (2022) investigated mentoring to assist newly qualified teachers. Their research highlights the reasons for mentoring these teachers to foster collaboration and enhance professional practices. Three diverse national contexts are studied, including Scotland, Malta, and Denmark, to determine the national and local levels of support for the Newly Qualified Teachers induction programme. The study compared the circumstances in Scotland, which adopted a national teacher induction scheme (2002), to Malta, where an induction programme has existed since 2010, and Denmark, where no national plans exist apart from some help provided at the municipal or school level. In all three nations, problems are identified in implementing mentoring, such as finding time for observation and feedback and learning how to mentor. It has also been recognised that mentoring is essential to enhance teachers' professional growth. It is an ongoing system of capacity building that takes time and patience. The study's conclusions suggest that mentors and newly qualified teachers both require time away from their teaching responsibilities to focus on their mentoring relationships.

Apambilla et al. (2024) investigated the mentoring role of headteachers and found that teachers strongly prefer headteachers' instructional role in mentoring. The study findings reveal that headteachers apply various evaluation techniques to mentor teachers, including assessing lesson plans, monitoring classroom lessons, and checking student class work. In addition, the study revealed that headteachers play a vital role in cultivating a positive school atmosphere by holding regular meetings with teachers to address instructional issues, providing constructive feedback, and ensuring that school rules and procedures uphold order and discipline. Headteachers contribute to a supportive and structured environment for teachers and students by delegating responsibilities and fostering open communication. The study findings also highlight that headteachers provide teachers a lot of guidance and support for professional development and emphasise being engaged with extracurricular activities. Teachers found it happy to accept the headteachers' instruction, practising new skills, and seeking innovative

solutions in their teaching. The findings of this study highlight the essential role of headteachers in mentoring and enhancing overall school management.

Another study by Handrianto et al. (2022) examined how mentorship can help teachers improve their professional growth in elementary schools. The study's findings showed that five factors; teamwork technique, teachers' behaviour, information sharing, ongoing learning, and teaching skill improvement—influence how mentoring strategies are implemented in teachers' professional growth. However, it emphasised that mentorship should be implemented for all teachers as an expression of lifelong learning, not just those less experienced or newly appointed. The current study's field note reveals the same statement: mentoring can be used to support the continual professional development of both new and experienced teachers.

Moyer (2014) explored three case studies of new teachers in their first year of teaching. The study investigates the efficacy of instructional methodologies and teacher development programs used in government primary schools in Bangladesh. It emphasises how new teachers' training and classroom practice might be bridged through the mentorship of head teachers. The study's results focus on how systemic, programmatic, and individual factors either facilitate or hinder the implementation of teacher training in the classroom. At the program stage, the school headteacher and the school's learning culture influence teachers' classroom behaviour. The study suggests that head teachers at government primary schools should provide instructional leadership training to improve their ability to support teachers in the classroom. Furthermore, effective school leaders assist new teachers by planning joint initiatives (induction and mentorship), establishing internal professional development, and encouraging collaborative exchanges.

While mentoring is a valuable approach to teachers' professional development, it may not achieve the intended results without proper planning. Munir and Amin (2020) emphasised that the success of mentoring relies on the commitment and involvement of the mentors. Consequently, effective mentors must clearly understand the teaching skill gaps among teachers and the learning capacities of students. Poorly designed mentoring programs often fail to meet the learning needs of mentees (Munir and Amin, 2020). Apambilla et al. (2014) investigate headteachers' mentoring role in the Pru West District. Findings reveal that headteachers apply various instructional leadership techniques to mentor teachers, including assessing lesson plans, observing classroom lessons, reviewing students' classwork, and

providing necessary feedback to enhance teachers' instructional practice. The study recommended that headteachers' mentoring experience should be considered a key requirement apart from qualification and rank. Headteachers should strive to enrol in professional mentorship certification courses, and the directorate ought to appoint a qualified scheduling officer responsible for mentoring headteachers.

Taken together, the literature confirms that mentorship is widely recognised as a powerful tool for teachers' professional growth and, by extension, student learning. Research across different contexts shows that mentoring supports new and experienced teachers alike, helping to bridge the gap between training and classroom practice. While studies emphasise the positive influence of headteachers in providing feedback, guidance, and professional support, they also highlight persistent challenges, such as time constraints, limited resources, and poorly planned programmes. Importantly, the evidence suggests that mentoring is most effective when it is well-structured, when mentors are committed and skilled, and when it is embedded into a school's culture of continuous learning. However, gaps remain in understanding how headteachers in resource-limited settings can balance their administrative roles with sustained mentoring, and how systemic support could strengthen these practices.

3.8. Headteachers and Decentralisation of Power

Decentralisation is a process whereby power is delegated from the central government to school districts and schools to support educational provision (Bush, 2016). It assumes the democratic involvement of leaders and stakeholders. McGinn and Welsh (1999) note that three key factors account for an upturn in interest in education decentralisation. First, they argue that political and economic globalisation has strengthened localised power while weakening central governments. Second, they note that rising enrolments worldwide, along with the growth in teacher and student numbers, have reduced the capacity of centralised governments to maintain quality and public satisfaction. Finally, they highlight that advances in information and communication technologies enable control of education systems without heavy central administration. According to McGinn and Welsh (1999), decentralisation can support key objectives, such as improving the quality of schooling and increasing innovation by redistributing some decision-making authority to local administrations.

The promise of decentralisation is that it alters governance and deepens democracy (Faguet, 2014). Jopling and Hadfield (2015) show evidence that England and Wales took the policy

which focused on collaboration as the product of policies that follow localism and decentralisation in education. The education system in the United Kingdom relies on local education authorities (LEAs) to provide all support, such as employing staff, supporting teachers' training, and following up on school inspections (Jopling and Hadfield, 2015). However, the author highlights that over the intervening stage, policies upholding decentralisation have substantially impacted the education system. Now, in the United Kingdom, every school has a governing body with the local community, parents' representatives, schoolteachers, school staff, and the school headteacher as an ex-official member (Bush, 2016) and the school system follows a highly decentralised system in respect of school choice, budgeting and administration.

Bush (2016) showed that highly centralised administration systems do not allow the school and the local communities to take decisions and initiatives regarding school improvement. Whereas within decentralised systems, the devolution of given key stakeholders significant powers to make school improvements (Jeong, Lee, and Cho, 2017). Policymakers have consistently advocated decentralisation to improve educational quality (Channa, 2016). Decentralisation encourages local political people to participate in school improvement activities (Faguet, Fox, Pöschl, 2015). In Colombia, decentralisation enhanced enrolment rates in community schools, and also it provided local administrators with the communication to be more accountable to make the school develop (Faguet and Sánchez, 2014). There are many arguments that decentralisation has many benefits concerning school development. It can be participation in decision-making and good governance (Nadeem, 2016). The research also showed that decentralisation of power makes public service activities closer to the general people as they have more opportunities to participate in local activities and policies than in the centralised one (Bush, 2016).

As Mullick and Deppeler (2011) acknowledged, the central management system frustrates the wider community seeking to contribute to school improvement initiatives. Power centralisation in primary schools in Bangladesh, especially at the local Upazila level, was affected significantly. This centralisation takes the form of political interference and the bureaucratic rules and regulations provided by the national education policies (Azizuddin, 2014).

Mullick, Deppeler, and Sharma (2012) found that school leaders in Bangladesh face several challenges in implementing inclusive education (IE), one of which is their lack of authority. The findings of this study revealed that the centralised management system makes it challenging for the leader to decide to implement IE. The study showed that the school headteachers and local stakeholders cannot be involved in primary education decision-making or policy development. One participant, a headteacher of this study, was frustrated to state that if they face any problem, they need to inform the Directorate of Primary Education (DPE) and wait for a decision from DPE, who rarely pay quick attention to school improvement challenges. He added that they (DPE officials) can sort the issue sitting in the air conditioning room, whereas at the field level, headteachers face severe challenges in school improvement, as well as relevant topics. Another participant of this study added that even in respect of more minor problems that are related to funding to carry out minor school repairs, headteachers needed to inform the education office and wait for a long time, sometimes even a year, to get the decision and sometimes this decision goes against the headteachers' demand. This study identified the significant challenges to making schools inclusive, such as controlling the education administrative system and decision-making process at the central level.

In their research, Mullick, Deppeler, and Sharma (2012) identified the education officer as a crucial influential leader in all school improvement initiatives. Although the education officer does not occupy a formal leadership role within the school, they are accountable for academic monitoring and supervision, guiding headteachers through the assistant education officer to execute school improvement efforts and activities. However, their actions position the headteacher as the second influential leader in the school, relegating parents and teachers to a lower status in decision-making. This structure reflects a bureaucratic administrative system, characterised by obvious hierarchical control. The study showed that all higher-authority officials make decisions about school improvements within Bangladesh's primary education system.

Bureaucracy within this centralised leadership and education management system is a barrier to headteacher leadership and school improvement. Ali (2011) examines the concepts, styles, tendencies, and present practices of headteachers' leadership in four private secondary schools located in both rural and urban areas of Bangladesh, finding that school leaders encounter a considerable bureaucratic burden when attempting to implement school improvement initiatives. Moreover, after a significant time, the school leaders may start getting afraid of the

rules and regulations, with the risk that they will refuse or abuse the rules and hold up to the existing order. The research examines how bureaucracy dominates educational administration in Bangladesh. Head teachers experience bureaucratic harassment while managing their schools, as government-appointed education administrators oversee school management. The processes involved in educational decision-making are often lengthy, which delays school improvements. Schools face many challenges, including a shortage of qualified and trained teachers, inadequate physical infrastructure, as well as a deficiency of resources such as teaching materials, classroom furniture and computers. private schools primarily rely on government funding for teacher salaries, development initiatives, and professional development. At times, government officials interact with school leaders in a manner that makes them feel undervalued. Moreover, government officials are occasionally appointed as chairpersons of the SMC, which further delays the decision-making process, as they are often preoccupied with other administrative duties.

Hossain et al. (2017) identified that local political leaders, especially those from the ruling party, significantly affect school management practices, hindering progress. Their research revealed that both local and national political figures show interest in local school performance for various reasons: a genuine concern for education, the social capital that comes with chairing or being part of School Management Committees (SMCs), education projects that offer chances to allocate contracts or benefits, and schools serving as venues for local democratic competition concerning performance, where different political parties strive to demonstrate their superiority by ensuring effective teaching. In one case, local power brokers manipulated the school to serve their personal interests and marginalised opposing voices from school management. As a result, people were afraid to voice their concerns even as the school faced declining performance. The study also found that local political competition could promote higher standards and enhance schools when oversight is generally constructive. However, there are cases where political competition tied to party affiliations undermines and diverts attention from improvement efforts in education.

Overall, the studies illustrate that decentralisation is often promoted as a pathway to improved educational quality, greater accountability, and stronger community participation. Evidence from both developed and developing contexts shows that devolving authority can empower schools and local stakeholders to respond more effectively to their own challenges. Yet, research from Bangladesh highlights the limitations of highly centralised systems, where

bureaucracy, political interference, and weak local authority restrict headteachers' ability to lead school improvement. This contrast suggests that while decentralisation has the potential to encourage innovation and responsiveness, it is not without risks—especially when political interests dominate or when local capacity is weak. The literature therefore points to a critical balance: decentralisation must be matched with transparent systems, adequate resources, and genuine empowerment of school leaders if it is to translate into meaningful improvements in teaching and learning.

3.9. Theoretical Perspectives on Educational Leadership

Educational leadership has been examined through several theoretical perspectives that highlight different ways in which leaders influence teaching and learning. Leithwood, Harris, and Hopkins (2020) emphasise that, after classroom teaching, leadership has the most significant impact on student learning. Bush and Glover (2014) identify a range of leadership models, including instructional, managerial, and transformational leadership, each reflecting different assumptions about how leadership contributes to school improvement.

Male and Palaiologou (2015) argue that effective pedagogical leadership goes beyond managerial and performance goals to include the moral, social, and cultural dimensions of education. They explain that pedagogy involves more than classroom instruction, it represents a relationship between theory and practice that is deeply embedded in social and cultural contexts. Pedagogical leadership, therefore, focuses on creating learning environments where interactions among teachers, learners, families, and the wider community are central.

According to Sergiovanni (1998), pedagogical leadership moves further than administrative duties and is grounded in shared moral values and a collective sense of purpose. Pedagogical leaders aim to build a collaborative learning community where teachers, students, and parents work together toward common goals. They model ethical behaviour, support teachers' professional growth, and foster conditions that enable effective teaching and learning. In this sense, pedagogical leadership combines moral guidance, instructional support, and effective management to strengthen both the culture and performance of the school.

Instructional leadership remains one of the most influential concepts in educational leadership. Bush (2015) notes that it first emerged in the United States when researchers demonstrated that school leadership directly affects student outcomes. During the 1980s, it became a dominant

model, portraying principals as key figures responsible for guiding teaching and shaping the curriculum. However, subsequent scholars highlighted its limitations, such as limited attention to how leadership develops, the requirement for subject-specific expertise, and the recognition that leadership should be distributed among senior, middle, and teacher leaders. These critiques led to broader approaches such as leadership for learning, which integrates shared leadership and a stronger emphasis on collective professional development.

Bush (2007) differentiates instructional leadership from other models by explaining that it focuses on the direction of influence—how leaders guide teaching and learning—rather than on the source of influence. Effective instructional leaders support both teacher development and student growth through modelling, monitoring, and professional dialogue (Southworth, 2002). Bush and Glover (2002) similarly define it as leadership that targets student learning through teachers, focusing on the impact and direction of leadership practices. While instructional leadership is central to improving teaching quality, Bush (2003) cautions that it may overlook other aspects of school life such as student welfare, socialisation, and extracurricular engagement.

Hallinger and Murphy (1985) developed one of the most influential instructional leadership models, identifying three key dimensions: defining the school's mission, managing the instructional programme, and promoting a positive learning climate. Principals are expected to set clear goals, coordinate curriculum and instruction, monitor student progress, and support teacher professional growth. Later, Hallinger (2011) expanded this model into the leadership for learning framework, which views leadership as a shared process extending beyond the principal. This approach recognises that leadership effectiveness is shaped by both the organisational environment and the leader's personal values, knowledge, and experience. It identifies core actions such as establishing collaborative goals, aligning resources, promoting teacher learning, and maintaining supportive conditions for effective teaching.

Transformational leadership focuses on how leaders inspire and motivate others by developing a shared vision, building trust, and encouraging professional commitment (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2005). It assumes that effective leadership transforms both individuals and organisations through collective moral purpose. In contrast, instructional leadership concentrates on improving teaching and learning through the direct involvement of leaders in classroom and

curriculum matters (Hallinger, 2011). Pedagogical leadership, meanwhile, extends these ideas by emphasising collaboration, reflection, and shared professional dialogue (Heikka & Waniganayake, 2011). It also contributes to strengthening the teaching profession and shaping societal values about education.

While these leadership theories offer valuable insights into effective school practice, they often portray leadership in idealised ways and pay limited attention to the broader social, cultural, and political contexts in which leadership occurs. Foucault's theoretical lens provides a contrasting perspective by conceptualising leadership as a form of power that operates through discourse, relationships, and institutional practices. This study applies Foucault's ideas to explore how headteachers' leadership is constructed and negotiated within everyday school contexts, revealing how power circulates among headteachers, teachers, and other stakeholders in the process of school improvement.

3.10. Conclusion

The literature review suggests that headteachers are crucial for school improvement efforts. Headteachers are accountable for ensuring a child-friendly environment to implement these improvements. The literature review sheds light on headteachers' complex roles, practices, and the challenges they face in fulfilling their responsibilities. As the literature on Bangladesh indicates, few studies have recognised the role of headteachers in leading school improvement initiatives, especially in primary schools. This present study addresses this knowledge gap. Therefore, by exploring headteachers' roles, their skills in negotiating with key stakeholders, and the power dynamics in their interactions with teachers, This study offers a unique contribution to existing debates in school improvement research, particularly in developing countries like Bangladesh, where knowledge in this area is limited.

Chapter 4: Theoretical Framework

4.1 Introduction

This study utilised Foucault's work to examine the power relations between head teachers and relevant stakeholders in the context of school improvement. Michel Foucault was one of the postmodernist thinkers of the twentieth century. As a writer, he addressed various subjects, such as philosophy, sociology, and history. His ideas are widely applied in multiple disciplines, such as government policy, medicine, and education. Within educational research, Foucault's theory is beneficial for analysing how power is exercised within the social structure and relationships. This study employs Foucault's concept of power as a theoretical lens to examine how the headteachers' leadership practices, shaped by their positional roles and personal subjectivities, affect school improvement in Bangladeshi government primary schools. Foucault's perspective is especially valuable because it views power not only as formal authority embedded in rules and policies but also as something enacted through everyday practices, relationships, and self-management. This enables a nuanced analysis of how headteachers interact with teachers, students, and the broader community, and how these interactions contribute to or constrain school improvement.

Accordingly, this study adopts three levels of Foucault's power: subjectivity and ethics, governmentality, and disciplinary power, with particular emphasis on hierarchical observation, normalising judgment, and examination. These concepts provide the analytical tools to interrogate how leadership practices are enacted, resisted, and reproduced within primary schools.

4.2. Knowledge and power

Power and knowledge are essential concepts in Michel Foucault's works. Foucault's idea of power/knowledge shows that power and knowledge are closely connected, arguing that they are not interchangeable or entirely separate, but rather mutually constitutive. As Christensen (2024) explains, power is deeply linked to knowledge. This does not mean that "knowledge is power" in a simple way. Instead, Foucault (1980) argued that there is no knowledge without power and no power without knowledge; they always work together. This means that what people accept as valid or essential knowledge is influenced by those in power, and that knowledge also helps keep power in place. In educational settings, such as government primary schools, headteachers do not lead only through their positional roles, but also through dominant discourses; rules, policies, and ideas about what makes a 'good school' or 'good teaching' and

effective leadership. These ways of thinking come from power/knowledge; they guide how people act and how their actions are judged. For example, when headteachers possess deep pedagogical knowledge, they are not merely informed teachers but influential leaders shaping how teaching and learning are understood and practised.

"Power exists only when put into action." (Foucault, 1982, p.219). Not all consequences of power are negative: "It induces pleasure, forms knowledge, produces discourse." (Foucault, 1980, p.119). Foucault (1980) asserts that all knowledge is possible and occurs only within a vast network or system of power relations that permit the emergence of knowledge, the utterance of claims acknowledged as "true" in any given context, and the initial generation of what constitutes knowledge. For instance, many activities in a school context exhibit interactions based on power and knowledge (Gillies, 2013). Teachers, for example, can assign grades to promote preferred knowledge, give promotions to students and write letters of recommendation to value specific knowledge. Power is also evident in curriculum and evaluation systems. Preferred knowledge, as outlined in the curriculum, will influence children's learning. Teachers, in turn, evaluate student abilities based on how they meet prescribed curriculum standards.

According to Foucault, power does not simply belong to individuals or institutions; it only exists when exercised, and its effects can be repressive and productive (Foucault, 1982). Repressive power typically relates to the juridical model characterised by (1) power being possessed something held by an authority (such as a headteacher or the state) (2) a flow of power from a central source downward through rules, restrictions and punishments, and (3) the exercise of power being mainly repressive (e.g., in the form of a ban enforced by sanctions) (Christensen, 2024). However, Foucault also identified a different type of power; the disciplinary model, which operates less through visible rules and punishments and more through subtle processes that shape how people think, act, and see themselves. This power is productive as it aids in shaping identities and behaviours, often without resorting to force. For instance, a headteacher may use motivational strategies, school management committees (SMCs), or student councils to create a shared purpose and responsibility among staff and pupils. In this case, teachers and students are not simply following rules out of fear of punishment but are influenced by norms and expectations that encourage them to act in specific

ways. These actions reflect how disciplinary power, rooted in discourse and daily practices, helps produce subjects participating in their regulation (Foucault, 1980).

Thus, headteachers in schools may exercise juridical and disciplinary power. They enforce rules (repressive power) while also shaping behaviours and values through relationships, dialogue, and institutional culture (productive power). Understanding this balance helps reveal how leadership operates not just through authority but also through shaping beliefs, behaviours, and identities within the school environment.

4.3 Subjectivity

Foucault's concept of subjectivity explores how individuals perceive themselves, shaped by surrounding rules, expectations, and systems (Foucault, 1982). He believed that individuals are not entirely free to define who they are; rather, it is influenced by power dynamics and external elements, such as societal norms, institutions, and prevailing discourses of truth. Instead of being innate or unchanging, subjectivity is formed through everyday practices and power relations, which are manifested in schools, families, and various institutions, thereby affecting behaviour and self-perception. As Foucault explains:

This form of power that applies itself to immediate everyday life categorizes the individual, marks him by his own individuality, attaches him to his own identity, imposes a law of truth on him that he must recognize and have others recognize in him. It is a form of power that makes individuals subjects (Foucault 2002a, p. 331).

Foucauldian ethics highlighted the importance of the intentionality of individuals' activities and how these activities are connected to individuals' moral responsibilities and the self. Foucault believed the subject is formed and shaped by multiple discourses intrinsically linked to social structures and practices (Niesche, 2016). Foucault's term 'Subject' refers to two meanings: 'first subject to somebody else's control and dependence and, second, tied to one's own identity by a conscience or self-knowledge' (Foucault, 1982, p. 212).

The word "subject" can signify two different things: either the individual as subject as he/she is attached to his/her own identity (creating his/her sense) by a conscience or self-knowledge, or he/she is subject to someone else by control (an external force or authority for example

institution, government or social norms) and dependency. Foucault, states that power often divides individuals into different categories. It labels and attaches people based on their social uniqueness and identity, perhaps forcing them to think and accept the law of truth. It is a type of authority that makes people subject to these truths. Foucault's notion of subjectivity means that individuals (in the case of my research, headteachers) are made into the subjects not by birth but by the influence of power and the practice of truth (Gillies, 2013). Foucault argued that an individual's subjectivity is determined by systems of power already in place, e.g. the school or state.

To explain the above context more effectively, we can consider how policy expectations and leadership actions shape a headteacher's subjectivity (Niesche, 2013). For example, a headteacher may be instructed to improve student literacy outcomes in response to national education policy and guidance from the Upazila Education Office. In turn, the headteacher organises regular teacher meetings and classroom observations to ensure that early-grade teachers use phonics-based instruction as recommended. The headteacher may also model these techniques during teacher training sessions and follow up with feedback. In this case, the teachers' classroom practices are shaped by direct policy and the headteacher's interpretation and enactment of that policy. This shows how the headteacher's subjectivity as a leader acting within a web of expectations, discourses, and relationships guides others, while being shaped by external structures. It also illustrates how disciplinary power operates through discourses of improvement and accountability, influencing how headteachers and teachers understand their roles.

4.4 Ethics

In Foucault's work, ethics is not just about following rules or knowing what is right or wrong. Instead, ethics is about how individuals shape their own behaviour and make decisions about how to live and act (Gillies, 2013). It focuses on people's relationship with themselves, especially how they try to become a particular person by thinking about their actions, values, and responsibilities. Foucault saw ethics as part of a wider idea of subjectivity: how people are made into subjects by power and how they shape themselves through their choices. In this sense, ethics is about self-governance. People are influenced by systems like schools, policies, and cultural norms, but they also personally reflect on and respond to these influences.

In school leadership, ethics can be seen in how headteachers reflect on their roles, treat teachers and students, and respond to policy demands while trying to do what they believe is right. For example, a headteacher wants to improve student attendance to enhance students' learning outcomes. However, how they choose to do this, whether through punishment, discourse, support, or community involvement, shows their ethical thinking and personal judgment. Therefore, ethics in this study is not just about professional codes of conduct, but also about how headteachers act in ways that reflect their values, how they balance power and care, and how they try to be effective leaders while staying true to themselves and their school communities.

Foucault identified four aspects of ethics (the kind of relationship a person has with themselves). These determine an individual's conduct: 1. Ethical substance 2. Mode of subjection 3. Self-forming activities 4. Telos. Freie and Eppley (2014, p. 657) state that the first aspect, ethical substance, informs the answer to the question, 'What aspect of me is subject to judgment?' According to Niesche and Gowlett (2019), ethical substance is an important aspect a person might use for moral assessment to ensure moral conduct. In the school context, the principal, as a school leader, understands their position and the ethical substance of their responsibilities, such as working collaboratively with stakeholders in the broader school community to maintain a positive relationship (Freie and Eppley, 2014). The headteacher's job description outlines what is expected of the headteacher.

Gillies (2013) notes that school leaders (headteachers) are then further influenced by a local authority's (or, in Bangladesh, Upazila) expectations to fulfil the school vision. Over time, these expectations shift into the ethical substance of a leader's leadership, shaping how each headteacher serves their school according to the stakeholders' expectations (Gillies, 2013). Through this mechanism, Freie and Eppley (2014) suggest that school headteachers become responsible for carrying out their school improvement activities, making sense of them through ethical substance. For example, a headteacher may oversee achieving the school's aim through administrative tasks such as creating and resourcing a yearly plan for enhancing students' learning outcomes, as seen in Bangladesh, with the School Level Improvement Plan. The head teacher assumes these actions by aligning himself/herself according to professional standards for efficient school management and societal norms, but also by recognising that these aspects of his/her role are subject to the judgement of key stakeholders.

According to Foucault, the second aspect of ethics is a mode of subjection, the process by which individuals are encouraged to assume their moral responsibilities (Niesche and Gowlett, 2019). For example, a headteacher, guided by national education policy that emphasises community involvement in school improvement, may take the initiative to organise regular meetings with parents and local leaders through the School Management Committee (SMC). He could initiate a community literacy campaign via parent gatherings, collaborating with the parent-teacher association to assist students facing reading challenges at home. By doing so, the headteacher sees himself as a school manager and a moral agent working to build inclusive and supportive relationships between the school and its wider community. This reflects how his/her sense of responsibility to fairness, inclusion, and student success is shaped by external expectations and internalised through his/her role. According to Freie and Eppley (2014), subjection is all about who or what guides/directs the decisions made by leaders that enable them to establish a practical educational setting.

Foucault's third aspect of ethics is self-forming practices. Self-forming practices are activities through which individuals actively shape their character and ethical behaviour. According to Gillies (2013, p. 17), these practices involve "mental techniques, self-discipline, and the cultivation of personal virtues." They are essential for individuals, especially leaders, to engage with societal roles and responsibilities. Foucault identifies these practices as the third aspect of ethics, focusing on how individuals work on themselves to become ethical subjects (Niesche and Gowlett, 2019).

Self-forming practices are vital for school leaders, such as headteachers, to effectively lead and engage the community. By leading parent-teacher meetings, headteachers can inspire teachers to adopt inclusive teaching practices and encourage parents to participate actively in the school's vision. These actions foster a collaborative school environment and demonstrate how self-forming practices contribute to ethical leadership. To support these self-forming activities, leaders may engage in continual professional development, appropriate leadership courses, and relevant qualifications, as suggested by Gillies (2013). These activities help leaders grow and act ethically in their everyday work, aligning with Foucault's concept of ethics as a process of self-formation.

Foucault's fourth aspect of ethics is telos - the attainment of a particular way of being that is typical of the ethical subject and, more precisely, the achievement of self-mastery, or the kind of person one wants to be (Foucault, 1992, 2000). A leader's values and beliefs will be reflected in telos, making it an immensely significant aspect of leadership behaviour (Gillies, 2013). For example, if the headteacher aspires to be a person of integrity, their telos will substantially influence their actions, guiding choices in particular leadership scenarios.

4.5 Governmentality

Foucault's concept of government goes beyond traditional political institutions. He uses the term to describe the various systems, institutions, and everyday practices, such as administration, education, and policy, through which individuals' behaviour is directed and managed. He explains that government involves specific techniques, methods, and procedures that allow some people to guide or control the actions of others. However, Foucault suggests that these forms of governance are now facing a major crisis, as societies begin to question and reassess how authority is exercised and what it means to govern effectively (Foucault, 2000).

Governmentality is the primary aspect of governance that is intensely focused on influencing the behaviour of others (Gillies, 2013). The term 'governmentality' was created by combining the terms 'government' with 'mentality' or 'rationality' to comprehend this specific area of study, how government is rationalised and justified (Mifsud, 2020). Foucault's theory of governmentality can be defined as the 'conduct of conduct' (Foucault, 1983). Governmentality refers to how individuals and institutions shape, steer and direct the behaviour (conduct) of others (Gillies, 2013). This also links to one's conduct and how individuals shape their own conduct through self-regulation. Governmentality as an idea sheds light on the application of power in various contexts (Foucault, 1980b), e.g. where an institution or society enacts processes or expectations that control an individual's behaviour. For Foucault, an institution such as a school assumes a hierarchical power structure to govern staff and pupils. However, this structure is fragile, and individual cooperation is needed to implement actions (Mifsud, 2020).

Freie and Eppley (2014) explain the term 'governmentality' as the management of conduct; this involves directing individual behaviour through implementing regulations and social norms. The authors add that in the school leadership context, the principal of the school is not only subject to shaping the individual behaviour or practise the norms and regulations

(government), instead the principal serves as the vehicle of the government, influencing and controlling the behaviour (conducts) of both staff and students in response to the governmentality of national and local policy, structures and processes.

Gillies (2013) applies Foucault's notion of governmentality to educational management and leadership. He argues that governmentality is evident in the discourses on educational leadership, which are focused on improving schools, providing examples of how power can be used in local authority relationships with school headteachers and how headteachers work with stakeholders to undertake assigned tasks via the authority. In schools, governmentality is then practised by the headteachers and key stakeholders who may have responsibilities to make school improvements. Governmentality, for instance, could be carried out through monitoring or supervision (surveillance) of schools, the requirement for self-evaluation or the submission to the local authority of a school improvement plan and yearly progress reports.

Dean (2010) broadened the definition of government by emphasising that governmentality involves more than just carrying out the government's functions (enacting laws, setting standards, and enforcing regulations); it also entails influencing people and groups more profoundly by reshaping their needs, desires, and way of life to meet particular objectives or expectations. This idea of governmentality highlights how the government shapes people's actions, behaviours, and lifestyles, affecting how they see themselves and their contributions to the organisation or society. According to Foucault, modern governmental logic is both individualising and totalising in its quest to understand what it is to control an individual and a group of people.

4.6 Disciplinary Power

Foucault's concept of disciplinary power is central to this study. According to Foucault (1995), discipline is a mechanism of power that targets individuals as instruments to shape and construct their norms and behaviour. He also notes that this power is not exercised through domination but through modest and calculated control integrated into everyday practices to ensure that individuals are constantly subjected to this.

Discipline 'makes' individuals; it is the specific technique of a power that regards individuals both as objects and as instruments of its exercise. It is not a triumphant power, which because of its own excess can pride itself on its omnipotence; it is a modest,

suspicious power, which functions as a calculated, but permanent economy (Foucault, 1977, p.170).

Here, Foucault clarifies how, through the mechanism of disciplinary power, individuals shape their thoughts, approaches and actions according to norms and expectations. Foucault says that power, unlike dictatorial control, works to discreetly mould social structures.

Gillies (2013) highlights that Foucault describes disciplinary power as individualising and totalising, focusing on how power operates within the society. For example, disciplinary power may be individualising where close monitoring, judging, or assessing a specific individual's behaviour leads to greater conformity to expected norms. Disciplinary power is also totalising because it applies its strategies to individuals and institutions.

In 'Discipline and Punish' (Foucault, 1977), disciplinary power is not about rulers issuing commands from above (a juridical or legal understanding of power), but about how power operates through everyday practices, rules, and routines that shape people's behaviour. This kind of power works subtly and continuously—it trains individuals to behave in specific ways by encouraging self-monitoring and adherence to norms. For example, teachers and students in schools may follow timetables, attend regular evaluations, or use performance data to measure improvement. These practices help ensure that people are doing what is expected efficiently and effectively, according to the institution's standards. Importantly, people begin to internalise these expectations—they start to govern themselves, even when no one is watching. Foucault calls this the creation of "disciplined bodies."

Gillies (2013) examines the contradictory circumstances faced by managers, administrators, and leaders in the field of education who, despite their positions of perceived authority, also face various forms of discipline. Even if these people hold positions of authority (e.g. headteachers), they are nonetheless subject to control and discipline from the institutional structures within which they work. Thus, they are subject to many forms of control, such as surveillance, self-management, discipline, and control. These are all intended to regulate leaders' behaviour to meet standards or expectations. Despite their strong positions, leaders frequently need to regulate their conduct, plans, actions, and decisions to conform to the standards of their profession and the expectations of their organisations. This activity could be completed through external or internal surveillance or self-management and control.

According to Foucault (1977), the application of disciplinary power comes no doubt by employing simple disciplinary tools such as hierarchical observation, normalising judgement, and the examination, which combines all three procedures. Though Foucault elaborates on this relationship in school settings, Gillies (2013, p. 58) suggests it can also be applied to educational leadership.

Hierarchical Observation

According to Foucault (1977), hierarchical observation acts as an apparatus where observing others generates power, and control systems make individuals visible and simpler to manage. Building on this, Niesche and Gowlett (2019) argue that such a relationship between observation and control strengthens authority within education. Several methods exist for conducting hierarchical observation in a school context (Freie and Eppley, 2014). It has long been a key component of the educational system (Gillies, 2013). According to Gillies, it is evident at the micro level through the use of monitors, officials, and other ranking systems for students; it is also evident in the way that staff members are arranged from the least senior to the most senior and in the way that local authorities oversee their operations up to the director of education. This vertical management approach functions best in a highly developed system with increased accountability and responsibility, meaning that everyone is both observer and observed at every stage.

Foucault introduces the panopticon as a disciplinary system that can oversee its mechanisms in addition to being a means of monitoring inmates (Niesche, 2011). Gillies (2013) exemplifies the 'panopticon', a prison concept developed by Jeremy Bentham in which every prisoner can be seen from a single point. The prisoner believes they are constantly being watched, allowing them to control themselves and modify their actions. While the prisoner is exposed, power is evident in the central watchtower. The panopticon offers a potent social metaphor by putting power in light, inspection, and architecture. It also employs doubt as a social control mechanism, pushing "rational" people to assume they are being watched when, perhaps, they are not (Hope, 2015).

Niesche and Gowlett (2019) give an example in a school context, pointing out that schools and other institutions include architectural elements that enable ongoing, personalised observation. These allow for the possibility of observation. As a type of surveillance and observation, a school might, for instance, have pupils seated in rows and classrooms designed so that someone

walking down the hallway may pass multiple classrooms and can see and hear what is happening in those classrooms. Foucault (1977) notes that surveillance has a lasting impact, even when it occurs occasionally. For example, in the case of a school, the teachers and pupils become aware that anyone passing by can observe what is going on, which, in turn, influences how they behave. Furthermore, Gillies (2013) notes that educational leaders may take on a conscious surveillance role since it will assist them in fulfilling their responsibilities, whilst simultaneously being subjected to monitoring from various stakeholders such as local authorities, inspectors, and parents.

Normalising Judgement

In his analysis of disciplinary power, Michel Foucault introduces the concept of normalising judgement as a key mechanism through which modern institutions like schools or prisons control people. Instead of using force, they create rules or standards—what is considered "normal"—and then judge everyone based on how close they are to that standard. This helps create a sense of sameness, but at the same time, it points out differences between people. These differences are not just noticed—they are measured, ranked, and used to decide how people should be treated. The quote below shows how this process works: even in a system that seems fair and equal, the use of norms helps organise and control people by comparing them.

In a sense, the power of normalisation imposes homogeneity; but it individualizes by making it possible to measure gaps, to determine levels, to fix specialities and to render the differences useful by fitting them one to another. It is easy to understand how the power of the norm functions within a system of formal equality, since within a homogeneity that is the rule, the norm introduces, as a useful imperative and as a result of measurement, all the shading of individual differences (Foucault, 1977, p. 184).

Foucault's conceptions of normalising judgement refer to standardising actions and processes. This normalisation unifies individuals' behaviour and performance within an institution and produces a standard for measuring potential gaps and deviations from norms. Within normalising judgement, everybody is regarded as a formal equal in social standards; according to Foucault (1977), equality does not imply complete equivalency but permits individuals to be recognised according to the norms they enact. Gillies (2013) illustrates this by using the example of a school inspection: leadership is a common talent in a school system, but

outstanding leaders are identified by their most successful leadership practices, which enable them to be recognised as 'ideal' leaders.

At the heart of all disciplinary systems functions a small penal mechanism. It enjoys a kind of judicial privilege with its own laws, its specific offences, its particular forms of judgement (Foucault, 1977, p. 178).

Foucault's idea of "a small penal mechanism" is central to all discipline systems. According to Foucault, modern discipline institutions (such as schools, prisons, and the military) have internal rules and methods of enforcing them, distinct from formal laws. These systems judge and regulate behaviour using tiny, frequently imperceptible mechanisms like appraisal or surveillance. Instead of employing conventional punishment, the authority often continuously observes and modifies people's behaviour to mould it. Following the rules, norms, and expectations is rewarded while breaking them is punished (Gillies, 2013). Breaking norms may include commission and omission sins, meaning that failing to comply or inaction can also result in a penalty.

According to Foucault (1977), normalising judgment aims for conformity. As Freie and Eppley (2014) note, this may be accomplished by detecting and penalising outliers who do not meet an established standard. The authors offer an example of normalising judgement by describing a principal's talk regarding the normalisation of new teachers. The principal wants new teachers to "fit perfectly into the frame." They must accept the normalised demands of conforming to the principal's disciplinary, cultural, and environmental standards (Freie and Eppley, 2014, p.665).

According to Niesche and Gowlett (2019), "normalising judgement" describes a power-based corrective process that uses mild penalties to change conduct. Procedures can be set up to monitor rule violations by offering guidelines and frameworks. For example, a school uniform policy aims to standardise students' dress. The school enforces a policy about expected adherence to the requirement that students wear the proper uniform. Teachers are expected to enforce such a policy or set of rules, and principals and other school leaders draft the supporting policies.

Examination

In *Discipline and Punish*, Foucault highlights the role of the examination as a key tool of modern disciplinary power. Through regular examination and observation, individuals are constantly monitored, judged, and compared to others. The examination combines surveillance and normalising judgement, allowing institutions like schools, prisons, and hospitals to classify people, shape their behaviour, and manage them more effectively. The following quote shows how examinations are about gaining knowledge and producing individuals who fit into structured systems of control:

The examination is at the centre of the procedures that constitute the individual as effect and object of power, as effect and object of knowledge. It is the examination which, by combining hierarchical surveillance and normalising judgement, assures the great disciplinary functions of distribution and classification, maximum extraction of forces and time, continuous genetic accumulation, optimum combination of aptitudes and, thereby, the fabrication of cellular, organic, genetic and combinatory individually (Foucault, 1977, p. 192).

Foucault explains that the examination is a fundamental instrument used to define and control individuals. It is both the target of power (since individuals are being judged or ranked) and the object of ability and knowledge (because it is used to categorise and interpret individuals in a specific way). According to Niesche and Gowlett (2019), "examination" can also refer to a practice that normalises judgment while combining hierarchical observation. As a normalising gaze, Foucault criticises the examination as "a surveillance that makes it possible to qualify, classify, and punish" (Foucault, 1991a, p. 184).

In the following quote, Foucault says that the examination brings together two main things: watching people closely (like teachers or supervisors do) and judging them based on what is considered "normal" or expected. This creates a way of looking at people that helps to label and sort them. It helps those in power decide who is doing well, who needs to improve, and who is falling behind. Because it is so important for keeping order, the examination becomes a regular and formal part of how schools, workplaces, and other systems are run.

The examination combines the techniques of an observing hierarchy and those of a normalizing judgement. It is a normalizing gaze, a surveillance that makes it possible to qualify, to classify and to punish. It establishes over individuals a visibility through which

one differentiates them and judges them. That is why, in all the mechanisms of discipline, the examination is highly ritualized (Foucault, 1977, p. 184).

Foucault says the examination is a method that involves people being watched and evaluated to determine whether they are qualified or, instead, identified as not living up to expectations. Therefore, the entire examination procedure is highly disciplined and ritualised to control the individual.

4.7 Conclusion

In conclusion, this theoretical framework has drawn on Foucault's concepts to explore how educational leadership operates within systems of knowledge and power. By examining how subjectivity, ethics, and governmentality shape leadership practices, this study highlights how leaders are shaped by and participate in broader structures of control. Key aspects of disciplinary power—such as hierarchical observation, normalising judgement, and examination—reveal how individuals within educational settings are observed, assessed, and guided to conform to institutional norms. Through this Foucauldian lens, educational leadership is not only a matter of decision-making or influence but a complex process of managing people, knowledge, and behaviour within a network of power relations.

Chapter 5: Research Methodology

5.1. Introduction

This chapter describes the research methodology that underpins the study. First, the chapter explores the research's philosophical assumption, interpretivism as a research paradigm for this research (section 5.2). Then, it explores the research design, which ultimately focuses on achieving this research's overall goal (5.3). It then explains the rationale behind choosing a qualitative research approach for this study. Additionally, it describes how different disciplines and studies have determined the best methods for conducting qualitative research approaches. This chapter examines the educational ethnography research methodology used to obtain, collect, comprehend, analyse, and interpret the data and seek the answer to this study's research questions. Following that, it examines sample sizes and sampling techniques (5.4). After that, it examines the various data collection tools (5.5), including participant observation, informal conversation, field notes, and document review. The chapter also explains procedure for securely preserving the data. Then, this chapter thoroughly explains the phases of qualitative data analysis (5.6). Section 5.7 considers the researcher's positionality before aspects of trustworthiness, credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability are discussed in Section 5.8. Section 5.9 considers access to the research site, informed consent, privacy, confidentiality and anonymity following ethical guidelines. Finally, this chapter concludes with a summary of the chapter.

5.2 Philosophical Assumptions

Research philosophy guides conducting, analysing, and interpreting research using theoretical ideas and beliefs. Creswell and Creswell (2023) described a worldview as a fundamental set of beliefs that guide actions. They discussed this idea and highlighted that while they employ the term worldview, other researchers have used different terms to describe the same concept, such as paradigms (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005; Mertens, 2010), epistemologies and ontologies (Crotty, 1998), or generally conceived research approaches (Neuman, 2009).

A paradigm is a set of theoretical ideas, beliefs, or philosophical assumptions researchers use to guide their research (Creswell, 2009). The philosophical assumption is associated with research philosophy and underpins the researcher's design (Creswell, 2013). Philosophical assumptions help researchers generate research questions and manage their search for answers. The term research paradigm has been coined to describe the guiding ideology that leads the

research (Lincoln, Lynham, & Guba, 2011). Thus, a research paradigm is a set of assumptions and ideas we bring to our studies (Creswell, 2013). This is supported by four basic concepts that are compressed into interpretative frameworks: ontological assumption, epistemological assumption, axiological assumption, and methodological assumption (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Denzin and Lincoln, 2005).

Ontology concerns the nature of reality and existence. It explores questions such as: What is real? What exists? What is the nature of social phenomena? (Crotty, 1998; Scotland, 2012). Ontological assumptions acknowledge that reality can be objective and singular, or socially constructed and multiple (Guba & Lincoln, 1994). In qualitative research, ontology often aligns with a relativist perspective, recognising that multiple realities exist and are shaped by individual and cultural experiences. For example, in educational leadership research, different participants may experience leadership differently, and all such perspectives are considered valid aspects of reality.

Epistemology refers to the theory of knowledge, examining how we acquire and validate knowledge (Crotty, 1998). It examines the relationship between the researcher and reality, guiding how knowledge is acquired and interpreted (Scotland, 2012). In qualitative studies, researchers typically adopt a constructivist or interpretivist epistemology, where knowledge is co-created through close engagement with participants (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Spending extended time with participants enables researchers to gain a deeper understanding of their lived experiences, values, and perspectives. This engagement ensures that knowledge is contextually situated, interpreted, and reflective of participants' realities rather than imposed from an external viewpoint. Ethnographic methods, for example, exemplify this approach because they involve prolonged observation and interaction in participants' natural environments (Hammersley & Atkinson, 2019). Epistemology, therefore, not only explains how knowledge is gained but also how the researcher positions themselves relative to the phenomena being studied.

Axiology addresses the role of values and ethics in the research process. It examines what the researcher considers significant, worthy of investigation, and how values influence the choice of topic, methods, and interpretation of findings (Killam, 2013; Edelheim et al., 2022). According to Creswell and Poth (2016), axiology focuses on the underlying values that shape

research practices, such as engagement with participants, the credibility of data, and the audiences to whom the findings are presented. It also raises questions like: Whose perspectives are prioritised? How are ethical responsibilities addressed? What values guide the dissemination of results? (Guba & Lincoln, 1994). In qualitative research, acknowledging axiological assumptions highlights the researcher's reflexivity, recognising how personal beliefs, cultural background, and positionality shape the research process and outcomes (Berger, 2015). By making these values explicit, the researcher ensures transparency, ethical integrity, and a deeper understanding of the meaning underpinning the inquiry.

Methodological assumptions involve the researcher deciding upon the framing and conduct of the research. Research should be conducted through a transparent and systematic methodological approach to generate reliable findings. Qualitative research explores individuals' experiences and aids researchers in understanding what is meaningful to these individuals (Silverman, 2021). In qualitative research, researchers look for meanings and insights in a specific scenario (Strauss and Corbin, 1990; Levitt et al., 2017). Such research seeks understanding people's perspectives on different situations-(Gentles et al., 2015). The quantitative approach, in contrast, operates with numerical data and generates generalisable findings from large sample sizes (Flick, 2020). Therefore, this method used for hypothesis testing, prediction, and establishing causal relationships through objective numerical data analysis restricts the depth of understanding regarding the meanings that designed the participants' realities in this study (Dehalwar and Sharma, 2024).

This study adopted a qualitative research approach utilising an ethnographic methodology (educational ethnography). It enabled the researcher to offer rich, detailed insights into the school headteachers' leadership of school improvement. This model is seen as effective in natural settings. It enables researchers to gain detailed insights through deep engagement in real-life involvements (Creswell and Poth, 2016). Ethnography was chosen as my research seeks to investigate headteachers' leadership practices in Bangladeshi government primary schools, focusing on three different schools and involving headteachers and stakeholders in their natural environment. Ethnography is particularly well-suited for this study because it integrates prolonged immersion, participant observation, informal conversations, and document reviews. This approach generates a detailed and comprehensive description of school leaders' leadership practices aimed at school improvement. Silverman (2021) emphasises that

the key distinction between ethnography and other research methodologies is that the ethnographer is more active in interpreting activity within the setting through watching, observing, looking at, and scrutinising. Furthermore, the author asserts that ethnography is not merely a tool for data collection; unlike other methodologies, it values “a particular moment in the history of society and thus embodies certain of its cultural features” (p.109). Alternative approaches, such as case studies and phenomenology, were examined for this research, but ultimately appeared less aligned with the study’s objectives. A case study generally emphasises an in-depth examination of one or a few specific instances, rather than providing insights into the broader culture of a group and the social contexts around the issues being explored (Luthfiandana et al., 2024). On the other hand, phenomenology focuses on deeply understanding individuals' subjective experiences and examines their life experiences, without typically prioritising cultural description and contextual awareness. Consequently, ethnography provides the most comprehensive framework for capturing and illustrating social realities, making it ideal for addressing my research questions.

Therefore, research paradigms are defined through the assumptions made about the nature of knowledge (epistemology), the nature of reality (ontology) and the role of values (axiology) (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017), which inform methodological choices (Creswell, 2013). My ontological stance in this study is constructivism, which is frequently coupled with interpretivism (Creswell and Creswell, 2023). As noted by Creswell and Poth (2016), individuals with this worldview strive to understand and interpret their surrounding environment. Furthermore, Creswell and Creswell (2023) highlight that researchers embracing constructivist perspectives focus on the subjective meanings of participants’ thoughts and experiences. Given that the research is grounded in participants’ perceptions of their immersion in the situation, the researcher prefers open-ended data collection techniques, enabling participants to share their interpretations and derive meaning from their experiences.

Interpretive positions influence who is investigated, what kinds of questions and issues are looked at, how data is collected, analysed, written, and evaluated (Creswell and Poth, 2016). The main objective of the interpretivist paradigm is to understand the subjective nature of human experience (Guba and Lincoln, 1989). A key assertion of the interpretivist approach is that reality is socially constructed; it has also been referred to as the constructivist paradigm (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). The research questions in this study, rooted in constructivist

ontology and interpretivist epistemology, acknowledge that knowledge is multifaceted and constructed, and that understanding reality, for example, how headteachers' leadership of school improvement activities is viewed and understood, is primarily subjective or interpretive. Thus, the study relies on observations and informal conversations as data collection tools, allowing one interpretation of headteachers' lived experiences, shaped by their daily interactions with stakeholders.

5.3 Research Design

Research design can be described as the way to achieve the research goals. Creswell and Creswell (2023) explain that research designs encompass different types of investigations that guide qualitative, quantitative, as well as mixed methods approaches in conducting studies. It is an appropriate framework for systematic and structured research by choosing suitable research methods and data collection techniques (Sileyew, 2019). A research design is a roadmap for gathering and analysing evidence from various fields, enabling the researcher to address any question. It also influences nearly every element of the research process, ranging from the specific details of data collection to the choice of data analysis methods. (Flick, 2014).

Vogt, Gardner, and Haeffele (2012) state that the suitable research design for a study is determined by its topic, research problems, questions, as well as the ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological assumptions, along with the research goals. The authors also explain that research design is fundamental as all the research elements ultimately emerge from the design choice, and the reason for this choice is strongly connected to the researcher's topic, research questions, and theory. This study employed a qualitative research approach, utilising an ethnographic methodology (educational ethnography) to gather data in a natural setting over an extended period (Creswell and Creswell, 2023). The data collection tools included observations and informal conversations with headteachers and key stakeholders, such as teachers, government officials, parents, and managing committee members.

5.3.1 Educational Ethnography: Research Methodology

This research utilised educational ethnography as its methodology (Hammersley, 2018), gathering naturalistic data (Erlandson et al., 1993) through participants observations and informal discussions. According to Hammersley and Atkinson, ethnography:

In its most characteristic form, involves the ethnographer participating, in people's daily lives for an extended period of time, watching what happens, listening to what is said, asking questions - in fact, collecting whatever data are available to throw light on the issues that are the focus of the research. (Hammersley and Atkinson, 1995, p.1)

Here, the authors explain that in ethnography, researchers typically immerse themselves, either openly or secretly, in individuals' daily lives over an extended timeframe. They observe all the events, listen to conversations, and collect insights that are relevant of the research. Additionally, they gather documents and relevant data to illuminate the key issues arising during their inquiry. Flick (2014) emphasises that ethnography is a key methodology in qualitative research across various disciplines, facilitating the creation of detailed field notes. The author notes that the essence of ethnography lies in documenting the field. In ethnography, the researcher observes and interacts with the target participants to get helpful information for the study daily (Green, Dixon, and Zaharlick, 2005; Hammersley and Atkinson, 2019; Sharma and Sarkar, 2019).

According to Reeves et al. (2013), the primary goal of the ethnographic research methodology is to ensure accurate, detailed, and comprehensive insights into people's views and behaviours in real natural settings through ethnographic data collection tools. Hammersley (2018) provides a list of the characteristics of ethnography, highlighting: staying long-term at the research site; accessing natural settings; focusing on the researcher's engagement with participant observation; collecting documentation from the research site; and focusing on the participant experience holistically.

Ethnographers have to record the culture, viewpoints, and behaviours of those present in these contexts. Reeves et al. (2013) identify several advantages of ethnography. For instance, the ethnographic research methodology enables ethnographers to collect information through participant observations, involving close interaction and participation with the society they are studying. Additionally, this methodology enables ethnographers to include detail in their field notes. Typically, informal or conversational interviews allow ethnographers to discuss and explore issues, or inquire about events in a naturalistic way while they are conducting their observations. This kind of interview technique can help elicit incredibly candid accounts from people due to its "casual" nature. Hammersley (2018) emphasises that ethnography is often not

confined to research design, data collection, and analysis but also encompasses methodological, ontological, epistemological and ethical assumptions.

Educational ethnography refers to a particular methodology of conducting research in educational contexts. While ethnography is commonly linked with anthropology (Wall, 2015), it can also be used in other social sciences. It is one of the most comprehensive research methodologies available because the researcher visits a research location for an extended period, or over many extended visits, and observes what individuals do and what they claim they do. Thus, an ethnographer can more detailed insights into the experiences of people, and the organisation and the larger context in which they work than they might have by simply interviewing participants.

This study investigates headteachers' leadership of school improvement. The following are the reasons why I chose ethnography as a research approach for my project: First, ethnographers are always mindful of conducting research in a realistic context (Hammersley, 2018). Second, the data collection approach in ethnography is holistic, inductive, and dialogic (Sangasubana, 2011; Tracy, 2019). Third, my extensive experience with school leadership enabled me to collect data both as an observer and as a participant.

Every research methodology has its limitations, and ethnography is no exception (Adhikari, 2023). Creswell (2016) highlights several challenges in implementing educational ethnography. Data collection is time-consuming, requiring researchers to spend considerable time in the field. Furthermore, many ethnographies are crafted in a literary, narrative style that can restrict readership. This represents one of the many challenges ethnographers encounter when engaging with a new cultural group or system. Researchers must remain mindful of the specific requirements of their studies and their consequences for the people and places they examine. According to Adhikari (2023), ethnographers often need to visit multiple locations, which can be difficult for researchers with restricted resources. Moreover, generalising findings across varied contexts can be difficult with a qualitative approach. Each educational setting is unique, which means the results of an ethnographic study might not apply elsewhere, although readers may find aspects of the research transferable to similar settings. Additionally, ethnographic research poses a risk of bias. Ethnographers, being human, can have biases stemming from their own experiences and beliefs that may affect their findings. Another

limitation of ethnography in educational research is the difficulty of accessing participants. In many academic settings, especially those not welcoming to outsiders, gaining participant access can be challenging. Researchers might have to dedicate considerable time to cultivating relationships with gatekeepers to gain access to the study participants.

In this situation, I have extensive experience with school headship, which assisted me in gaining access to the study's research sites and being perceived (to some extent) as an insider. This research focuses on Bangladeshi primary school headteachers' leadership of school improvement initiatives. The data originates from school headteachers' and stakeholders' experiences, views, and values. The research methodology allows for interpretation of data, focusing on individuals' observed and talked about experiences (Levitt et al., 2017; Creswell and Poth, 2016; Corbin and Strauss, 2008). The study questions were designed to concentrate on the behaviours of the participants and understanding these from their point of view (King, Horrocks, and Brooks, 2018) and those of their key stakeholders.

Informal conversation is a component of participant observation that has applications beyond ethnography and can be used in everyday settings where talking is involved, often producing more naturalistic data and creating greater ease of communication (Swain and King, 2022). My role as an educational ethnographer in the research schools necessitated ongoing reflection on the research and sensitivity in observations and conversations to the feelings of those around me. I felt ethically obligated to the participants' kindness, acceptance, and trust in allowing me to conduct the research in their school. To join the school, one needs to build and maintain reciprocal relationships (Kornbluh, 2015), which I sought to do. This, in turn, can allow observations to inform 'rich descriptions' (McQueeney, and Lavelle, 2017).

5.4 Participants and Sampling Procedures

Sampling is an important stage in research. Researchers often wonder about the necessary sample size for qualitative studies (Dworkin, 2012). Since qualitative research does not rely on statistical generalisations, its practitioners might argue that sample size is not a critical concern (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2005). This study, being an educational ethnography, favoured depth of insights over breadth of participant numbers.

This study utilised purposive sampling to choose participants who fulfilled particular criteria related to my research objective. The selection first focused on headteachers with more than

10 years of school leadership experience, ensuring they hold practical knowledge and insights into school leadership. Second, only the headteachers who hold at least a master's degree were considered, as this educational quality was essential to reflect a certain level of academic preparation and understanding of school leadership. The study ensured that the sample included skilled, experienced, and knowledgeable participants by employing these selection criteria, those who could provide rich and informed perspectives that aligned with the research focus. Moser and Korstjens (2018) define purposive sampling as the process of choosing participants based on the researcher's judgment of who among them is most knowledgeable about the research subject. The participants in my research were chosen because they would best assist me in comprehending the phenomenon under investigation (Creswell, 2013) and offer credibility to the study (Patton, 2002).

For this study, three schools were selected for an 'ethnographic' investigation on how headteachers in Bangladeshi primary schools led school improvement initiatives. Extended observations of the leadership actions of these headteachers were made, alongside informal conversations with them. In addition, informal discussions were conducted with key stakeholders such as teachers, parents, managing committee members, PTA committee members, and community leaders connected to these headteachers' three primary schools. Data collected also included conversations with primary education officers.

Initially, 15 headteachers were contacted via email to assess their interest. Eight responded positively, and three headteachers from distinct primary schools in Dhaka City were chosen because of their differing school demographics and each headteacher's reported experience working with the school management committee. Each selected headteacher possessed a master's degree in education and over ten years of experience in their role. Additionally, they were recognised as seasoned educators, adept at guiding their colleagues and students.

At the time of data collection, School A (pseudonym) had 453 students and nine teachers. It was located outside Dhaka's urban area and served a population of low-income families. I chose this school because its headteacher had 20 years of experience in school leadership and has served as a leader in the central headteacher association. Furthermore, the headteacher reported that the School A managing committee members were highly involved in school development activities.

I chose School B because of a few unique features. For instance, School B was situated in a suburban area, and most students were referred to as ‘floating children’ because they were from the slums. The socioeconomic status of the students was extremely low. While the headteacher had 12 years of experience in school leadership and was significantly involved in school improvement activities, some teachers and management committee members were not. Thus, the school had a contrasting demographic to School A. School B had 520 students and nine teachers at the time of data collection.

The headteacher of School C had 15 years of experience in school leadership. I chose School C because it was close to the DPE. As a result, education officers and higher authorities closely monitored this school. The headteacher reported that the management committee at School C was highly involved, and the teaching staff was supportive. School C had 20 teachers and 918 students at the time of data collection.

In July 2022, I visited the research sites to familiarise myself with the three schools and engage with stakeholders, particularly the SMC and PTA members. Data collection took place over five months at the research site and was divided into two phases. The first phase commenced on August 8, 2022, and continued for three weeks, while the second phase extended from January 1 to April 10, 2023.

In the first phase of data collection, I examined the school’s observation books and records from the SMC, PTA, and teachers’ meetings. I also gathered preliminary data on school improvement through informal conversations with headteachers, teachers, and parents. Additionally, I engaged with the Facebook pages of the three schools to gain insights into the programmes they shared on social media. During the initial meetings with the education officers and the headteachers, they suggested that starting the second phase of data collection at the beginning of the academic year would yield more comprehensive insights. Considering that the academic session in Bangladesh begins in January, the second phase of data collection, from January to April, was threefold: 1. Participant observation (three schools), 2. Informal conversations with the headteacher, local stakeholders, and education officers; and 3. Document review.

A total of 36 participants engaged in participant observation and informal discussions. Table 10 provides the biographical information of the participants. The participants selected pseudonyms to maintain their anonymity.

Table 11. Research participants

Schools	Participant	Position	Gender
School A	Headteacher A	Headteacher	Male
	Headteacher 1	Visiting Headteacher	Male
	Headteacher 2	Visiting Headteacher	Male
	Headteacher 3	Visiting Headteacher	Male
	Headteacher 4	Visiting Headteacher	Male
	UEO A	Upazila Education Officer	Female
	SMC Chairman A	SMC Chairman	Male
	Ms N	Teacher Representative (TR)	Female
	Ms F	Teacher	Female
	Ms K	Teacher	Female
	Ms P	Senior teacher	Female
	Mr H	Senior teacher	Male
	Ms Ru	Teacher	Female
	Poly	Student	Female
	Raza	Student	Male
Maria	Student	Female	
School B	Headteacher B	Headteacher	Female
	Ms Z	Thana Education Officer (TEO)	Female
	Mr Rh	ATEO	Male
	SMC Chairman B	SMC Chairman	Male
	Ms R	Teacher Representative (TR)	Female
	Ms T	Teacher	Female
	Ms MJ	Teacher	Female
	Ms Q	Teacher	Female
	Mr K	Teacher	Male
	Ms M	Teacher	Female

School C	Headteacher C	Headteacher	Female
	Ms Z	Thana Education Officer (TEO)	Female
	Ms B	Former TEO	Female
	Mr T	Assistant District Primary Education Officer (ADPEO)	Male
	SMC Chairman C	SMC Chairman	Male
	Ms L	Teacher Representative (TR)	Female
	Ms Lily	SMC vice chairman	Female
	Ms Ruby	Senior Teacher	Female
	Mr X	Community leader	Male
	Ms Farida	PTA Chairman	Female

5.5 Data Collection Tools and Techniques

Tracy (2019) notes that ethnographers use research methods such as participant observation and informal interviews to study people and social organisations for data collection. Participant observation is critical to ethnographic research, particularly in educational ethnography. Participant observation techniques have been used to collect data for a long time and are essential for ethnographic research (Flick, 2020). 'Observation,' according to Marshall and Rossman (1989), is a methodical analysis of events, actions, and artefacts in a specific social situation. It is also a process of individuals coming to better understand day-to-day normal activities through engagement or involvement (Schensul, Schensul and LeComple, 1999). To explore the research questions, I used participant observation, informal conversations, researcher field notes, and document review as data collection tools.

5.5.1 Participant Observation

Silverman (2021) defines ethnography as a method rooted in participant observation. Ethnographers engage in conversations, examine documents, interact with individuals, listen attentively, and ask questions during data collection. However, what primarily sets ethnography apart from other methodologies is its emphasis on the active cognitive processes of observing, looking at, seeing, watching, and scrutinising (ibid). Participant observation is a widely used ethnographic data collection method that involves observing and engaging with a group or individuals over a period (Moser and Korstjens, 2018).

Musante and DeWalt (2010) describe participant observation as a technique in which the ethnographer observes the daily activities, communications, and various cultural events of the participants. The ethnographer attempts to observe both explicit and implicit aspects of the participant's everyday experiences (Spradley, 2016). This data collection tool is accepted mainly among ethnographers as it elicits data from participants in a naturalistic context (Hammersley, 2018).

For this research, observing headteachers' leadership conduct was central. As a result, I observed the school headteachers' activities, behaviours, and actions with their colleagues, students, parents, stakeholders, management committee members, and community members while attending the school programmes, teachers' weekly meetings, parents-teachers association meetings, school management committee meeting and the headteachers' and Thana education officer monthly meeting. I was particularly interested in Bangladeshi primary school headteachers' leadership when seeking to lead school improvement initiatives. As a result, I found the participant observation method to be an effective data collection tool for my research, enabling me to observe how school headteachers' leadership skills interact with others to lead school improvement initiatives. Flick (2020) highlights that participant observation can reduce the gap between the researcher and the observed environment. This approach enabled me to gather data from three diverse natural settings, specifically the leadership practices of three different primary school headteachers, allowing me to obtain more robust insights related to my research questions.

During my observations at the research sites, I refrained from taking notes in front of the participants. Instead, I recorded some of my observations privately to avoid data loss. As Hammersley (2018) reminds, natural settings are effective for collecting actual and accurate data, and I wanted to minimise my impact on this. As Mercader, Weber, and Durif-Varembont (2015) observe, some participants may greet ethnographers with open arms as soon as they enter the field. While one ethnographer may be greeted warmly, another may face various challenges from participants, or the organisation's head or stakeholders may expect or hope that the study findings will aid them in identifying solutions to institutional difficulties. For my research, I encountered this issue while observing School B. I was warmly welcomed by the school's Head Teacher (HT) and other teachers. However, on the second day, I noted that the HT consistently tried to mention how unmotivated her one female teacher was. Similarly, that

female teacher continuously tried to convince me that the HT was in error. So, on day three, I reminded them that I was not there to offer any solutions but rather to observe how the HT used her leadership in support of school improvement. It was tricky because I knew that if I tried to talk to that teacher about her issues, the HT might become upset. My task was to *observe* that naturalistic setting. So, I kept the field notes to gain a holistic view through my observations (Hammersley, 2018).

Field Notes

Field notes are important data collection tools ethnographers use while observing or interviewing people. Writing field notes can capture observed phenomena, emotions, reactions, and the researcher's positionality (Pacheco-Vega, 2019). This process produces data for analysis, improving the researcher's understanding (Hammersley and Atkinson, 2019). It also involves reflecting on what and whom we include or exclude in our fieldwork and analysis. According to Creswell (2013), field notes provide detailed data and a rich context for subsequent analysis. The role of field notes becomes significant for the ethnographer, as they help protect contextual information (Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2018).

No strict guidelines exist for writing ethnographic field notes, and most ethnographers create notes during (or shortly after) their observations (Eriksson, Henttonen, and Meriläinen, 2012). This is primarily because ethnographers cannot recall all the data without taking notes.

According to Phillippi and Lauderdale (2018), there is no set way to record observations in field notes because the ethnographer is primarily concerned with collecting significant data for analysis while protecting participant confidentiality. However, the authors emphasise that field notes can be written in various formats, including visual sketches and brief or more detailed textual notes.

I used field notes for my research to protect my data from being lost. I made only brief notes on site to ensure I did not further disrupt the natural setting. I did not attempt to record participant voices or make notes in their close presence. However, I often stepped outside and recorded my voice to avoid missing significant information. I also made brief notes in my notebook during my lunch break. However, when I returned home and sat down at my desk to write the detailed information every day after data collection, these brief notes in the field notes

enabled me to recall significant actions and interactions that informed my more detailed notes (see Appendix E).

5.5.2 Informal Conversation

Informal conversation was another ethnographic tool utilised for data collection in this study. According to Turner and Hagstrom-Schmidt (2022), informal conversation is an ethnographic data-collecting method in which the ethnographer does not ask pre-specified questions but relies on informal interaction with the participants (often resulting from something observed) to engage in conversation. The ethnographer keeps all of his/her questions in mind and speaks methodically, which benefits both the researcher and the participants in flexible and natural settings. Swain and King (2022) studied how informal discussions in ethnographic research might help data production in naturalistic situations improve findings. The authors state that many ethnographers use informal conversation as a natural part of participant observation. They make the case that researchers can spend time in colleges and schools where they can observe classes and ask questions pertinent to their research. However, some issues cannot be understood through observation alone. Thus, ethnographers require conversations with teachers or those around them, frequently either before or after class. Informal discussions may occur in the classroom, staff room, canteen, or even the corridor; they are not official interviews and are not recorded. Their function is to collect background knowledge, to create a better understanding of something observed. Thus, informal conversation is very effective in developing trust, establishing rapport, and forming an empathetic set of interactions in which the researcher engages with the participant's position and strives to understand the issue. Such informal conversations allow for greater collaboration between the ethnographer and the participants, which typically results in more accurate data collection (Swain and Spire, 2020).

Participants often struggle to express their opinions clearly, yet many find informal discussions to be productive and beneficial for plunging into detailed information. As a result, informal interaction can produce richer and often more informative data. According to Swain and Spire (2020), a relaxed, informal conversation is the most helpful technique to make the research more natural. I used informal discussions in my study to get more specific information and guide the conversation toward my research questions.

5.5.3 Document review

Documents are a key resource in social research. Silverman (2019) suggests that documents should be systematically reviewed through screening, and coding to extract meaningful evidence. The author provides a fourfold categorisation (Table 11) to offer various ways of document allocation that the researcher has appropriately allocated.

Silverman (2019) noted that bureaucratic organisations, including schools, healthcare agencies, and government offices, often produce more comprehensive and structured textual data than that derived from field observations. Reeves et al. (2013) stated that documents such as legislation, media reports, graphic documentation, and photographs can offer valuable background information for the study, triangulating with the research's other methods and providing insight into how participants perceive themselves.

In this study, I collected information from multiple documents to support my informal conversations and field notes observed in three schools. The sources comprised legislation provided to schools by MoPME and DPE through Upazila/ Thana education office, teachers' home visit forms, school observation and meeting records for SMC, PTA, teachers, mother gatherings, official letters, and various school register books.

5.6 Data Analysis

Data analysis is an essential part of any research (Coffey, 2018). Qualitative data analysis organises, classifies, and interprets data to generate statements about the implicit and explicit patterns of meaning (Flick, 2014, p.370). Thus, qualitative research involves arranging large, unstructured amounts of data to uncover meaning through processes such as pattern recognition, coding, exploration, and description of themes, topics, and categories.

According to Jacques (2021), the analysis of educational ethnographic data is iterative. However, in analysing qualitative data, researchers may utilise a variety of processes or procedures to better comprehend the data and find emergent themes (Creswell, 2013). This viewpoint is supported by Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018), who assert that "there is no one single or correct way to analyse and present qualitative data; how one does it should abide by fitness for purpose" (p. 643). Coffey (2018) continues by saying that there is no right or wrong way to create or use codes when analysing ethnographic data. Codes should be identified, questioned, and updated in response to ongoing data analysis. The researcher should

use coding and categorisation as thinking tools. According to Grbich (2013), to analyse the ethnographic data, researchers need to describe the event's perspective, recognise the structural elements, including time, place, culture, and context and then interpret the event in the context of theory development.

According to Reeves et al. (2013), educational ethnographic data analysis has three components: description, analysis, and interpretation. The term description refers to the ability to describe data in detail and provide a complete picture of any phenomenon. Analysis connects all the data collected in the field and establishes relationships between data points. Interpretation helps create a comprehension of the data. Coffey (2018) supports that analysis involves both "thinking about" and "thinking with" the data. He emphasises that thematic analysis is a primary method of analysing ethnographic data. Data needs to be coded and categorised to find themes and patterns in and across the data sets. Data can be broken down into its parts and connections can be made between and within the data with the aid of codes or labels. Additionally, code-and-retrieve processes are useful for managing and organising ethnographic data as well as for examining connections between and within the data. The use of coding and categorisation to support thematic analysis and data management is common in ethnographic research.

Computer software can support the analysis of qualitative data. This can be used to explore the relationships between data as well as assist with data management, retrieval, and display. Reflexive use of software applications is recommended. Atlas.ti, and NVivo are two examples of modern software programmes for qualitative data analysis that have roots that go back to the first qualitative analysis software (Silver and Lewins, 2014). However, using computer technologies is not required to deal with ethnographic data (Coffey, 2018). It is, of course, possible to manually organise data files. Index cards, paper documents or files, colour coding, or various kinds of tagging may be used in this situation.

This study utilised manual coding, which, though time-consuming, was comfortable for me due to the straightforward access to reading and coding using paper and pen. The specifics behind selecting manual coding are detailed in Phase Two: Creating Initial Coding.

Phases of Qualitative Data Analysis

There are no universally established phases in the analysis of qualitative data. Various writers mentioned different phases for analysing qualitative data. For example, Schreier (2014) quoted

in Flick, 2014) described eight phases for qualitative content analysis. However, according to Creswell and Creswell (2023), seven processes are involved in data analysis. Furthermore, according to Bryman and Burgess (1994, referenced in Mezmir, 2020), six steps were followed while analysing qualitative data. Braun and Clarke (2012, 2013, 2014, 2020, as mentioned in Byrne, 2022) presented a six-phase process to aid analysis and assist researchers in identifying and attending to the relevant components of a thematic analysis. Kiger and Varpio (2020), assert that thematic analysis is a robust and suitable approach for understanding thoughts, experiences, or behaviours within a data set. Its implementation in various qualitative research methods aligns with ethnography, and other qualitative techniques that incorporate coding and themes during data analysis. Castleberry and Nolen (2018) highlight that qualitative research comprises various designs, including case studies, grounded theory, ethnography, narrative inquiry, and phenomenology, utilising open-ended data rather than solely numerical data.

Thematic analysis (TA) is a popular data analysis technique widely utilised across various qualitative designs and is the focus of this methodology review. For instance, qualitative school ethnography research conducted by Izumi et al. (2020) and Wan and Nasr (2021) uses thematic analysis to assess the data. Thus, the current study follows Braun and Clarke's (2021) six phases of thematic analysis. Thus, the six phases suggested by Braun and Clarke (2021) provided a systematic yet flexible framework for qualitative data analysis as described below:

Phase One: Getting Familiar with the Data

Familiarisation with the data is an essential stage. According to Byrne, (2022), familiarisation involves reading the entire dataset several times. In this regard, the author suggests, that manual data transcription can be quite beneficial to the researcher because it greatly allows deep immersion into the data. Immersion, as a feature of educational ethnography, this study allows me to become intimately familiar with the data. Furthermore, I was advised by the study directors to read the material again, go over the data again, and annotate the field notes with theory and research questions so that in-depth reflections would develop. I had the chance to read and reread throughout this process and become more acquainted with the relationship between the research question and the theory.

Initially, I always ensured that all data related to the research questions were collected. As mentioned previously; while closely observing participants and having informal discussions with them to collect data, I made notes in notebooks (filed notes). I recorded audio, which was

subsequently saved on OneDrive. I reviewed the audio recording multiple times before transcribing it into a Word document and checking that the written text was in line with the audio. It is important to transcribe data orthographically to ensure the quality and correctness of transcripts (Gibbs, 2018; Byrne, 2022; Braun and Clarke 2022). Therefore, the transcribing procedure of this study included a translation from Bengali into English text. I made an effort to transcribe the field notes as closely as feasible to the participants' genuine Bengali expressions to guarantee the accuracy of the transcripts and capture the relevant meanings of the original expressions, and language. Transcripts were verified by two of my colleagues who already have expertise in both Bangla and English.

Following the completion of each session's transcription (and, if applicable, translation), I carefully re-examined the field notes and listened to the audio recordings several times while reading the final transcripts to double-check their accuracy. The transcripts were stored on my password-protected computer after being anonymised using pseudonyms to maintain secrecy. As recommended by Creswell (2013), I then read the transcripts several times to have a broad understanding of my data. Even though reading and transcribing such large amounts of data manually was difficult and time-consuming, it was a necessary initial step that allowed me to interact with the material in-depth and note down certain initial ideas.

Phase Two: Creating Initial Coding

Codes serve as the essential building blocks which will later eventually become themes. Coding is undertaken to create succinct, brief descriptive labels for data points that may relate to the research questions (Byrne, 2022). After becoming familiar with the data, I began coding them. Codes should be concise yet provide sufficient content to stand alone and reveal the underlying similarities including constituent pieces of data on the research topic (Braun and Clarke 2022). Coding is frequently difficult for novice researchers; however, Gibbs (2018, p.57) refers to "intensive reading," which comprises closely and precisely reading a document to find out its purpose.

It should be noted that manual coding was used in this study. Although manual coding can be time-consuming, I felt at ease because it was simple to access reading and coding with paper and pen. The use of paper and pen was emphasised by Gibbs (2018, p. 56), who explained that the majority of the classic research from the previous century conducted qualitative analyses

without the aid of software or electronic aids. Thus, in the early stages of data analysis, the author discovered manual data analysis; the paper offers a variety of freedom, creativity, and convenient access to the data to investigate the concept.

I therefore printed all of the transcripts and, to type the codes below, I left a double space between each line. To make it simpler to identify Headteachers from the beginning of the fieldwork, anonymous identities were chosen. I began reading each transcript using a set of highlighters and coloured pens, underlining any words, phrases, or sentences that I felt were important to comprehending the participants' stories. According to Byrne (2022), all data that could help answer the study topic or questions should be coded. After that, the data analysis was divided into two phases based on the research questions: the first involved utilising theory-based annotation, and the second involved using code for thematic analysis (for example, see Appendix D:2). This procedure was repeated for each transcript.

Phases Three and Four: Generating and Reviewing Themes

I began developing themes once all the information pertinent to the topic and research questions had been coded. Byrne (2022) stated that coded data is analysed to identify potential merges of different codes based on shared interpretations, thereby forming themes or sub-themes. According to Braun and Clarke (2019), the codes and data items must convey a relevant message that helps to answer the study questions. Consequently, a theme reflects an essential aspect of the data pertinent to the research question, offering a structured response or interpretation within the dataset. While themes must be distinctive and may occasionally conflict, they should collectively contribute to a clear and unified representation of the dataset (Byrne, 2022). As I looked for links connecting the original codes, I grouped related codes into units with a shared concept or idea.

To review prospective themes, the researcher must perform a repeated analysis of possible themes of the entire dataset and the coded data items (Byrne, 2022). Specific potential themes may not be compelling interpretations of the data at this point or may not provide information that addresses the study question or questions. So, I proceeded to review the themes from the previous phase, making sure that the coded extracts aligned with the themes to which they were assigned. This step also included re-examining the connections between the codes and themes found to confirm they accurately reflected the data's meaning and, if necessary, combining

some of the themes. Due to these adjustments, some topics may be combined or divided into other themes.

Phase 5: Identifying and naming the theme

Naming themes is crucial as it gives the reader an initial clue about the documented data (Byrne, 2022). Braun and Clarke (2021) promote innovation and employ captivating names that instantly engage the reader's interest while conveying an essential thematic element. Names should be brief, informative, and distinctive; perhaps the most common tendency is to come up with names that describe the theme. In this phase, I provided a thorough examination of the theme structure. Every theme and sub-theme were discussed in light of the dataset and the research questions. I developed the theme that best reflected each theme's essence and, most importantly, included participant headteachers' voices that focused on the research topic and questions. This is because all themes should come together to create a straightforward narrative that aligns with the dataset's contents and is informative for the research question(s) (Byrne, 2022).

Phase Six: Creating the Report

The concluding phase involved coherently and entertainingly articulating and interpreting the findings based on the selected themes and categories. The following chapter will review the themes with detailed excerpts from the study questions and theory.

5.7 Researcher's Positionality

Positionality is essential for any ethnographic study because it challenges the researcher to recognise their privileges, power, and biases while denouncing the power frameworks encompassing those they investigate (Powell, 2022). In an educational ethnography study, researchers' positionalities depend on their identities, backgrounds, roles, and experiences that make them familiar with the research site and may influence the study process, such as data collection and interpretation (McGinity, 2012; Gelir, 2021). Powell (2022) states that understanding every potential case allows researchers to assess their biases, ensuring their findings are more deliberate and well-founded. Thus, by fully reflecting on subjectivity, positionality, privilege, and power relations, researchers become more aware of the environments and the people they investigate (Powell, 2022).

In my situation, my teaching profession mirrors my research topic and interest, which has led me to advance my career by completing an MSc in educational leadership and pursuing a PhD in the same field. As an educational ethnography researcher, it is evident that immersion in the data and setting is essential (Parker-Jenkins, 2018), and my professional identity assisted me greatly in immersing myself in my study contexts. When interacting with my study participants, I was always mindful of my social and professional status since I understood that their responses to this were critical to gathering reliable data. Gelir (2021) asserts that the researcher's personal and professional backgrounds gave them varying degrees of authority, positioning them as both insiders and outsiders.

In addition, researcher positionality is frequently situated through an "insider-outsider" duality that, in certain situations, can be possibly deterministic while providing a simplified explanation of fieldwork activities (Czerniawski, 2023). One ongoing argument about whether researchers are "insiders" or "outsiders," according to Reyes (2020), emphasises how both positions can have a few "insider moments" with participants and/or be "outsider moments" because of their varied statuses. Additionally, the author noted that social science researchers have a long-standing tradition of highlighting how certain characteristics can help better understand the potential advantages and disadvantages of their research methods and results. In the current ethnographic study, my position as a researcher was situated between insider and outsider.

According to Gelir (2021), an insider has an intuitive understanding of the field's socio-historical condition, which allows the researcher to more effectively analyse sociocultural clues related to the community's values and belief systems. In this study, I am an 'insider' researcher', working in the same field as my research participants. I have 12 years of experience enhance the researcher's understanding of their study and the phenomena being examined (Saidin, 2016). As an insider researcher, I leveraged all the advantages while collecting data in the research field. My role as an insider researcher allowed me to establish a strong relationship with my participants. All my research participants knew my profession and social identity, encouraging them to share their leadership activities. They freely expressed their opinions and confidently discussed issues, leading to the collection of detailed and valuable data.

While my insider position offered several advantages, it also presented some challenges that could have impacted data collection and analysis. For example, during informal conversations with the participant headteachers, they sometimes asked me to clarify my experiences, as they thought I was already familiar with the particular research context and their leadership experiences. I needed to adapt to the situation and set up informal talks to collect additional information. To respond, I changed my approach by setting up more informal discussions. These talks helped me understand their views in greater detail and collect deeper information. Gelir (2021) warn researchers about the dangers of becoming overly familiar with the research site, as this can make it challenging to maintain critical distance and achieve the research objectives. Additionally, insiders may overlook specific issues in their research, viewing them as less significant than outsiders (Saidin, 2016). Their awareness and sensitivity to specific information or issues might not match that of outsider researchers.

However, I also viewed myself as an outsider. Although I am acquainted with Bangladeshi school leadership, the research site presented an entirely unfamiliar socio-economic context. Diverse leadership styles and observations of unique experiences sometimes hindered my comprehension of the headteachers' actions and experiences in their workplaces. Moreover, my experience as an international student at a UK university has shaped my researcher's perspective more than my former profession. This was partly due to my adaptation to the UK research culture, which influenced my self-identification as an outsider in the research field. These feelings were heightened when I requested participants to sign the consent forms and follow the instructions.

In an effort to somewhat mitigate my subjective influence on the study's conduct and outcomes, I needed to balance my roles as an insider and an outsider. As outlined in the following section, additional measures were implemented to lessen the potential impact of my subjectivity and enhance the study's trustworthiness.

5.8 Trustworthiness of the Research

Validity and reliability are often aligned to quantitative research (Armour and Williams, 2022), whereas trustworthiness is frequently used to guide qualitative research approaches, with transparency being the most significant feature (Adler, 2022). Lincoln and Guba (1985) recommended evaluating qualitative research based on trustworthiness metrics rather than conventional scientific criteria such as validity and reliability. These authors present five

strategies to enhance research credibility: prolonged engagement, ongoing observation, triangulation of data, peer debriefing, ensuring appropriate interpretations, and member checking. Cope (2013) notes that quantitative research is defined by its validity and rigour, whereas qualitative research is characterised by its authenticity and credibility (Creswell and Creswell, 2023).

The trustworthiness of this study is reflected in the field notes, data gathering, data analysis, data interpretation, and presentation of study findings. This research utilised Creswell and Creswell's (2023) eight strategies to increase the credibility of qualitative research. These include prolonged engagement, triangulation, member checking, thick and rich description to transfer the findings, clarifying the bias, providing contradictory evidence, peer debriefing, and external auditing.

5.8.1. Techniques for Establishing Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness is considered the key strategy for enhancing the quality and firmness of qualitative research.

1. *Spending a prolonged period in the research site*

The researcher must spend sufficient time on the research site to establish credibility. This enables the researcher to identify the cultural context and social settings and build trustworthy relationships with the participants to collect in-depth and rich data (Alexander, 2019). Lincoln and Guba (1985) state that while prolonged engagement offers broad insights, continual observation contributes to in-depth understanding. Creswell and Creswell (2023) state that spending prolonged periods in the research site helps the researcher gain more experience with the study participants in their natural surroundings, which in turn helps produce more valid and accurate findings. This also allows the researchers to gain a comprehensive grasp of the study phenomenon and collect more detailed information from the research location and the participants, thereby contributing credibility to the narrative interpretation (Creswell and Creswell, 2023).

For the present study, I spent nearly five months in persistent participant observation in three primary schools at the research site. Between the first and second faces of the data collection period, I connected with the school's headteachers and teachers on social media for four months. While collecting data on the research site, I spent most of my time with the

participants. Even after school, I often joined them at some events organised by the Thana Education Office. I built a trusting relationship with my participants, which eventually helped me get in-depth, rich information from the field. During this time, I dedicated an extended period to the research site, enhancing my comprehension of the research phenomenon by acknowledging insights from participants and the site itself, thereby strengthening the credibility of my study.

2. *Triangulation*

Triangulation is a process that makes the research more credible. Data triangulation involves using various data sources to validate the findings, such as time, space, and person triangulation (Flick, 2020).

This current study used different times of the year to collect data from three schools. In the first phase, it collected data in the middle of the academic Year (August), and then in the second phase, it collected data from January to April (in the Bangladeshi school setting, the academic year starts in January). Collecting data at the start of the academic year and in the middle of the session can help distinguish between temporary issues like attendance verification, dropout rate, and pupils' reading difficulties, and understand how various roles of headteachers' leadership play in addressing these issues. Thus, using different times for data collection (Alexander, 2019) will likely increase the research quality and ensure internal validity.

Space triangulation entails gathering data on the same phenomenon from multiple locations to assess cross-site consistency (Alexander, 2019). Data were collected from three distinct primary schools as research sites to enhance the research quality. In addition, this study collected data from three schools' headteachers and key stakeholders, including teachers, members of SMC, PTA, parents, community people, and education officers. These offer 'Person Triangulation' to collect data involving different levels of people to validate data through manifold perceptions of the phenomenon (Alexander, 2019).

Methodological triangulation involves employing multiple methods, typically three, to enhance accuracy and ensure validity (Patton, 2002). Creswell and Creswell (2023) state that data triangulation involves collecting data from different sources, including observations, interviews, and document analysis. The current study used three ethnographic data collection

tools, such as participant observation, informal conversation, and document review, to collect data for this research, which enhanced clarity and a comprehensive understanding of the study phenomenon.

3. *Member verification*

Member verification is a procedure in which research participants review interview transcripts and preliminary data interpretations for accuracy and credibility. Researchers offer participants feedback on emerging views and solicit their reactions (Alexander, 2019). As a researcher, I understand how crucial member verification is to prove the study's accuracy. I began this process by asking the participants' permission to fill out an informed consent form so they would be aware of and comprehend the study's goals and objectives. After witnessing the school event and engaging in informal conversations, I summarised observations to the key participants (headteachers) to confirm the data's accuracy and validity.

As a researcher, my role involved accurately representing the participants' realities. Each participant obtained a copy of the observation and informal conversation transcript, and I asked them to review it to ensure their comments were documented correctly. All participants confirmed that the transcriptions accurately reflected my observations at the research site. Additionally, two key participants consistently provided essential documents that enhanced my study data. Even after completing data collection, I remained connected with three key participants through Facebook Messenger. I shared the necessary data to clarify their responses and validate the accuracy of the information obtained from their schools. Use an external auditor to review the entire study.

4. *Using a detailed and thick explanation to convey the results*

Detailed and thick descriptions offer manifold perspectives about the themes, and the findings become more realistic, leading to the validity of the study findings (Creswell and Creswell, 2023). Alexander (2019) emphasised that adequate information should be presented clearly and richly to guarantee credibility.

I have included a comprehensive account of my ethnographic observation for this study. My findings are organised thematically, reflecting a thorough presentation of the data, as is typical for ethnographic field notes. Thus, rich and thick descriptions effectively convey this study's findings.

5. Clarify the bias that the researcher introduces to the study.

Researcher should be open about their backgrounds, such as their gender, history, culture and social status. According to Creswell and Creswell (2023), Self-reflection fosters an authentic narrative that strongly connects with readers. Reflexivity is fundamental to qualitative research, requiring researchers to articulate their identity and background, which may influence their findings. This approach ultimately improves the accuracy and impartiality of the research.

To produce credible findings, I explained my position as a female headteacher with 12 years of experience to the participants at the beginning of the research process. My professional background could shape how I interpreted the data and how participants might respond. For instance, some participants may have viewed me as a colleague, which could influence the openness of their responses. To reduce this potential bias, I used strategies such as building trust over time, ensuring voluntary participation, and keeping reflective notes throughout the research. Acknowledging my position and being transparent, I aimed to maintain fairness and strengthen the study's trustworthiness.

6. Present negative or conflicting information that contradicts the themes.

While doing research, themes come from the main idea of the collected data. Creswell and Creswell (2023) state that real life includes various common perspectives, but sometimes, some different or opposite information also exists. Addressing opposing information enhances the study's credibility.

My research establishes credibility by presenting and examining evidence related to a specific theme. Although most evidence supports this theme, I also incorporate information that contests the widely accepted perspective. By including a variety of viewpoints from participants, my study becomes more realistic and valid.

7. Peer Debriefing

Creswell and Creswell (2023) highlight that peer debriefing is significant for spotting blind spots. This involves regular meetings with those not engaged in the research but are informed about its hypotheses and findings. In this context study, throughout the data gathering and analysis process, I was connected with both of my supervisors to discuss my collected data and emerging research findings. At each stage of the process, I received thorough feedback to help

me identify any blind spots or ideas that needed clarification. I also presented my research findings to my assessor to obtain his detailed feedback. These interventions, emphasising peer debriefing, enhanced the trustworthiness of the study.

8. *Use an external auditor to review the entire study*

External auditing differs from peer debriefing because it requires an individual unfamiliar with the researcher or the study. This allows for an objective assessment either during the research process or after its completion (Creswell and Creswell, 2023). In my research, once I had finalised my data collection, I shared the transcription, field notes and findings with two of my colleagues who had already completed the PhD and started teaching in my university, the Education and Social Sciences school. Their role was as investigators because they checked the accuracy of the transcription, the relation between the data and research questions, and the various steps of data analysis, data presentation, interpretation and then discussion, which enhanced the trustworthiness of the ethnographic study. Furthermore, I had the opportunity to present part of the findings at the UWS PGR Teach Meet, UWS research seminar 2022-202, UWS Festival 2024, and European Conference on Educational Research (ECER) in 2024. These were venues where I shared my research with academics who were not familiar with my study, and at international conferences, I was not familiar with them, enabling me to explore various aspects and viewpoints. This proved especially beneficial since most feedback and inquiries during these events came from external perspectives.

5.9 Ethical compliance and procedure

Before initiating the fieldwork for this research, I achieved ethical approval from the Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland. The application included information regarding the research aim and objectives, data collection strategies, and participant selection processes. After receiving the ethical approval, an information and consent form for participants and an information sheet and observation instrument for observation participants were emailed to the participants (See Appendices A, B, and C). When they confirmed their involvement, I informed all study participants that their contribution was optional and that participants could take back their statements at any moment, even after data collection.

Then, I reassured all the study participants that I would not place them in any circumstance where they would be mistreated. Furthermore, recognising that confidentiality is a core element

of research ethics (Brooks, Maguire and Te Riele, 2014), I reminded them that I would maintain anonymity and strict confidentiality by eliminating all personal and professional details from my data collection archives. I also assured each participant that their information would remain confidential. Additionally, I informed all participants about the nature of my research. Lastly, I explained that the data collected would be stored in a password-protected folder on my personal computer's OneDrive and deleted after the study's submission.

5.9.1 Securing gatekeeper approval and ensuring access to the research location.

Gatekeeper approval in research refers to permission from an individual or organisation chief who regulates access to potential research participants in a research location. A gatekeeper typically includes a school principal, managing director, or administrator (Singh and Wassenaar, 2016). To ethically and legally conduct the study, researchers must obtain gatekeeper approval. The gatekeeper in the present research was the Director General (DG) of the Directorate of Primary Education (DPE) in Bangladesh. To secure this permission, I sent an application by email to the DG of DPE, mentioning the study's aims and objectives. It took around 3 weeks after overcoming the bureaucratic process. The Directorate of Primary Education has approved my application to collect data from any Government Primary Schools in the Dhaka district. I gathered research data from three schools through educational ethnographic fieldwork, observation, and informal conversations. In addition to guiding the study's aims and objectives, I provided each headteacher with a Gatekeeper approval letter (see Appendix C), a participant information sheet (Appendix A), and a headteacher's information sheet (Appendix B). The teachers at all three schools and relevant stakeholders welcomed my presence during the data collection for my research.

5.10 Conclusion

This study employed a qualitative research approach, as it allowed the researcher to provide compelling evidence of the challenges encountered by school headteachers in their institutions. The study aims to investigate how Bangladeshi school headteachers navigate contested leadership spaces. Researchers observed school heads at work in a natural environment to carry out this examination. Samples were chosen for the investigation's credibility and understanding. The researcher chose participants from three distinct schools to strengthen the research findings. Research methodology includes investigating human culture, making observations, having informal conversations, taking field notes, reviewing documents, and

summarising new findings (Creswell and Poth, 2016). Each approach and its implementation were outlined, including rigour and validity tests, transcription procedures, and transcription preparation for analysis. Observing people's perspectives in natural settings helps to acquire a true picture of them (Gentles et al., 2015), which is extremely useful for this research into school headteachers' leadership and efforts to improve the school.

Chapter 6: Headteachers' Role in Leading School Improvement

Initiatives

6.1 Introduction

This chapter aims to explore the role of primary headteachers in steering school improvement initiatives, in alignment with Research Question 1. To enhance clarity and comprehension, this study presents and discusses the findings thematically. Data were collected across the three schools through document reviews, observation of headteachers at work, and gathering of anecdotes through informal conversations with headteachers, teachers, parents, the SMC members, and government officials' data emerging from the three schools. The data revealed issues that help to explain the role of the headteacher when leading school improvement initiatives within which different understandings of 'school improvement' in the Bangladeshi school context emerged.

The chapter is structured into five key sub-themes, each reflecting various aspects of the headteacher's role in leading school improvement initiatives. The first sub-theme addresses the headteacher's role in ensuring and managing the quality of the learning environment. The second sub-theme explains the headteachers' role in securing funds and resources for school improvement. The third sub-theme highlights the role of the headteacher in ensuring a sustained focus on student attendance and academic success. The fourth sub-theme focuses on the role of headteachers in promoting active parental engagement in support of school improvement. The fifth sub-theme explores the role of the headteacher in ensuring teachers are well-prepared, trained and motivated for effective classroom practices.

Each sub-theme provides a detailed analysis supported by data and is referenced to the existing literature in this field. By synthesising these issues thematically, this chapter offers insights into the multifaceted roles of headteachers' and their contributions to school improvement.

6.2 Headteacher's Role in Ensuring a Quality Learning Environment

In this study, the role of the headteacher in monitoring the quality of the learning environment in schools came out strongly. Stakeholders in the three schools emphasised the role of headteachers in managing and monitoring the quality of the learning environment as an important facet of school improvement. When referring to the quality of the 'learning environment' stakeholders explained that the headteachers' role and responsibilities were to

ensure the quality of the school campus, including school gates, boundary walls, school fields, and gardens, as well as ensuring that classrooms were well-decorated, had adequate teaching aids, and had access to the multimedia classroom. In addition, stakeholders emphasised the importance of classrooms with electric fans, enough light and toilets for both females and males with sufficient clean drinking water.

Stakeholders in the study indicated that a high-quality learning environment included good infrastructure in modernised learning spaces, stressing that a visually appealing environment was necessary for children's educational development because it attracted parents to enrol their children in a school. Observing headteachers as they undertook their work, holding meetings with parental groups and speaking with teachers demonstrated their understanding of the importance of the headteacher's role in ensuring a quality learning environment.

In a meeting observed at the headteacher's office at school A on February 2, 2023, the headteacher, the chairman of the School Managing Committee (SMC), the Teacher Representative (TR), and two local leaders discussed their efforts to secure adequate funding for providing a high-quality learning environment:

In the headteacher's office, several people gathered for morning tea, where they also engaged in conversation about the school. The room was modestly furnished, with shelves filled with files, registers and other documents. As the conversation progressed, the headteacher explained that the school required funds to enhance the learning environment, gesturing towards a list of written documents pinned on the notice board nearby. There was a need to decorate classroom walls, purchase teaching aids, repair washrooms, and install water filters. Then the headteacher of School A slightly paused, briefly glancing at a report in front of him on the table before starting again. He noted that although they received a substantial amount from the SLIP fund, it was not sufficient to fulfil all school needs. He noted a need to explore community fundraising, working closely with the school managing committee.

The aforementioned observation emphasises the importance of the headteacher in ensuring and maintaining a high-quality learning environment to enhance student enrolment and attendance. In the observation noted above, the headteacher sought to broker funds for classroom decoration, renovations and installations. Due to insufficient SLIP funds, the headteacher had

to negotiate funding from the SMC. After identifying the common understanding of a 'quality learning environment' among stakeholders and headteachers in Bangladeshi primary schools, the ethnographic data highlighted the headteacher's role in overseeing school improvements related to this concept. In School A, the headteacher exercised his role by inviting the SMC chairman to join the conversation:

As he spoke, the Headteacher of school A glanced towards the SMC chairman; it seemed to invite him to join the conversation. The SMC chairman nodded in agreement and added that they needed to urgently focus on making the learning environment more attractive before the annual sports. He continued that it was a great responsibility for the SMC to successfully manage funds from the donors to ensure this. Both community leaders agreed with the statement of the headteachers and SMC chairman by showing a sense of shared responsibility and demonstrating community effort to improve the learning environment, which was important for school improvement.

The above data highlighted that the Headteacher of School A focused on improving the learning environment by implementing various strategies to manage funds, including enhancing stakeholders' shared responsibilities. He engaged the SMC chairman to understand the importance of an attractive learning environment in attracting pupils. The data revealed that headteachers and other stakeholders expressed their thoughts that the school's outlook and colourful classroom decorations increased students' attraction to attend the school and overall outcomes. It was observed that the headteacher always arrived at the school before the class started. He ensured that the school premises were clean and tidy, and the classrooms were attractively furnished so that classroom teaching and learning could begin effectively.

The research indicated that fostering a positive learning environment enhanced student attendance and classroom instruction, aligning with Yasmin, Rumi and Robert's (2020) study on public primary schools in Sylhet, Bangladesh. These authors note that improving schools with comfortable seating arrangements, enough classrooms, and playgrounds can support a positive learning environment. This research indicates that sufficient funding should be allocated for infrastructure development to guarantee high-quality education. However, the authors emphasised the importance of government education policy and the involvement of concerned parties (teachers and guardians) in fostering a child-friendly environment, rather

than addressing head teachers' roles in improving the school setting. In this study, the headteacher of School A demonstrated an instructional leadership style by focusing on improving the learning environment to enhance teaching and learning. His actions, such as ensuring classrooms were clean, well-decorated, and conducive to learning, reflected his commitment to creating conditions that support effective instruction. By engaging stakeholders like the SMC chairman and motivating staff to maintain a productive environment, the headteacher exemplified key aspects of instructional leadership, which emphasise setting clear educational goals, providing supportive learning conditions, and monitoring the teaching process (Hallinger, 2011).

Furthermore, School A featured a lovely garden, which was mentioned during an informal discussion about how gardening relates to school improvement.

The headteacher reflected that the school garden was an important aspect of the school's improvement. He added that last year, in July 2021, trees were planted in the schoolyard to beautify the school campus. The objective was to establish an inviting educational atmosphere for the students within the institution. During their break time, students tended to the garden, which helped them understand the value of tree planting. Some of his teachers participated in tree plantations as well as inspiring students to do the same. He was pleased to see one of his teachers often bring the students to the garden to teach them science concepts. High officials always encouraged them to plant trees on school grounds. In his opinion, it could serve to improve primary education by combining teaching and learning and improving children's physical and mental well-being.

The above conversation reflects the headteacher's efforts to improve his school in various ways, including encouraging learning science and environmental knowledge, promoting well-being for parents and students, and raising environmental awareness. It was observed that the headteacher was concerned about students' understanding the importance of planting trees. The headteacher of School A was closely involved in enhancing the school's learning environment in efforts to improve his school, resonant findings by Khan et al. (2020). These authors discovered that children preferred learning in visually appealing outdoor settings, such as gardens and playground equipment, since these settings allow children to interact with nature and keep them engaged in thinking, creating, and learning. Besides, they found that the teachers

also identified various affordances of natural materials for teaching science and other curriculum subjects, consistent with the current study's findings.

Similar viewpoints were also found in the field notes, where the headteacher of School B demonstrated her proactive role in creating a child-friendly learning environment by improving classroom practices and decorating the classrooms with various colourful pictures and paints. The headteacher felt that parents were more inclined to select a school that offers a quality learning environment. For this reason, she worked hard to make the classrooms, especially pre-primary classrooms, child-friendly despite the challenging infrastructure conditions at the school. This was also evident in her efforts to decorate the pre-primary classroom as observed on 10 January 2023:

The walls are adorned with colourful pictures related to the lessons, and various toys create an inviting atmosphere. Along with colourful toys, there are plastic slippers, dolls, horses, and elephants in the room. Lovely red carpets are available for seating. The young girls are wearing sky-blue frocks with white belts at the waist, while the boys are dressed in white shirts and blue pants. All the young students carried school bags featuring the UNICEF logo.

The above field notes reflect the Headteacher's role in providing a welcoming learning environment, something she considered paramount to school improvement. In School A, the headteacher focused on creating a child-friendly environment by providing many toys for pre-primary students. It was observed that she arranged comfortable seating for the students. Furthermore, she engaged UNICEF to provide materials for pre-primary children, including school bags and teaching aids. It was also observed that the attendance of pre-primary students was high due to special care by the headteacher.

The headteachers' reflections on their role in ensuring a high-quality learning environment align with the results of Salam's (2015) study in government and private elementary schools in Bangladesh, which discovered that a high-quality learning environment promotes effective teaching and learning and higher student achievement. This research investigated the quality and effectiveness of classroom teaching and learning in primary schools in Bangladesh, including factors like class size, learning atmosphere, physical facilities, and teaching aids.

However, there was no discussion of the headteacher's responsibility in ensuring a quality school environment.

During an informal conversation, the headteacher of School C expressed a similar sentiment about the relationship between the quality of the learning environment and pupil attendance. The headteacher emphasised the importance of improving the school environment as it is a critical factor in increasing student enrolment and attendance. She highlighted the collaboration of SMC members, parents, students and teachers to ensure a child-friendly learning environment in her schools. As a headteacher, she recognised her role in ensuring that all necessary classroom teaching equipment was available, including teaching aids and a healthy environment, such as clean toilets, safe drinking water, enough lighting, comfortable seating arrangements, and well-decorated classrooms with white marker boards. She demonstrated a glass door cabinet filled with various teaching aids and was delighted to showcase her collection. She explained that her teachers always use these teaching aids during classroom instructions. She mentioned that students, under the guidance of teachers, had prepared many teaching aids as part of their innovative activities. Additionally, she noted that she was able to buy the teaching aids with the funds from SLIP (School Level Improvement Plan) and contributions from local stakeholders. This reflects the characteristics of pedagogical leadership as described by Male and Palaiologou (2015). Here, the headteacher demonstrated a strong commitment to creating inclusive and caring learning environments that responded to the social and cultural context of their communities. By decorating classrooms with colourful materials, providing adequate teaching aids, and ensuring cleanliness, safety, and comfort, they shaped environments that supported children's emotional and academic development.

As in the other two schools, it was evident by observing the pre-primary and the other classrooms at School C that they were noticeably well-decorated. The Headteacher reinforced this view, noting that parents were delighted to enrol and continue to keep their children in such well-designed classrooms:

There were special features in the school C's pre-primary classrooms. Remarkably, 95% of the pupils were in attendance during the observation. The headteacher pointed out the brightly coloured paintings of different animals and birds that related to the lessons and explained how the visually appealing environment encouraged the young child to attend

school. In addition, there were toys, little rides, and students' paintings. The students are seated on colourful carpets (School C Fieldnotes, 12 January 2023).

The informal discussions and observations detailed how the head teacher effectively secured funding for the SLIP fund. She engaged local stakeholders to acquire all the necessary supplies for classroom decoration. Her practices align with the instructional leadership model, which emphasises headteachers' strategic actions in providing resources, setting goals, and supporting teaching practices to improve student outcomes (Hallinger & Murphy, 1985; Hallinger, 2011). By mobilising SLIP funds and community support, the headteacher demonstrated how instructional leaders create the enabling conditions necessary for effective teaching and learning. Additionally, her critical role in fostering a high-quality teaching and learning environment significantly improved the pupils' overall experience. These perspectives align with the findings of Alam et al. (2023), who evaluated the significance of physical facilities in Bangladeshi Upazila stage primary schools. This includes comfortable seating, decorated classrooms, multimedia resources, a library, a playground with equipment, and teaching aids. The authors found that improved physical facilities boost students' academic performance by increasing their attraction to and motivation for learning in the classroom.

This study indicates that headteachers across all three schools were highly attentive to their responsibilities in fostering a child-friendly educational atmosphere to enhance school quality. Stakeholders highlighted the essential part headteachers play in cultivating an attractive school setting, which can motivate parents to choose specific schools for their children. In an informal discussion with an assistant District Primary Education Officer (ADPEO), he noted that effective school improvement encompasses appealing infrastructure, well-equipped classrooms, flower gardens, clean restrooms, handwashing facilities and students wearing school uniforms. Wearing a school uniform helps students feel equal and part of the same school community, promotes discipline, and supports a positive and focused learning environment. He commented that such an environment allows teachers and students to feel secure and comfortable while striving to meet learning objectives. The headteacher's pivotal role entails engaging stakeholders to ensure all crucial elements are in place, making the school inviting and appealing.

The above statement from the education officer indicated that headteachers are responsible for ensuring an appealing school environment by effectively involving stakeholders. This is also

supported by the Thana Education Officer (TEO) responsible for Schools B and C. She shared a school visit form provided by the DPE, which indicates the school's name and the head teacher's name, as well as several criteria that need to be filled out by the education officer after observing the school. This document was found to exhibit the following features:

- Are the school premises, classrooms and teachers' rooms clean?
- Is the toilet clean?
- Is there safe drinking water?
- Are class activities conducted according to the weekly class routine?
- Is the classroom decorated with students' creative work?
- Are there educational-related pictures, country maps, and environmental paintings on the classroom walls?
- Do the students have school dress?
- Does the headteacher organise an assembly daily?

The TEO stated that during school visits, officers consistently highlighted the significance of a good learning environment, as evidenced in the visit form. This included assessing the cleanliness of the school grounds, classrooms, toilets, and decorations, particularly noting the classroom walls adorned with images from textbooks. Additionally, the document stipulated that the headteacher should coordinate these efforts with appropriate stakeholders. This oversight function also resonates with instructional leadership, where headteachers are expected to monitor classroom conditions and teaching practices to ensure alignment with national educational goals (Hallinger, 2011). Another document echoed this perspective, stating that it is the headteacher's responsibility to create a child-friendly atmosphere, for which they should be recognised. The Upazila Education Officer commended Headteacher A for the school's well-kept appearance, noting her feedback in the observation book:

All students are dressed in school uniform, classrooms are well decorated, and school premises are clean and tidy, thanks to the headteacher (Observation book at School A, November 20, 2022).

The study also highlighted that when headteachers provided an appealing and favourable learning environment, parents were more willing to enrol their children in their school. This also highlights the headteacher's role in meeting these responsibilities, which are

acknowledged by higher authorities. In an informal conversation, one of the SMC members at School A shared her opinion regarding the headteacher's role in improving the school's learning environment. She commented that, for her, only the headteacher has the power to improve the school by making sure that the premises are appealing and that the teaching and learning environment is strengthened. While discussing the role of the Headteacher in leading school improvement, which included promoting a quality learning environment, she was quick to point out the following aspects:

They are all aware that vision comes first, followed by judgment. When people visit a school, they first assess the facility's exterior. If they find it satisfactory, they move on to looking for other characteristics that are essential to running an effective school. When the headteacher is very active and effective in their leadership, they can easily overcome challenges to make the school's learning environment appealing with the help of community members (School A Fieldnotes, 6 February 2023).

As noted here, keeping a good relationship between the headteacher and SMC members ensuring a child-friendly school environment. That was revealed in the statement by the Chairman of School C. The chairman of the managing committee of School C stated that although most schools only have one pre-primary classroom division, his school has two separate sections. He emphasised that he and the headteacher were careful to provide all the equipment needed for the pre-primary classroom decorations in these classes. Furthermore, he mentioned that the pre-primary classroom decorations pleased the education officers and the DPE visitors. He added that while the government supplied funding each year to update the toys and decorations in the pre-primary classrooms, he also assisted the headteacher in managing funds to make these classrooms child-friendly. He appreciated the headteacher's effort to make the school environment appealing.

This statement is consistent with the researcher's informal conversation with teacher Ms L at School B. The teacher reflected that when calling a parents' meeting, parents of pre-primary students request more toys, while others suggest improvements to the seating arrangement. Some parents also expressed concern about their children's comfort in hot weather and proposed increasing electric fans in every classroom. The teacher explained that they then share the parents' perspective with the headteacher, enabling her to secure the necessary equipment through the support of the school managing committee and government funding.

The above field notes emphasised the importance of the headteacher's involvement in improving the classroom environment, increasing enrolment and attendance and, in turn, improving the schools. The findings revealed that all the stakeholders expect the headteacher to provide the necessary items. Kamal and Chowdhury (2019) emphasised headteachers' crucial role in creating a joyful learning environment in Bangladesh's government primary schools. This finding is noteworthy, as Kamal and Chowdhury revealed that headteachers engage stakeholders by organising cultural programs to involve the community in fundraising efforts. This aligns with the current study, where the headteachers of Schools A and C employed similar strategies to encourage stakeholders during their fundraising initiatives.

Field notes from observations, informal conversations, and document reviews revealed that the headteacher's role includes brokering resources for classroom decoration and repairs to maintain a quality learning environment. From the three schools, the headteachers acknowledged their role in school improvement and the need to involve stakeholders to ensure a quality learning environment. Findings from this study demonstrate that stakeholders in three government primary schools in Bangladesh agreed on the headteacher's key role in ensuring and managing the quality of the learning environment. Stakeholders highlighted various activities supporting this quality environment, including ensuring a clean and tidy school campus, well-decorated classrooms with adequate lighting and electric fans, comfortable seating arrangements, access to pure drinking water, clean toilets, a school garden and sufficient teaching aids to carry out effective classroom teaching. These findings illustrate that the headteachers performed both instructional and pedagogical leadership roles. Instructional leadership was evident in their strategic management of resources and efforts to align teaching practices with school improvement goals (Hallinger, 2011), while pedagogical leadership was reflected in their commitment to enhancing the learning environment and supporting teachers' daily instructional work (Male & Palaiologou, 2015). Together, these leadership approaches underpin how school leaders influence student motivation, attendance, and overall learning outcomes.

While existing studies (Alam et al., 2023; Khan, 2012) have investigated and identified the importance of a quality learning environment that includes appealing teaching and learning environments and is linked to enrolment and attendance, most did not specifically focus on the role of headteachers in ensuring a quality learning environment. This gap in the literature is

addressed by the current study, which emphasises that the classroom should be well-decorated with an appealing school atmosphere to attract young children and their parents and that the head teacher is responsible for providing these facilities to ensure students' increased enrolment and attendance.

6.3 Role of Headteacher in Securing Funds and Managing Resources

Observing and speaking with headteachers in the three primary schools indicated that securing funds and resources was seen as one of their essential roles in ensuring school improvement. Headteachers revealed how prudent money management from the central government through the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (MOPME) was essential in ensuring that various school activities were financially supported. Furthermore, the headteachers explained the need to secure additional funds and resources from the local community to support school activities.

In informal conversation, the headteachers revealed how they organised events such as mothers' gatherings, annual sports, cultural programs, prize-giving ceremonies and international day celebrations (with the support of SMCs) and invited the Upazila Education Officer (UEO) as guests. At these events, parents and other guests were encouraged to give funds and gifts, which the schools would use to support various school-related projects. Inviting UEOs was seen as necessary because their presence attracted the attendance of parents and other stakeholders keen to listen to the officers' advice and words of 'wisdom'. Observations at one school provided an important snapshot of what typically happens during one of these events:

It is 21st February 2023, and the event is International Mother Language Day. Part of the school grounds is covered with tents and chairs. Students are present in their school uniforms and wearing black badges. The headteacher, teachers, education officers, SMC chairman, parents, and other community members are also present wearing black dresses with black badges (black because of remembering the tragic history of sacrificing lives to establish the mother language 'Bangla'). Students walk barefoot while carrying flowers, which they later place on the Shaheed Minar, a Martyrs' monument situated on the school's campus, following Bangladeshi tradition. After placing flowers, the headteacher calls the students. In his speech, the headteacher thanks all the guests. As he finishes, the headteacher makes a plea for support, for example, that the school needs electric fans for classrooms. In her speech, the UEO praises the headteacher for organising the event and

inviting the community to attend. She also invites the community to support the headteacher in school improvement activities. After the UEO sits down, one of the attendees (SMC chairman) pledges that he will provide two electric fans for the school (School A Fieldnotes, 21 February 2023).

Here, the headteachers' role was central in ensuring that the community was involved in the schools' efforts to secure resources and funds to support school improvement initiatives, such as securing classrooms' fans to provide a conducive learning environment for students, especially during the summer. Research indicates that government primary schools in Bangladesh face significant funding shortages (Das, Us-Sabur, and Shafiq, 2015; Hossen, Khondker, and Raihan, 2020; Mousumi, and Kusakabe, 2021), prompting school leaders to seek financial support from local stakeholders (Islam and Fardosh, 2013). This observation implies that such funding inadequacies are present in the schools involved in this study, as evidenced by the headteacher of School A actively pursuing local stakeholder contributions to enhance school improvement efforts.

Schools were observed to be seeking support in other areas. For example, in school B, the headteacher exercised her active role in utilising the government Fund (SLIP) to buy essential items for school improvement:

The researcher and a teacher accompanied the head teacher on a visit to a nearby shop (close to her school) to buy a water pipe. The headteacher found the schoolyard was filled with dust, so she planned to use a water pipe to help reduce the dust on the school grounds. It was also observed that she hired someone to clean her school's top roof (School B Fieldnotes, 12 January 2023).

The above practical and needs-based decision-making demonstrates her instructional leadership, where headteachers take direct actions to create a safe and supportive learning environment (Hallinger and Murphy, 1985; Hallinger, 2011). By addressing physical conditions that affect student comfort and attendance, the headteacher reflected a leadership approach focused on improving teaching and learning conditions. Afterwards, in an informal conversation with the researcher, the Headteacher explained how the funds were used to buy water pipes and pay for the roof's cleaning costs. She detailed that she used money from the SLIP fund (received from the Government) for various initiatives, including purchasing

teaching aids, repairing toilets, addressing water pump issues, filter installation, and maintaining the school premises. She added that only the SMC chairman occasionally provided funds for school improvement. For example, in 2022, he contributed 3,000 BDT to fund the annual sports prizes for the students, approximately GBP 23 based on 2022 exchange rates. Additionally, she mentioned that each year, she and her staff established a fund to purchase uniforms for underprivileged students, funded by their Zakat donations (the almsgiving by Muslims to assist those in need). She shared her plans by stating that once the new school building construction was completed and the school field was ready to arrange a meeting, she planned to organise an Alumni event to foster social gatherings, which might help fund the school.

The observation and informal conversation above highlighted the headteacher's role and dedication to improving the school. She demonstrated resourcefulness by utilising the SLIP fund for essential needs, such as dust control and cleaning the rooftop, while also planning to involve the community through alumni events. Lacking an engaged SMC and an affluent community, she and her team established a fund from charity money (Muslim's Zakat donations) for buying uniforms and other necessary supplies for them to continue the school improvement initiatives, highlighting her competence and commitment to adapt to limited financial support from school stakeholders. A study conducted by Al Mamun (2014) on the purpose of SMC in Bangladeshi government primary schools revealed that when headteachers follow school improvement plans, they receive both government and local donations. However, local donations from rural areas were small or zero, whereas the urban community was engaged in supporting the school improvement plan. The study findings are equally pertinent to the location of school B. Section 5.6 previously mentions that School B is located in a suburban region, and most students are referred to as floating children since they come from slums.

Conversely, the head teacher at school C illustrated her ability to engage donor support for the school's enhancement initiatives effectively. It was interesting to see that she invited influential people within the school's catchment area, such as a local political leader and government high officials, simply for coffee. A pre-planned meeting at School C with the presence of the headteacher, SMC chairman, a local leader, and a community-rich businessman was observed on 19 January 2023:

The headteacher was on the phone, inviting someone to her office to have a coffee. After finishing the call, she looked at me and explained that she had invited a local leader and a wealthy businessman to visit her office. The SMC Chairman will also join them. Then she asked her office assistant to prepare snacks and coffee for all the guests. Shortly afterwards, the two guests and the chairman arrived at her office. The environment was lively, and the discussion mainly covered the political situation, inflation of daily commodities, and the current situation of primary education. The headteacher systematically shifted the discussion towards the school's requirement, mentioning that the inflation of daily goods severely affected the poor parents of her school. She highlighted the requirements for some students' school bags and uniforms. She continued by mentioning that the school's funds were almost depleted, then appealed to her guests, as the community's wealthy individuals, to contribute to supporting the school's disadvantaged students, so that in the future, these students could contribute to national development. When she delivered her speech, her words resonated with the guests; one of the leaders said he would provide 5000 BDT for the school improvement through the SMC chairman. He also assured the headteacher that he would inform some of his friends who might contribute to her school improvement activities.

The above field notes indicated the headteachers' proactive approach to building relationships with the community by inviting influential individuals to fill the gaps where government funding was insufficient for fulfilling the school development activities. The invitation for coffee might be seen as informal behaviour, though it was a carefully considered action by the headteacher to build relationships with potential donors. By presenting the school's needs as a national duty, she motivated the donor to quickly commit 5000 BDT, paving the way for additional support. This highlights that headteachers can take on a proactive role, serving not only in administration but also as community mobilisers, fundraisers, and advocates for students.

Their (headteacher and SMC chairman's collaborative actions) proactive engagement with the community and the ability to leverage the limited government fund suggest their practical leadership skills, particularly in arranging various school events and building relationships with the local community. Ananda (2021) found that in Bangladesh, headteachers of government primary schools employ instructional leadership to gain community support and secure resources through the School Management Committee (SMC) for necessary school reforms. These approaches were very essential for school improvement, where external fundraising was

sparse. However, the observations reported above revealed the issues that headteachers in government primary schools confront due to inadequate government allocation/funding.

6.4 Headteacher's Role in Sustaining Focus on Student Academic Success

The study revealed that paying attention to daily attendance to enhance student academic success is one of the key roles expected of headteachers towards school improvement. Headteachers in the three schools identified students' attendance and academic success as important indicators of school improvement. When pressed to explore this further as to what they meant by academic success as 'school improvement', headteachers of all three schools gave examples such as students being able to read and write accurately in both Bengali and English, excelling in Mathematics and importantly doing well in the school's annual examinations.

They noted that when students are frequently absent from classes, they struggle to understand the lessons, which in turn pushes teachers to repeat lessons, a task that teachers are often unwilling to undertake. Noting that some students constantly arrived late to their first period, the headteachers exhibited concern over the impact on the teachers and made every effort to ensure students' punctuality. Headteachers stated their commitment to arranging regular parent meetings and encouraged teachers to communicate with parents to ensure good attendance. They emphasised that during daily assemblies, they have regular meetings with parents to encourage them to make sure their children do not miss school unnecessarily, or, in cases where they cannot attend school, the parents should contact the class teacher or headteacher to authorise their absence. This was evident from an observation at School A:

The headteacher was seen monitoring the daily assembly. It started with the pledge and ended with the national anthem. This was followed by a short speech by the headteacher on the importance of reading attentively, emphasising the school's key rules, such as punctuality and arriving on time with a school uniform, which was significant for school discipline. Finally, he instructed all the pupils not to make unauthorised absences, suggesting calling their class teacher if they need to leave (School A Fieldnotes, 13 February 2023).

The above observation highlighted the headteacher's active role in leading school improvement, specifically by monitoring the students' assembly and motivating them, which

boosted the students' attendance and ultimately enhanced their academic success. This finding is consistent with a previous study conducted in secondary schools in Bangladesh by Islam, Rahman, and Islam (2023), which found that head teachers had a noticeable leadership influence on student engagement by overseeing and assessing students' academic progress, involving them in extracurricular activities and providing guidance and motivation for active participation in classroom teaching and learning. The study also found that some principals support disadvantaged, talented pupils by providing books, uniforms, funding, and tuition waivers. They frequently stimulate students by organising essay and quiz competitions, offering incentives for good grades, and encouraging them to attend class, which ensures a high-quality classroom performance.

Another observation in school A indicates the headteacher's effort to enhance students' attendance by engaging the stakeholders:

The headteacher is in his office sitting with the SMC chairman, discussing various strategies for encouraging the students to begin the year by presenting rewards for attendance and excellent behaviour and placing first, second, and third in class. He intended that this would inspire all students to develop their activities regarding attendance and academic success. The head teacher at School A recommended to the managing committee that he wished to provide prizes to students based on a variety of criteria, and the chairman of SMC chose to sponsor these awards from his personal funds and thanked the head teacher for this innovative plan to encourage the students (School A Fieldnotes, 2 February 2023).

As noted in this observation, enhancing school improvement can be supported by the headteacher's engagement with key stakeholders. It was also observed that the headteacher frequently connected with the local community, and the management committee members arranged meetings with education officers to boost students' attendance. In an informal conversation, the headteacher of school A revealed that he was working to enhance students' attendance by creating a sound environment in the classroom where students found interest in learning within lessons. He did this by acting as both an administrator and a teacher. This dual role illustrates the headteacher's instructional leadership, as he was directly involved in teaching and guiding his staff to strengthen classroom practices. His continuous presence in lessons and emphasis on pedagogical improvement align with Hallinger and Murphy's (1985)

notion that effective instructional leaders focus on managing the instructional programme and promoting a favourable learning climate. Through his modelling of effective teaching strategies, the headteacher influenced his teachers to prioritise student engagement and achievement. He motivated his team to participate more enthusiastically in teaching and learning.

This was also observed in the headteacher's classroom practice at school A. The headteacher at school A emphasised that he believed the students' performance was crucial to the school's improvement. For this reason, he worked hard to inspire the teachers to employ various classroom strategies to pique students' interest. While observing in School A, field notes reflect that the headteacher frequently engaged in classroom activities. He believed his presence in the classroom encouraged his teachers to work hard to keep students active and engaged. School A's headteacher conducted classes in Primary Five: Section A Mathematics and Section B English. The following is an observation of the Class Five English class:

At the beginning of the class, the headteacher started a song. It looked like all the students became happier after listening to the music, and some sang with him. After that, he showed the children some posters and pictures with new words. Then, he wrote some new words on the whiteboard and invited the children to repeat them aloud in English and Bengali. The students were then instructed to copy all the new words. The headteacher opened the textbook and read 'Saikat's Family'. Students were working in groups to practise reading. Finally, he instructed the students to present their readings to the group. Five students appeared to struggle with English reading. The headteacher assigned five more active learners to teach and learn in pairs. He concluded the class by assigning them the homework of writing ten sentences about their families (School A, February 1, 2023).

The field notes above highlighted the headteacher's effort to enhance students' academic progress. His use of teaching material and active participation in his class were intended to inspire his teaching team to follow his example. Here, the headteacher acted as a role model to motivate the teachers. One teacher at school A shared that their headteacher always arranged meetings to discuss improving their skills to ensure students' academic success. This viewpoint aligns with Ananda's (2021) research, which examined how headteachers' instructional leadership aids teachers in improving their performance in the classroom. According to this study, headteachers can train teachers using various classroom strategies after monitoring

students' performance. Furthermore, the study found that head teachers emphasised the necessity of professional development for teachers to improve classroom performance and encouraged teachers to receive training.

This was also found at School B, where the headteacher regularly monitored the daily assembly and classroom practice to ensure students' academic success. This was observed on January 15, 2023:

During the headteacher's routine of monitoring teachers' classrooms, she found grade 3 students in the Bangla class. The teacher was sitting and delivering the lesson; however, some students were not engaged in the classroom instructions. She also observed another class where the teacher delivered English to the students of class four primary students. She found that some students were disengaged while the teacher was instructing them.

During lunch break, she discussed both observations with the teachers, suggesting they could use more effective strategies to engage the students. She suggested group work so that they could learn from their peers. She also suggested they make the group mix stronger and weaker learners. After that, she concluded that when teachers successfully engage the students in classroom instruction, students feel interested, encouraging them to attend school every day. In a follow-up observation, one week later, both teachers implemented some of the approaches suggested by the head teacher and more successfully engaged the learners. The teachers were pleased to share the positive news about incorporating group work with the headteacher and other colleagues. The headteacher thanked them in front of the rest of the staff and encouraged everyone to follow such methods, which benefited the students. The above field notes emphasised the headteacher's endeavour to effectively engage the teachers in classroom instruction by regularly monitoring and providing support to enhance classroom instruction. It also highlighted how regular classroom monitoring by the headteacher, and constructive feedback can enhance students' academic performance. This is also found in a study by Lamia (2021) in primary schools in Dhaka, Bangladesh, to investigate headteachers' leadership roles in achieving quality primary education. This study found that the headteacher's instruction of the peer learning approaches helped teachers engage students more effectively.

The headteacher of School C shared the same viewpoint, emphasising the importance of pair work and group work to ensure weaker learners benefit and learn from stronger learners. She also emphasised that teachers should not sit in one place but rather move around the class and observe the students' activities, which can enhance students' performance and enable the learners to engage more fully in the lesson. This approach was encouraged during the weekly meeting with teachers at School C, as follows:

The headteacher met with the teachers to discuss classroom needs. The Teacher Representative (TR), Ms L, noted the need for at least four whiteboards for the current year. The headteacher recorded the meeting's summary in her notebook. After addressing several requirement issues, she shifted the conversation to classroom instruction. She urged teachers in January and February to concentrate on assessing students' achievements and identifying areas where progress was lacking, especially in Bangla and English reading and writing. She recommended that teachers compile a list of each class based on their learning capabilities and group students into weaker and stronger learners. Additionally, she reinforced the importance of teachers moving around the classroom to observe student activities, which would enhance performance. She also noted that the SMC and Education Officers would monitor all classes' performance. To conclude, she directed the TR to submit progress reports for all classes within two weeks, stressing her desire to maintain the school's good reputation and calling for increased commitment and dedication from the teachers.

The above field notes highlighted the headteacher's proactive role regarding supervision of teaching and learning and constructive feedback to enhance teachers' classroom activities and students' learning. Like school A and B headteachers, the headteacher of school C also emphasised peer learning to help the weaker students get the support they require. The headteacher's instruction to identify students' learning gaps and take the initiative accordingly was intended to direct the teachers towards setting targets for systematically supporting pupil progress.

Additionally, the observation suggests that the head teacher was proactive in her efforts to improve teachers' abilities and uphold the school's reputation through careful supervision intended to inspire instructors to improve their pedagogical practices, which eventually contributes to students' academic performance. The observation also noticed the headteachers' efforts to collaborate with teachers, TR, SMC, and education officials to improve students'

academic performance, which is consistent with the findings of Morshed's (2016) research on secondary schools in Dhaka, Bangladesh. The study discovered that headteachers used instructional leadership to communicate and share their school's vision with teachers and relevant stakeholders in implementing ICT-based classroom instruction.

Few studies have been undertaken in Bangladesh to examine the influence of headteachers in improving students' academic progress. The existing studies (Kamal, and Chowdhury; 2019; Kabir, Green, and Chowdhury, 2020; Ananda, 2021; Tasnim, 2021; Islam, Rahman, and Islam, 2023) in both primary and secondary schools provide headteachers' leadership practices. However, they do not specifically clarify headteachers' direct role in achieving students' academic success. The current study fills this gap by explaining the headteachers' role in ensuring a sustained focus on student's attendance and academic success.

6.5 Role of the Headteacher in Ensuring Active Parental Involvement

Ensuring active parental involvement in school activities was noted as the headteacher's role towards school improvement. In the three schools, headteachers were seen to play a vital role in encouraging parents to participate actively in school activities and, by doing so, help in the education of their children. For instance, the headteacher of School A considered parents as essential stakeholders in achieving the school's overall goals and acknowledged the necessity of their active participation. He noted that sometimes it was challenging to involve parents in school reform initiatives because the socioeconomic status of most parents in primary schools was poor. However, he believed a proactive headteacher could establish clear communication to facilitate more effective parent involvement. The following observation represented the headteacher of School A's efforts to involve the parents in school improvement activities in the presence of the teachers on February 2, 2023:

The Headteacher offered tea and biscuits to the attendees. Eight parents and five teachers attended the meeting in the pre-primary classroom. Only the primary five children's parents were contacted today, and teachers were also teaching in class five. The headteacher expressed his disappointment at seeing the poor attendance of parents after sending invitations to twenty parents. He invited all the teachers to talk about how well the students performed in class and any important points they wanted to bring up. Following the conversation's conclusion with the teachers, the headteacher talked about several school improvement initiatives, such as homework, classroom activities, and student attendance.

The head teacher mainly addressed parental support for their child's attendance, learning and wellbeing. He concluded the meeting by emphasising that since students will move to high school the following year, parents should handle it carefully to support their child's academic success.

The above observation highlighted the headteacher's active effort to involve parents in school improvement activities. The above field notes clearly show that the headteacher understands the importance of parents as key stakeholders in achieving the school's overall goals. The headteacher tried to get their attention by involving the class teacher in acknowledging their children's achievements. This dimension reflects the headteacher's role as an instructional leader, as he sets a clear vision focused on enhancing students' academic performance through collaborative efforts between teachers and parents. Instructional leaders often establish well-defined goals centred on student achievement and create supportive structures to realise these goals (Hallinger and Murphy, 1985). In addition, the headteacher values the parents' focus on their contribution; only they can support the headteacher in ensuring their child's attendance, learning, and wellbeing. These findings are aligned with the findings of Jahan and Embong (2023), who examined students' outcomes in primary schools in Bangladesh in the context of supportive parents. The study found a positive correlation between Parent-Teacher Association activities and parental involvement, which are statistically significant in student outcomes. The following observation further highlighted the headteacher's proactive role in enhancing parents' involvement in school improvement activities.

After finishing the meeting with the parents, the headteacher came to his office along with all the teachers. Afterwards, he spoke with the staff about how they could, together, include more parents in meetings to enhance school improvement activities. The headteacher advised teachers to improve their communication with parents, asking them to update parent contact information. This initiative would help teachers communicate with the parents in case students were absent and inform them of the school's good news, any events that happened, or their children's stipend issues. Furthermore, he encouraged teachers to invite parents to join PTA meetings. He concluded the meeting by giving the teachers final instructions to observe the parents who regularly wait in the playground for their children after school, as some of these parents might be interested in volunteering, especially in helping with daily assemblies, as it could make them feel valued and encouraged them to

be more involved with school improvement activities (School A Fieldnotes, 2 February 2023).

The aforementioned observation highlighted the headteacher's role in fostering parental engagement in school improvement activities. It was evident that the headteacher's commitment to engaging parents reflected the significance of the headteacher's proactive leadership role in encouraging teachers' consistent communication, updating teacher-parent associations, and creating supportive spaces for parents to participate in school events. However, despite the headteacher's constant efforts to engage the parents in school improvement initiatives, low parental presence in meetings indicates the headteacher's leadership challenges. These findings are consistent with the study by (Biswas, 2021) who investigated parents' involvement in students' learning in rural primary schools in Bangladesh and found that the headteachers carry out several activities to include the parents in school improvement activities such as parent meetings, monthly mother assembly, and informal parent meetings outside of school. The study highlighted the main issues that head teachers deal with; nevertheless, parents' low levels of education and financial situation make it difficult for them to interact with schools, which makes it difficult to ensure students' academic achievement.

This is supported by another observation in School A that showed how parental engagement played a significant role in increasing student attendance, as observed on 9 February 2023:

During lunch on a Thursday, a discussion with the headteacher in School A in the presence of some teachers centred on parental involvement in improving the school. One teacher, Ms F, noted that parents became more active in their children's education under the headteacher's leadership. She highlighted that all parents valued the headteacher's leadership role, encouraging them to stay involved. Another teacher, Ms K, added that the headteacher's welcoming approach made parents feel more confident in being involved in school, giving students confidence and motivation. This led to better attendance and improved academic performance, as they received support from the schools and their families. A senior staff member, Ms P, noted that some mothers would drop off their children at school and stay until classes ended. Their presence directly impacted the school's improvement, as teachers and students were more alert, knowing they were being watched. Some parents even reported unusual behaviours from teachers or students to the headteacher. Another senior teacher, Mr H, mentioned that many parents stayed on the school campus during the morning shift (pre-primary, class one and class two). Some of

these parents seemed to have connections with the headteacher and the SMC chairman and were quick to report any issues.

As noted in the observation above, teachers' reflections on active parental involvement in their children's education directly helped improve schools as parents and teachers understood that they were welcome in school. Equally, parental presence on the school campus created a sense that parents monitored teacher and pupil behaviour and sometimes reported to the headteacher and SMC. The headteacher of school A also confirmed that, even when he was not present on the school campus, the parents kept him informed of what was happening on the school premises. This sense of being monitored by the engaged parents (rightly or wrongly) kept the teachers alert and served to maintain higher standards in classroom teaching and learning. The above observation underscores the headteacher's role in fostering and encouraging parental involvement in school improvement.

Moreover, he (in)directly monitors the school by building a positive relationship with the parents. This collaboration between the headteacher, teachers and parents created a culture of accountability where both teachers and students feel motivated to perform their best. These field notes suggest that creating a welcoming environment for parents where they feel valued can enhance school improvement. Afrin and Chowdhury (2019) researched Bangladeshi rural government primary schools to investigate the parents' role in their children's education. The findings illustrate that parents and teachers are well-informed about the positive effect of parental engagement on their students' learning. The study revealed that building good relationships, regular interaction between parents and schools, and arranging training for working and socio-economically disadvantaged parents can enhance parents' involvement in their children's education.

Similar opinions on the importance of parental involvement were shared by the headteacher of school B, who emphasised how partnership with engaged parents could significantly enhance the learning environment for students. In a meeting with the parent-teacher association (PTA) at school B, which took place in the pre-primary classroom, the headteacher was seen suggesting the parents maintain connection by keeping in regular contact with the headteacher and teachers and discussing their children's strengths and weakness, as doing so would support their academic success and increase the teachers' sense of accountability.

Three PTA members at School B also agreed that when the headteacher and his team actively encouraged parental participation, it considerably aided numerous school improvement activities. For example, it helps ensure children's attendance, allows them to complete their homework properly, and ultimately, the headteacher can acknowledge the teachers' classroom performance through parents. This is also supported by a study by Ullah (2021) investigating parental engagement in government primary schools in Dhaka. This study underlined the importance of parental engagement in ensuring their children's achievement. yet the study also identified substantial barriers to parental involvement in their children's education, such as illiteracy and socioeconomic status. In his research, the author discovered that headteachers organised meetings to engage parents in their children's education and visited schools frequently to communicate their children's education status, including weak points, with teachers.

Another observation occurred in a brief tea-time meeting on 17 January 2023. It was held in the School B teacher's room with the headteacher and eight other teachers before starting the second shift. It was observed:

The headteacher and the teachers' conversation focused on an interesting theme that one of the class three teachers shared. She discussed a student's artwork representing a village scene that her mother encouraged all the teachers to view. The teacher mentioned that the art was appealing and that the student's mother was very involved in her child's education. This parent was constantly concerned about her child's education and spoke with the teachers when she thought it was essential. The head teacher was pleased and appreciated that the teacher was aware of the parents' interest. She carefully redirected the conversation to emphasise the parents' involvement. She gave her teachers instructions to periodically check to see if parents were signing off on the students' homework so that parents were aware of their progress. The headteacher also emphasised the importance of staying connected with parents. She also supported teachers if they needed help to engage parents more effectively.

The above information highlights the headteacher's proactive role in enhancing students' performance by encouraging teachers to involve parents in regular communication about their children's learning. Here, the headteacher appreciated one of her teachers for valuing the

parents' active engagement in their child's education. At the same time, she encouraged all her teachers to involve the parents in the students' learning setting. By doing that, the headteacher set an example of valuing the parents as important stakeholders in school improvement. The study conducted by Islam (2021) in Bangladesh also mentioned that the headteachers and teachers both expressed the importance of involving parents, as they have school guidelines which they always maintain through organising parent meetings. This study also emphasised the importance of quality and frequency of interaction and collaboration between parents and teachers to improve children's education.

The headteacher's strategy to involve parents in signing off homework demonstrated her commitment to involving the parents in the monitoring process. These initiatives were positioned to help create a bridge between the school and home, supporting the headteacher in gaining parental commitment to pupil learning. In addition, the above observation suggests that the head teacher plays a proactive role in strengthening the teachers' and parents' relationship, which is very effective in enhancing students' academic growth. Besides, offering support to the parents involved by the headteachers reflects a collaborative leadership practice where teachers feel empowered to address challenges, ultimately helping the headteacher to develop students' outcomes and a strong parent-teacher association within the school.

The dedication to connecting with parents was also evident with the headteacher of School C. In an informal conversation, the headteacher stated that active parents were the second key to enhancing schools, following teachers. This was, she felt, because active parents monitor their kids at home, ensure they attend school consistently and provide support, both of which enhance the educational quality in the classroom. She noted that by sharing feedback on classroom requirements, teachers' performance, and students' learning difficulties, parents assist the headteacher in tailoring the learning environment better to meet students' demands. This proactive role was also evident in an observation at School C:

The headteacher was sitting in her office with the school managing committee chairman when she instructed Ms L, the teacher representative (TR), to inform all the teachers to check whether students were bringing water bottles and school tiffin (lunch). If students were missing these essentials, she suggested that class teachers inform their parents and

request that they ensure their children's well-being. She concluded that if the issues persist, the teachers should inform the headteacher, who would then directly engage with the parents (School C Fieldnotes, 5 March 2023).

Similar viewpoints were expressed by the chairman of school C, who stated that parents contribute substantially to enhancing schools and that active parents can help shape their children's academic careers by collaborating with headteachers. He noted that when the headteacher reached out to parents to share students' progress, it enabled parents to take practical actions that support their children's academic success. He added that he observed that the children of parents related to the SMC, headteachers, and teachers always performed well. The chairman of School A also expressed similar views; when parents visit the school regularly and observe teachers' efforts in the classrooms, their negative attitude usually shifts away from the teachers. He concluded that it is ultimately the headteacher's responsibility to strengthen the relationship between teachers and parents to enhance school improvement efforts.

As observed in school C, the above field notes highlighted the headteacher's concern for students' well-being. It also highlighted the headteacher's commitment to accomplishing the school's vision by building a relationship with the parents and focusing on their children's well-being. The field notes from informal conversations with the chairman of Schools A and C also revealed the importance of parents' engagement with the schools, which ultimately supports their children's academic success. The field notes also emphasised the chairman of School A's view that the headteacher's responsibility is to ensure a positive relationship between teachers and parents to enhance students' achievements. These results are relevant to Robin's (2021) research in Bangladeshi government primary schools, which aimed to explore the link between parents' involvement and pupils' academic success. This study discovered that multiple factors, including parental-teacher relationships, parental involvement with schools, parental participation in various school programs, and parental participation in school reform talks, are highly related to students' academic success.

6.6 Role of the Headteacher in Ensuring Well-Prepared, Trained and Motivated Teachers

The study found that the role of headteachers in keeping teachers motivated was an essential component of school improvement. It was noted how having motivated teachers also enhanced classroom practice. Headteachers in this study highlighted their role in ensuring teachers were

effectively motivated. It was pointed out that motivated teachers are likely to be professional and, therefore, well-prepared when planning and teaching. After being appointed, teachers receive all essential training, including a Diploma in Primary Education (DPED) and 6-day subject-based training. The headteacher of School A emphasised several elements affecting the quality of teaching, such as the teacher's higher education, subject-based training, active classroom practice, job dedication, and concern for students' learning. He mentioned some issues that hindered the proper training of the teachers.

School A's headteacher is also a master trainer of mathematics (6-day subject-based training) in Thana's education. As a master trainer, he observed that some teachers were keen on receiving comprehensive subject-based training, while others opted not to participate. As a result, these teachers often failed to provide adequate classroom instruction. The headteacher also shared why they are not interested in receiving training, citing several reasons. They find working longer hours boring and dislike going outside the school. Additionally, many female teachers prefer to return home after school rather than receive training, and some believe the training is ineffective.

He highlighted the headteacher's crucial role in collaborating with the education officer to ensure that all teachers received subject-based training and applied relevant skills to enhance classroom teaching and learning. He went on to say that, aside from building new facilities, the most crucial element in improving schools was strengthening teaching in the classroom. He claimed that he regularly monitored and directed classroom teaching and learning to bring about this development. Aligned with this, School A's headteacher attended classes to act as a role model for teachers, inspiring them through direct example. This reflects an instructional leader who demonstrates high standards even when challenges arise, maintaining professionalism and a strong commitment to excellence (Hallinger, 2010). As observed at school, A headteacher's classroom instruction with the presence of one teacher on February 6, 2023:

At 12.30 pm, I observed the headteacher inviting Ms F to join him in his mathematics class. Ms F taught Mathematics in another section of Class Five. The headteacher wished that following his session, the teacher would adopt some of the techniques shared, improving the other section's engagement and student performance. During his session, the headteacher demonstrated his teaching techniques. The headteacher started by mentally

stimulating the students and engaging them in warm-up activities to prepare them for subsequent lesson activities. Following this, he asked students to solve problems on the board related to subtraction, ensuring students could recall the previous knowledge with today's concept. Students were involved in breaking down the problem and the key concept, focusing on the knowledge identified in subtraction in chapter one. He continued emphasising a single operator, subtraction, to keep the students focused and ensure good understanding. After delivering the lesson and finishing one assessment, he allocated time for group classwork practice. Before concluding the class, he provided 5-minute feedback sessions, especially for those falling behind.

The field notes highlighted the headteacher's key role in ensuring all teachers received subject-based training and applied training skills to enhance classroom teaching and learning, which also aligns with the yearly sector performance report (ASPR), which mentions that all teachers receive subject-based training in the five subjects (Directorate of Primary Education, 2022, p.179). The document demonstrates that there is no provision for recruiting teachers who specialise in specific subjects in primary education in Bangladesh, meaning that each teacher teaches almost every subject in the classroom.

The above field notes also revealed that some teachers receive subject-based training willingly. However, some teachers are not interested in training in all five subjects. A related study conducted by Harris et al. (2017) also confirmed that the Malaysian Education Ministry organised seven days of mandatory professional teacher training for all teachers. The study highlighted that to maintain a prestigious status in the school cluster, teachers often focus on finishing the syllabus to achieve good results for students, and these practices reduce their motivation to attend teachers' training to enhance their skills. This finding is also consistent with the School A headteacher's assertion that some teachers in Bangladesh are not interested in training to improve their classroom skills.

The above field notes also evidence the headteachers' proactive approach to fostering pedagogical development for the teachers, which sought to develop their ability to enhance students' performance. This is also evident in the post-class observation:

Following classroom instruction, the headteacher returned to his office with Ms F. He began discussing mathematical tasks with her, focusing on using a single operation because it was the beginning of the school year, so the students could understand the problem and remain engaged in mathematics. He instructed her to follow the guidelines to improve student performance. He commented that Ms F should notify the headteacher immediately if the children do not grasp the class instructions. He noted that class five is critical for the students because they will move on to high school in the following class (School A Fieldnotes, 6 February 2023).

The above field note demonstrated how the headteacher used instructional leadership, participating in classroom teaching, applying various teaching strategies and demonstrating his support and mentorship to the teacher to improve teaching and learning. As Hallinger (2011) states, instructional leaders cultivate a strong school culture where teaching and learning are valued through the creation of an 'academic press'. In this instance, by inviting the other section's mathematics teacher to observe and participate in this lesson, the headteacher demonstrated a commitment to peer learning to fulfil his role as a headteacher in promoting and role-modelling effective classroom teaching and learning. This approach highlights his role as an instructional role model who promotes reflective practice, collective growth, and a sustained culture of pedagogical excellence. The study (Ananda, 2021) observed that the school's head teacher offered instructional leadership by overseeing and evaluating teachers' teaching performances. The authors found that headteachers visit teachers' classrooms to assess lesson plans, record performance, and watch whether pupils actively participate in classroom instruction. The results also showed that, in line with the field notes above, head teachers can use such instructional leadership to encourage their teachers' professional development training to improve classroom instruction.

Another observation highlighted how the headteacher praised a skilled teacher to motivate others to follow his classroom strategy:

During a weekly teacher meeting, the headteacher recognised a teacher in his office who had been observed in the morning. He provided him with some feedback regarding his class for the day. He began speaking with the English teacher, Mr H and was delighted to see his classroom instructions and the ideal classroom teaching strategy. He added that he noticed that students' engagement was excellent. He told Mr H to keep up this good work.

Then, he invited all the teachers to follow Mr H's strategies. Also, he instructed Mr H to share those techniques with his colleagues (School A Fieldnotes, 9 February 2023).

Based on the above observation, the head teacher increased teacher motivation while providing peer learning opportunities among his teachers. In addition, the research found that School A's headteacher consistently applied various strategies to keep the staff active and motivated in classroom teaching and learning, which is an example of instructional leadership. The finding is consistent with the study by Harris et al. (2017), which found that headteachers in Malaysia apply instructional leadership as they significantly engage routinely in monitoring teachers' classroom activities, mainly to support their classroom development. This demonstrates to the teachers that they are respected and valued.

In an informal conversation, the headteacher of School A shared one strategy he applied last year to motivate one teacher in classroom engagement. According to the headteacher, one of the teachers could not guide the students properly despite his instructions. So, he discussed this issue with the Upazila Education Officer and the Assistant Upazila Education Officer. Both Education Officers noted this issue as being of great importance, and accordingly, they visited that class. However, when the UEO visited this class and found the students had difficulties reading correctly, she instructed the teacher to give extra attention to these students. As a result, the teacher took better care, which helped improve classroom teaching and learning. The headteacher believed that some teachers felt pressure when the headteacher gave them instructions, which could lead them to demotivation. However, when the education officers visited and spoke with the staff and provided recommendations to enhance classroom performance, it became easier for the headteacher to manage the staff effectively.

The above field notes highlighted that the headteacher of school A used various strategies, such as involving the education officers, to motivate his teachers to enhance classroom teaching. The headteacher strongly believed that routine supervision and monitoring by headteachers and education officers could enhance teachers' classroom performance. This statement was also evident during a teacher meeting when the headteacher of school A announced that the UEO would be visiting the school the following week. It was observed:

The headteacher instructed all the teachers to follow the training instructions while teaching. He gave them reminders to use proper teaching aids. He again reminded them to ensure all the students attend the school with proper school dress. The teachers became more dedicated, ensuring they brought teaching aids while teaching in the classroom. However, it was observed that after being instructed by the headteacher, all the teachers arrived at school earlier than usual. Their outfits were likewise really dazzling. Along with the students, they were all well-organised (School A Fieldnotes, March 5, 2023).

The above observation indicated that the headteacher's strategy to invite UEO to motivate teachers demonstrated his proactive role and dedication to school improvement initiatives. According to School B's headteacher, the school could only be strengthened and fulfil all the school's goals by having committed and capable teachers. This study also observed headteacher B's influential leadership role in enhancing teachers' motivation towards classroom teaching and learning. In one example, the researcher noted:

During a teacher meeting, the headteacher praised one teacher, Ms T, as a motivated teacher in her school. She appreciated the teacher's dedication to creating a successful pre-primary classroom. She stated that education officers were quite pleased after visiting the pre-primary classroom. Parents were pleased as well with their children's willingness to attend school. She encouraged another teacher to adopt a similar strategy to impress the young children. She also advised all teachers to develop unique ideas for improving classroom instruction and to apply the knowledge gained from subject-based training (School B office room, 18 January 2023).

The above findings revealed that the headteacher's actions fostered a cooperative atmosphere where skilled and motivated teachers felt valued, which drove them to put in more effort and motivate others. This finding reinforces the idea that effective instructional leaders foster a professional learning culture where teachers' motivation is fundamental to school improvement. To ensure school improvement through effective teaching, the headteacher exemplified Southworth's (2002) view that instructional leadership involves "modelling, monitoring, and dialogue" to promote teacher growth and educational excellence. The data also highlighted that the headteacher of School B believed that if she had a highly motivated teaching team, she could achieve all the set goals for improving the school. The headteacher of School C likewise believed that having dedicated and skilled teachers was the key to the

school's success. Fieldnotes present that to improve teacher effectiveness, headteacher C scheduled a teacher meeting every Thursday to address student achievements and any problems they had. She claimed the school could not operate well if the teachers were not entirely motivated to enhance students' classroom achievements. She also emphasised head teachers' crucial role in enhancing teachers' motivation towards effective classroom teaching and learning.

During a conversation with some parents, the headteacher of School C reinforced the importance of teachers' enthusiasm, expertise, and activity in improving the school's overall performance. Every parent stressed the importance of having caring teachers teach their children. They exhibited their expectations that the head teacher would encourage her team of teachers to teach their children with more attention. The headteacher firmly agreed with all participants that caring and qualified teachers were essential for improving schools and emphasised that her role was to ensure an environment where all the teachers felt equally valued so that they could provide more care for the students.

A recent study by Ahmed, Adhikary, and Rahaman (2024) highlights the need for funding teacher training to ensure students' academic performance in Bangladeshi primary schools. While previous research in Bangladesh has investigated and identified the importance of qualified and experienced teachers in improving the quality of the teaching-learning environment, it has not addressed the role of headteachers in motivating teachers to receive proper preparation and training for effective classroom teaching and learning. The current study addresses this gap in the literature by emphasising that as a school leader, it is the headteacher's role and responsibility to ensure that teachers are well-prepared, trained, and motivated for effective classroom practices.

6.7 Conclusion

Issues raised in this chapter provide insights into understanding headteachers' roles in improving Bangladeshi primary schools. The observations reported in this chapter showed that the study explores and explains how headteachers play a vital role in leading school improvement initiatives by ensuring a quality learning environment, securing school funds and resources, ensuring students' attendance, fostering active parental engagements, and motivating

teachers to get healthy preparation and trained while classroom teaching and learning. The findings here highlight the multifaceted and collaborative leadership approaches where headteachers play a vital role in integrating various ideas and activities, including collaboration with other stakeholders towards effecting school improvement.

Chapter 7: Headteachers' Enactment of Power in Leading School Improvement

7.1 Introduction

The previous chapter explored the findings guided by research question one. As stated in Chapter 1, this study is directed by three research questions. Thus, research question two presents the data using the lens of Foucault's concept of power: subjectivity, governmentality, and disciplinary power, which encompasses hierarchical observation, normalising judgement, and examination. Through this lens, the chapter examines how headteachers in Bangladeshi government primary schools experience power when they exercise leadership in school improvement initiatives. The chapter is divided into three sub-themes: Exercising Subjectivity and Ethics in Pursuit of School Improvement, Governmentality and Headteacher Leadership, and Headteachers' Exercising Disciplinary Power in Monitoring the Quality of learning.

7.2 Exercising Subjectivity and Ethics Towards School Improvement

In the school context, subjectivity and ethics refer to the headteachers' experience, self-knowledge, values, and beliefs that help them shape themselves to successfully engage the wider community (Freie and Eppley, 2014). As described in section 4.3, Foucault identified four parts of the relationship between Subjectivity and Ethics: 1. Ethical substance 2. Mode of subjection 3. Self-forming activities 4. Telos. Headteachers in this study agreed that stakeholders, especially teachers, parents, students, government employees, local government representatives, members of the school managing committee and finally well-wishers, have different expectations from school headteachers. This is also explained by Gillies (2013) who notes that school leaders (headteachers) are undoubtedly influenced by the local authority expectations, and over time these expectations have come to direct the ethical substance of leadership (behaviour concerned with moral conduct) - shaping how the headteachers serve their school according to the stakeholder and local authority expectations.

The headteachers in the three research schools demonstrated the ethical substance of their leadership in relation to the broader community leaders, parents, teachers, students, retired officers, NGO officials and education officers. As an example of self-forming activity, the headteacher of School A was observed to be very active in socialising with the school community's various programs, such as attending the wedding ceremony and cultural program and allowing community leaders to use the school grounds for weekend celebration football

matches and other cultural programs. Informal conversations with the members of the PTA and SMC, along with school records, confirmed that these activities helped strengthen trust and collaboration between the school and its stakeholders. They also showed that such engagement enabled headteachers to mobilise community resources and raise school funds, further enhancing the school's capacity to meet its improvement goals.

Another example of ethical substance was evident in an informal conversation with School A's headteacher. He emphasised how the SLIP instructions actively engaged parents and community members in school improvement activities to ensure the school's overall improvement. To achieve this goal, the headteacher was advised to conduct various activities involving community members, including participation in various social programmes organised by people in school catchment areas. He and most of his teachers actively participated in school community programs, demonstrating their commitment to stakeholder engagement. The head teacher at School A stated that he was involved with community programs after school and most weekends. He often sat with the SMC chairman at the evening tea party in the local political party office. Because he wanted to be judged positively in the community as an effective school leader, he felt it necessary to engage in such activities - an example of a mode of subjection. This notion aligns with Freie and Eppley (2014), who note that, often, for the community to view the school principal favourably, they must actively communicate and engage with the broader school community.

However, this headteacher reflected that he also liked being a part of the school community because it made him feel valued, even though this activity was not part of his job responsibilities. The headteacher was engaging with his community, demonstrating his ethical substance.

The above informal conversations highlight the headteacher's active engagement with the stakeholders and demonstrate how he consciously engaged in self-forming activity to support school improvement. Foucault's theory of subjectivity and ethics is relevant here. As the headteacher maintains a close relationship with parents and community people in the school catchment area, he enacts the ethical responsibilities of his position as a headteacher. To drive school improvement, he engages with community leaders, participating in events that occur outside of official school hours, reflecting his commitment beyond formal duties. His

leadership participation in such out-of-school activities demonstrates the kind of headteacher he aspires to be (telos) - engaging parents and community who, in turn, will want to support improvement initiatives for the school.

In another example of ethical substance, the headteacher of School B discussed her moral obligations through maintaining strong connections with retired officials, political leaders, and local shopkeepers. Her school was near a small market that included grocery and confectionery shops. During an informal conversation, the headteacher mentioned that her school's School Management Committee (SMC) was not fully engaged with school improvement activities. However, she maintained warm relationships with parents, often visiting their homes—a practice she called a 'home visit.' She reflected on the discourses that shaped her (modes of subjection), noting that she likes to be a kind headteacher who accepts her ethical duty to help these economically disadvantaged children in her school. She mentioned that her ethical responsibility was to contact the people who could help her underprivileged students, giving an example of maintaining a good connection with a retired high-ranking official who had helped her facilitate the entry of an NGO into her school. Through this NGO (UNICEF), all her pre-primary students received school bags, bookshelves, and tables for the classrooms. The headteacher was clear about the ethical substance of her role as a headteacher, taking time to greet the small shopkeepers and grocery sellers, as most of them were her students' parents. She also maintained a good relationship with the private high school headteacher next to her school, which resulted in many poor students being admitted to high school with reduced admission fees and monthly tuition fees.

This headteacher was committed to helping students improve their educational outcomes, believing this to be her moral obligation. This reflects Gillies' (2013), who asserts that in cases of modes of subjection, some leaders are not motivated by external influences but may decide how to act by applying ethical or religious codes own. This same headteacher frequently acted as someone who cares for her staff, engaging in self-forming activities aligned to these values, as observed below:

The teachers' room is very large and has a large rectangular table in it. Along with the typical administrative surroundings and meetings, the room is now inhabited by a small, cheerful presence: the four-year-old daughter of a teacher, Miss T. The young girl is playing with the toys she had brought from home while sitting quietly near the window.

At times, she wanders through the space, pointing at various wall-mounted pictures, entering the hallway, and then returning to her seat. I discovered that the head teacher and the other two teachers, Ms MJ and Ms Q, quietly observe, and when they make eye contact with the little girl, they smile to comfort her. Ms T: The mother of the child, who is teaching in the classroom nearby, occasionally comes to see if her child is comfortable or not. The headteacher reassures her with a kind smile, “Don't worry, she'll be fine. Go to the classroom and concentrate on the classroom teaching.” The teacher feels at ease with this straightforward reassurance, and it shows in her eyes with gratitude (School B Fieldnotes, April 5, 2023).

The above observation highlights how this headteacher's flexible attitude toward staff can contribute to a positive school culture. Foucault notes that individuals (those in positions of authority) can demonstrate their moral obligations through direct enforcement and subtly through their actions (Foucault, 2000b, p. 264). The headteacher's authority is exercised in a positive, supportive way; her self-forming activity of flexibility allows her to demonstrate care to the teacher, her child, and the teachers' pupils. By allowing the teacher to bring her young child into the school's office, the headteacher exhibits leadership that prioritises her staff's well-being and evidences the kind of headteacher she aspires to be (telos). Here, power is applied to control and shape the work environment, encouraging trust and care. Power, in this sense, is productive and exists to shape the norms and expected behaviours within School B. By allowing the teacher to keep her young child at the school, the headteacher creates a supportive environment where the teacher feels valued. This, in turn, might enhance her dedication to the school and effectiveness in the classroom, ultimately contributing to school improvement.

Foucault's concept of subjectivity highlights how individuals come to understand themselves within social structures. In this context, the teacher is a subject of institutional power, navigating both her roles as a teacher and a parent. The fieldnotes (School B, April 5, 2023) show that the headteacher's accommodation, allowing the teacher's young child to be present in the staff room and reassuring her, enabled the teacher to balance these dual roles, demonstrating that she is valued. The headteacher, in turn, enacted her own subjectivity by ensuring her staff felt supported, motivated, and cared for, illustrating her ethical and leadership responsibilities (telos).

Another example of ethical substance is the headteacher of School C, who firmly believed in maintaining a strong relationship with the community to support school improvement. In an informal conversation, the headteacher of School C remarked that developing relationships with staff, parents, and SMC members is critical for effectively implementing all school improvement initiatives. She noted that she worked hard to maintain contact with some parents (PTA members), which aided her in implementing her recommendations about school development. These parents talk to other parents about significant issues and act when necessary. Additionally, she maintained strong connections with the SMC chairman and local political leaders and invited them to the school's various programmes.

In addition, the headteacher of school C stated that she sees herself as responsible for ensuring a child-friendly environment to facilitate school improvement. This is subjectivity which relates to how individuals shape, position and understand their roles within the context of school leadership. She continued to state that, she arranged various programs such as the yearly annual picnic, winter food fair, and various national day celebrations to promote the staff's physical health. Besides, she involves the students and their parents in all these programmes including SMC members, PTA members and local leaders who are the well-wishers in her schools. She noted that establishing positive relationships with teachers, SMC members, community members, parents, and children is the primary cause for successful classroom teaching and learning outcomes. Furthermore, the headteacher of School C talked about how she wanted to be considered by the community, SMC, and education officers as a highly skilled headteacher who conducts her students' classroom activities well and produces satisfying students' results. This aligns with Gillies' (2013) reflection that different leaders hold different forms of subjectivity; for example, some leaders may evaluate themselves based on the expectations of the school inspectorate or the students' outcomes.

The headteacher here becomes a subject reflecting her self-forming activities by consciously showing her care for the school's improvement through fostering good relationships with staff, parents and community people. According to Freie and Eppley (2014), Foucault's concept of subjectivity is useful for understanding the reasons behind a principal's interactions with the community. The authors explain that choosing to be actively involved with the community may be interpreted as a form of self-forming activities by the headteacher. As an outsider, the headteacher chooses to show her dedication to the school and community through continuous

fostering of communication with them. By showing dedication to the community, she demonstrates that she cares and reflects her telos, that she is the person who is an appropriate leader for the school. This ultimately helps the community trust the headteacher and helps them involved with the headteacher when the headteacher invites them to various school improvement initiatives.

7.3 Governmentality and Headteachers' Leadership

Foucault explains that different forms of power, such as the authority of rulers (sovereignty), control through discipline (like rules, surveillance, and routines), and the management of people through systems and policies (governmentality), do not simply replace one another over time. Instead, these powers work together and influence society in different but connected ways. He describes this as a triangle of sovereignty, discipline, and government, all focused on shaping and managing the population. As he states:

We need to see things not in terms of the replacement of a society of sovereignty by a disciplinary society and the subsequent replacement of a disciplinary society by a society of government; in reality, one has a triangle, sovereignty-discipline-government, which has its primary target the population and as its essential mechanism the apparatuses of security (Foucault 2002, p. 219).

Foucault's ideas show that sovereignty, discipline and governmentality do not supersede each other. Instead, these elements worked together to exercise power (Gillies, 2013). Each form of power plays a vital role in implementing governmentality to govern the school. Foucault's idea helps us better understand how headteachers' leadership can be seen as part of governmentality. In this role, headteachers manage and guide schools not just through rules or authority but by working within broader systems of monitoring, accountability, and performance tools that aim to shape the behaviour of teachers, students, and the school community.

In three schools, government power is observed to be exercised by the headteachers to shape the conduct of teachers and students, to improve classroom activities. Through informal conversations and observations of three headteachers, this study found that the headteachers exercise government power by blending norms, regulations, and motivation. These techniques encourage teachers to self-regulate their activities to align with the school's goals and the headteacher's expectations. The headteacher's leadership roles highlight that, in turn, they are

subject to governmentality, albeit indirectly, as their actions demonstrate that they are the government's vehicle for governing staff and students through implementing various school improvement initiatives.

The above is illustrated by the headteacher of School A, based on an informal conversation with him:

The Headteacher of School A was standing on the playground, where he could see all the classrooms. Facing the classroom, he continued his conversation with me. The bell rang to signal the start of the classroom. All students were inside the classroom. Teachers were seen entering the classroom. Students were inside and ready, and they carried their attendance registers and teaching aids. The school environment appears totally disciplined (School A Fieldnotes, 5 February 2023).

In a conversation following this observation, the headteacher explained that this level of discipline in school was not created overnight. He noted that the teachers were not punctual when he first joined the school, but he changed this situation by arriving at school each day earlier than usual. He, along with a few teachers, directed all the students to enter the classroom and selected 2 class captains for each classroom to organise other students and prepare them for the lesson. The headteacher said that when teachers found him in their classroom early in the day, they started to feel embarrassed, and within seven days, they started to come to school on time and enter the classroom. The headteacher proudly stated that even after 20 years, he continues to arrive at school early.

The above emphasises the headteacher's endeavour to enhance the school by enforcing rules and maintaining order in the school's culture. He consistently arrived at school earlier, made sure class activities started on time, and made the teachers and students think about standardising their behaviour to ensure good order. How the head teacher constructed the norms of punctuality and discipline in school encouraged the staff to self-govern their behaviour; as Foucault emphasises, within contemporary neoliberal society, the individual takes the responsibility to govern themselves in line with society's expectations (Gillies, 2013).

According to Mifsud (2020), an acknowledged goal of governmentality in school leadership is to shape the behaviour of others. By enforcing discipline and influencing the behaviour of the

teachers, the teachers, in turn, encourage pupils to regulate their behaviours in line with expected norms. Furthermore, the idea of governmentality extends to how the principal acts as the government's representative, influencing and regulating the conduct of the staff and students (Gillies, 2013). In this instance, the head teacher assigned tasks to students by appointing a class captain to foster peer participation. Additionally, teachers were told how students could help manage the classroom, resulting in a self-sustaining system that enabled the school to accomplish its objectives related to pupil behaviour and classroom engagement, in line with the school's goals. Furthermore, the headteacher's sustained practice of turning up early throughout the last 20 years demonstrated the head teacher's disciplined self-governance. Thus, the techniques used by the head teacher resemble Foucault's concept of governmentality, which served on multiple scales by displaying norms, strengthening discipline, and ensuring punctuality.

The following observation demonstrates how this same head teacher used his authority as a vehicle of government to control student behaviour in the school setting:

All pre-primary to fifth-grade students attend the assembly (everyday activity) on the school grounds. Preschoolers, primary one and primary two students stand with their school bags behind them. There are also some parents standing next to the assembly. After completing all assembly steps, the headteacher delivers a brief speech outlining the school's goals and values and any positive news regarding the teaching staff, school and students. In front of the students stand the head teacher and other teachers. Students are lined up in the field based on their class and height. There is a queue of students from a mixed class. They all wear incomplete school uniforms, with someone missing a school shoe, shirt/top, or pyjamas (School A Fieldnotes, 13 February 2023).

The above field notes emphasise the headteacher's disciplinary practice in school, which includes daily assemblies with all students. Since morning assembly establishes a daily habit for the children to arrive at school on time, the associated activities align with Foucault's concept of conducting conduct, shaping the students' behaviours. The headteacher's identification of students not wearing the appropriate school uniforms and his instruction for them to remain in separate lines highlights his governance practices. The findings align with Gillies' (2013) statement, which notes that the concept of conduct at the school level is

important, as school leaders can exercise this form of conduct when implementing any school development plans. The field notes above also imply that the entire group of students were expected to learn a lesson that helped them maintain their behaviour and dress code and not break the school rules. Here, the headteacher focused on guiding specific students' behaviour (part of the school improvement plan), which resulted in shaping the entire group of students, which is an excellent example of Foucault's concept of 'The conduct of conduct', how individuals are directed to shape their conduct (behaviours).

In the case of school leadership, governmentality refers to using the headteachers as the vehicle to govern the teachers, staff and students (Niesche, 2011). This is seen in the fieldnotes of school B as observed:

The visiting teams consist of eleven education officers from different districts and thana/upazilas are gathered in School B's teachers' room. The team leader is one assistant education officer who first starts talking with the headteacher giving a big thanks from the team. He expressed his admiration for the pre-primary class teacher as they were happy to observe Ms T's classroom teaching performance. He mentions that the teacher's classroom performance was excellent as she successfully kept engaging all the students in her class including using the teaching aids. The team leader mentions that Ms T was teaching the students despite having received only the pre-primary training; the education officer gave the headteacher special thanks as she provided pre-primary training to this teacher to make her eligible to teach pre-primary students (School B Fieldnotes, 20 March 2023).

The field notes suggest that effective leadership by headteachers is essential for implementing school improvement. Here, the headteacher and teachers are subject to the practices of the government through the inspection of classroom teaching by the education officers, whose feedback suggests that they are keen to observe preferred teaching practices, e.g. high student engagement. However, the school headteacher is also a vehicle for governing staff (Niesche, 2011) in pursuit of school improvement, hence praise for the headteacher's quality staff training and selection. Through these processes of governance, the teacher, in turn, acts as an instrument of governmentality, enacting particular preferred teaching and learning practices to secure a positive inspection outcome.

Thus, the headteacher's role involves implementing government regulations to ensure the school's operation as a government institution. The observation shows that the headteacher's decision to choose a qualified teacher to instruct the pre-primary students was commended. This decision might reflect the headteacher's self-governance in improving the quality of teaching and learning in pre-primary classrooms. In the scenario described, Foucault's concept of governmentality can be further applied to choosing a female-trained teacher for pre-primary class teaching and learning. In this case, the headteacher is entrusted with supporting a government priority of raising the quality of pre-primary education. In turn, he functions as a school representative, using his authority to select this specific trained teacher to implement pre-primary classroom teaching.

The field notes of this study indicate that successful school leadership is significant in enacting school improvement. School leaders have exceptional power (government) and influence to enhance organisational goals by influencing teachers' and students' classroom teaching and learning environment. In school leadership, the government uses the headteacher as the key vehicle to govern teachers and students (Freie and Eppley, 2014), and headteachers employ various tools to implement government policies. This is evident in the following observation, where Bangladesh's Ministry of Primary and Mass Education issued guidelines for implementing the Primary Education Stipends, 2021 (2023). The guidelines state that to receive the stipends, students must attend at least 85% of school days each month, except for reasonable causes. In ensuring student attendance, the headteacher of School B appears to exercise governmental power, as observed in a meeting with her teachers:

The headteacher began by addressing the unsatisfactory attendance of the students in the classrooms. She informed the teachers that she had visited all the classrooms, spoken with the students and made a list of the absent students. To address the issue, she had already created a group of students to reach out to their neighbourhood classmates and encourage them to attend school. In the meantime, all teachers were instructed to call the parents to ensure their children's attendance. She also shared her plan that in the assembly class, she will declare gifts for the students monthly who will present 100% in the school. The headteacher instructed the teachers to make classroom teaching and learning engaging to spark students' interest in attending school. To motivate her teachers, she emphasised that most students came from poor families and instructed them to avoid assigning home tasks

rather than finishing them during the class to help encourage attendance (School B Fieldnotes, 17 January 2023).

The above observation highlights the headteacher's proactive efforts to shape students' behaviour by reaching out to their neighbourhood classmates and encouraging them to attend school, ultimately focusing on enhancing school improvement. This finding aligns with Gillies' (2013) statement that home communications can be an example of where conduct can be displayed and exercised at the school level. The field notes show that the headteacher uses peer support to ensure absent students return to school. Here, the headteacher uses students as instruments to help her to fulfil government expectations.

As Foucault emphasises, the principal is not only the person who is subject to fulfilling government practices but also includes staff and students in implementing the school vision and expectations (Freie and Eppley, 2014). In the above example, the headteacher plans to introduce incentives for 100% attendance highlights her use of different techniques and strategies to achieve institutional goals. Since governmentality is defined as the logic of ruling over others (Freie and Eppley, 2014) and the rationalisation of behaviour management (Gillies, 2013), it is evident that the headteacher uses institutional power to govern the teachers by instructing them to finish classroom tasks during class so as to spark students' interest, enhancing attendance and the goal of ensuring students full stipends.

From a governmentality perspective, the headteacher of School C illustrates how leadership involves guiding the behaviour of others to meet institutional expectations. In the school context, Gillies (2013) highlights that internal audits are closely linked to managing conduct, which falls within the everyday responsibilities of school leaders and managers. This is further evident in the following observation, where the headteacher of School C is keen to ensure, during an internal visit, that figures of authority hold her school in high regard. She uses her instructional power to influence the conduct of her teachers and students to achieve desirable goals, as observed:

Today, the TRC (Thana Resource Centre) instructor phoned the headteacher and informed her that she would like to visit her school after lunch. The headteacher then asked the TR

to inform all the teachers about the TRC instructor's visit, advising them to be more focused on classroom instruction and using teaching aids. However, the headteacher also went to the classroom to monitor the situation. She was happy to see all the students were wearing proper school dress and teachers were using teaching aids. The headteacher instructed a few teachers regarding classroom practices and asked the students to respond well when the instructor asked questions (Field note, school C, 22.01.2023)

In the above fieldnotes, the headteacher was keen to inform the teachers of the upcoming visit and monitor their classrooms to encourage the teachers and students to conduct themselves. Here, the headteacher instructed some teachers to follow the classroom norms, as evidenced by governmentality. Furthermore, all her observed behaviours influenced others, demonstrating how she intended to shape individuals' conduct (Gillies, 2013, p.69).

The governmentality of leadership is heavily centred on influencing the conduct of others (Freie and Eppley, 2014; Gillies, 2013). According to Gillies (2013, p. 77), the school leader is a critical aspect of government in the educational setting because he or she influences others to act in a different way that might help achieve the intended goals. Gillies stresses that leaders should seek to transition from government to governance and that school leadership should be distributed so that individuals feel empowered and act as leaders. Using a boating metaphor, he likens school leadership more to "steering" than "rowing" (Gillies, 2013). Interestingly, this notion closely aligns with my findings, particularly the informal conversation with the headteacher of School C, which echoed these concepts. She described how she establishes a vision, involves stakeholders, and 'steers the boat' by implementing governance practices and distributing responsibilities to the appropriate personnel to achieve school goals.

7.4 Headteachers Exercising 'Disciplinary Power' in Monitoring Quality of Learning

In this section, the theme 'Monitoring Quality of Teaching and Learning', emphasises the significant role of monitoring as perceived by the head teachers of three schools. They agree that effective monitoring directly influences school improvement. They all reflected that quality teaching and learning are essential to effectively improving schools. Therefore, they recognise that their active involvement in classroom monitoring ensures quality standards in teaching and learning. The National Student Assessment (NSA, 2022), conducted by Bangladesh's Directorate of Primary Education (DPE) under the Ministry of Primary and Mass

Education (MoPME), used a sample-based technique to collect data on students' learning levels in grades 3 and 5. This assessment also revealed that student achievement was significantly higher when head teachers monitored classroom actions, as supported by outcomes from the teachers' and head teachers' survey questions (National Student Assessment (NSA, 2022). This study's data also links to ensuring effective monitoring for quality classroom teaching and learning as a form of school improvement. The following observation in school A demonstrates this:

There are 60 students in the pre-primary class, and one female teacher is present. The class teacher (CT) wears a green saree (traditional women's garments in Bangladesh) with a red blouse, and all the students wear school uniforms. Girls are dressed in blue skirts, white blouses, and black shoes, while the boys wear white shirts, blue trousers, and black shoes. The belt also has the school's logo on it. When the headteacher enters the room, everyone in the class says, "Good morning, sir." The Headteacher responds, "Good morning, dear students. The CT looks to the headteacher for further instructions, Headteacher tells her to begin her class. With the arrival of the headteacher, the class settles to listening attentively to the teacher. No students are engaged in peer-to-peer chatter or shouting out and the teacher focuses on the details of her lesson to frame the questions [School A, Field Notes, February 2, 2023].

It was interesting to note during this observation that the CT was committed to ensuring that the students received instruction following her training expectations. For instance, she presented the lesson plan, which clearly outlined the content to be covered, the learning outcomes, the teaching approach, the necessary resources (teaching aids; plastic alphabet, chart, flashcards, colour posters), and the activities that were to be used to engage and assess the students. As the headteacher looked through the students' notebooks, the CT continued to interact with the students, appearing accustomed to working with the headteacher in the pre-primary classroom. As the lesson proceeded, the headteacher began talking to some students and greeting them in Bengali and English, and the student's responses was very positive. The headteacher stays in this class for about half an hour, reviewing the students' drawing and letter writing. He appeared pleased with the student's performance and praised the class teacher by commenting on her lesson plan before leaving the classroom

Reflecting after the lesson, the headteacher stated that he monitors the class every morning, believing that teachers would be more conscientious and serious in such a context. The headteacher reflected that monitoring classroom activities was a significant component of school improvement, acknowledging that frequent monitoring from the headteacher increases teachers' and students' attention. The above observation and informal conversation can be reflected upon through a lens of Foucault's concept of power, particularly surveillance and disciplinary power. According to Foucault (1995), disciplinary power is a tool used to categorise, group, and (in this case) normalise individuals and their behaviour, with such power often being exercised through the tools of hierarchical observation, surveillance and normalising judgement - through which the individual is monitored, assessed and judged and (Gillies, 2013).

Freie and Eppley (2014) highlight that in schools, hierarchical observation takes place when students and teachers are observed to discipline and manage behaviours. They also note that disciplinary power can be exercised via normalising judgment, where individuals are subject to judgment that seeks to reinforce preferred norms of behaviour. Such normalising judgment seeks conformity (Foucault, 1977). The third tool of disciplinary power is the examination. This process offers a structured way to assess and classify discipline (Foucault 1977). As noted by Freie and Eppley (2014, p. 666), "examination can use either or both hierarchical observation and normalising judgment in its exercise" and, in schools, may assume the "gaze" of surveillance to judge or assess pupils and staff (Gillies, 2013).

The headteacher's practice of monitoring classroom teaching and learning every morning (as described in the above field note) might be understood as surveillance. Foucault's research in prisons concludes that surveillance (or even the perception of surveillance) effectively ensures norms or desirable behaviours (Foucault, 1975). In the educational context, Gillies applies this concept to critique how surveillance might influence teaching practice efficiency, as surveillance is an ongoing and constant process that can have a lasting impact on teacher performance. Gillies (2013) highlights how surveillance can become an essential 'tool' for education leaders to maintain control over school improvement. The teacher referred to in the above observation is accustomed to the headteacher visiting her classroom - she and the students are aware that the headteacher could monitor their classroom at any time, which, in turn, influences their conduct. For example, in the above field note, it is observed that students

and teachers remain focused on the learning and the lesson throughout the time of the headteacher's visit and ensure conformity to lesson planning requirements.

This monitoring may also lead teachers and students to self-discipline as they feel they are under surveillance. For Foucault, self-discipline is the process by which individuals regulate their behaviour. In Foucault's view, the perception of being subject to surveillance plays a role in shaping individual behaviour to activate certain behaviours. The power of surveillance (or the perception/anticipation of it) is closely tied to Foucault's idea of the '*Panopticon*'. The Panopticon is a type of prison designed by Jeremy Bentham (Gillies, 2013). Foucault introduces the panopticon as follows: "All that is needed, then, is to place a supervisor in a central tower and to shut up in each cell. One can observe from the tower, standing out precisely against the light, small captive shadows in the cells of the periphery" (Foucault, 1995, p. 200).

Through panopticon surveillance, all prisoners are monitored from a single point, creating the feeling that they are continuously viewed, which leads them to perform expected behaviours and discipline themselves. In a school context, this notion of the panopticon may encapsulate the regulation of teachers' and students' norms. In many schools, headteachers assess and monitor teachers to ensure they maintain the school schedule and follow training rules when teaching. Similarly, teachers monitor students in a broader panoptic sense, including observation of their classroom behaviour and interactions with teachers and peers. For example, the above observation showed that the students were engaged in classroom activities rather than chatting with peers or making noise. All responded to the headteacher's greeting with 'Good morning, sir'. Similarly, the teacher looks to the headteacher for permission to commence the lesson and adheres to her lesson plan, remaining focused on teaching (using proper teaching aids) and teaching following pre-primary classroom training protocols. In such a context, the headteacher might be understood to be exercising power by observing the classroom's practices and monitoring activities.

This exercise of disciplinary power gives the head teacher some control over the behaviour of teachers and students. This control is intended to facilitate good pupil outcomes supporting school improvement. It was observed that the headteacher involved himself in the lesson. The headteacher and students understand that he has the position of power to interrupt the class, permit teaching to commence and comment on students' work. Monitoring of classroom

teachers at work with their students thus exemplifies the exercise of disciplinary power, ensuring that teachers' conduct is appropriate, and students are attentive.

Foucault explained how the institutions, in the case of this research, the school, normalise behaviour through disciplinary instruments such as hierarchical observation, normalising judgement and the examination. In this research, monitoring classroom activities ensures that teachers follow training protocols and use teaching aids effectively, demonstrating compliance with expected professional standards. Feedback and evaluation, including comments such as 'good' and 'very good,' as well as visual incentives like drawing stars, promote adherence to expected norms. As Gillies (2013) notes, hierarchical observation through monitoring of classroom activities establishes norms within the school and exercises power in a way that encourages teachers and students to ensure the standards and regulations are meticulously followed.

Freie and Eppley (2014) note that exercising power within schools is common at the disciplinary level. They reflect that school leaders fully know their role in subjecting individuals to normalising judgements. Normalising judgements in schools are understood as the mechanism of power where norms and regulations are established, and both teachers and students are judged based on their adherence to these regulations and norms. For example, as observed in the field note above, teachers are required to prepare lesson plans, use teaching aids when delivering classroom teaching, and follow the classroom instructions provided by the training program. Similarly, students are expected to follow the teachers' instructions and behave accordingly, without making noise or displaying off-task behaviour. However, according to Foucault, power exists only through individuals' voluntary submission or resistance.

The following quotes from two parents who wanted to talk to me during a visit to School A speak to this reciprocal relationship between power and resistance (Foucault, 1982), illustrating how the headteacher's absence from monitoring the day-to-day life of the school and learning can enable or facilitate teachers to resist the exercise of power:

The parent commented that her child frequently informed her that his classroom teachers use their cell phones. She noted that teachers keep a close eye on the headteacher or any

rushing high official by staying near the door while speaking on their mobile phones. This is unfortunate. She reflected that she could not raise her voice because ‘they are our children's teachers’, but she shared it with the headteacher (School A Field Notes, 1 February 2023).

The other parent commented that when the headteacher consistently observes the teacher’s classroom, the teacher becomes alert and cordial in delivering the teaching and learning. She reflected that when the headteacher is not in the school, teachers will simply leave the classroom, talk over their mobile phones, or spend time chatting with their colleagues in the office room. She concluded that if the headteacher is not present in the school, she can see that the school is not functioning properly (School A Fieldnotes, 1 February 2023).

The above data hints at the teachers’ resistance to power. The above conversation can be examined via the lens of Foucault's theory of power resistance. According to Foucault (1978), resistance exists where there is power, and in the context of education, resistance and power are intertwined. For example, in the above the teacher uses a mobile device during classroom practice, rather than following administrative guidelines. By disregarding the school policies about mobile phone use openly, the teacher, in this instance, resists the power of school expectations and norms. These parent comments suggest that the teachers sometimes followed the rules set out by the school about mobile phone use. However, when individuals use their phones in class and believe they are not being monitored, they might be understood as exercising their resistance to power. There may be many reasons for mobile phone use during lessons that are not directly related to conscious acts of resistance (e.g. practical considerations/requirements). However, for these parents, the absence of a gaze of surveillance from the headteacher is viewed as resulting in some teachers’ flouting of school norms/expectations.

The following observation of two different teachers’ classroom teaching techniques, monitored by school A’s head teacher, further demonstrates how Foucault’s concept of power, particularly disciplinary power (enacted through surveillance), might be evident:

The headteacher of school A speaks individually in his office room with the two teachers monitored in the morning. He provides them with some feedback regarding their class for the day. He begins by speaking with the English teacher who sits across from him in a very

attentive manner, demonstrating steady eye contact and nodding her head to show her engagement. The headteacher says, “I am delighted to see your classroom instruction.” He commends her for using ideal classroom teaching strategies and excellent student performance. The headteacher begins a conversation with the Bangla teacher. She appears slightly tense but remains attentive, sitting with her hands clasped in front of her and making occasional eye contact. The headteacher starts by mentioning the education officer’s visit from the previous week. He explains that during her visit, the education officer observed that many of the students in class two were struggling to read their Bangla textbooks. In response, the headteacher provided instructions to improve classroom instruction, suggesting activities like exercise pair work, group work, and peer support. He also instructed her to follow the training guidelines (Bangla subject-based training) more closely which she received just two months before and remain active in the classroom, as some students at the back were not attentive during his observation. The headteacher thanked her before concluding the meeting. Ms. X stood, thanked him briefly, made eye contact, and left the office (School A Fieldnotes, 6 February 2023).

The above field notes might be interpreted as an example of disciplinary power as enacted through hierarchical observation; the headteacher’s monitoring of classroom activities establishes and reinforces norms within the school, enabling him to exercise power in a way that encourages teachers and students to follow the norms and expectations. Feedback is an example of Foucault’s disciplinary power, particularly in the practice of normalising judgment. For instance, the headteacher of school A provides instruction after observing the teachers’ classroom practices, which helps shape the teachers’ classroom practices. The positive feedback provided by the headteacher to the English teacher was constructed based on norms (such as using lesson plans, teaching aids and effective classroom teaching methods) that the teacher followed. The reinforcement encouraged her to continue those activities.

On the other hand, the Bangla teacher received corrective feedback that guided her further actions. Normalising judgment can be understood as an instrument for leaders to promote actions which might, in turn, lead to school improvement. For example, in the above observation, the headteacher provided corrective feedback to the Bangla teacher as she did not apply the knowledge received from training on effective classroom teaching. The headteacher reminded the teacher that teaching effectively involves breaking the class into pairs or small groups, as the lecturing method does not provide enough opportunities to engage all students.

Here the headteacher also reminded her that she had recently completed the training, so she should remember and apply the instructions she achieved. In the above field note, the headteacher's comments to both teachers reflect that certain actions are preferred for effective classroom teaching.

Furthermore, Foucault's notion of examination might shed light on the above observation. Here the headteacher has monitored classroom activities, and feedback sessions to the teachers might be interpreted as direct examinations where the headteacher reviews and assesses each teacher's actions and then provides positive and corrective feedback. Another observation in school A (described below) can also be explored with reference to Foucault's concept of hierarchical observation, normalising judgement and above all the practice of disciplinary power:

The headteacher is in the assembly class on the school field to monitor all students (pre-primary to class Five) assembly. Every student is very disciplined during the assembly. The headteacher delivers a short speech before finishing the assembly, emphasising the importance of punctuality, discipline, self-respect, school norms and good news for staff and students. In this session students are closely monitored they are with complete school uniforms are not (Fieldnote School A, February 7, 2023).

In the above observation, the headteacher monitored the assembly class which might be interpreted as hierarchical observation. Here, the headteacher ensures that the students follow the norms of specific routines and behaviours that exhibit disciplined behaviour, e.g. arriving on time and wearing the school uniform. This assembly class monitoring also reflects the dynamic relationship of power that influences the students' subjectivity by placing them within an institutional framework (normalising judgment). Here, the headteacher exercises power by controlling the students' behaviour and shaping the students' subjectivity - how they see themselves as learners, their attitude towards schoolteachers, and schools' norms, regulations and values (Freie and Eppley, 2014). It is observed that the headteacher's direct monitoring and repeated messages control the students' immediate behaviour. Even when he is not present in the school, the students are found to pick up the papers and keep them in the bins, water the school garden and stay disciplined while entering the classrooms and playing on the school grounds during the tiffin break.

A consistent observation among the head teachers across the various schools is their strong belief that monitoring plays a vital role in enhancing school improvement by ensuring quality teaching and learning in the classrooms. However, during the process of monitoring classroom activities, headteachers sometimes find that using they encounter strong resistance, despite their efforts towards normalising judgement, through the setting and reinforcing of school expectations and rules. As Foucault notes, power manifests and individuals may submit or resist. The headteacher of school B underscored this truth which is clearly evident from the following informal conversation and observations:

The headteacher of school B reported that she regularly monitored classroom teaching and learning. She commented that she walked through the corridor while teachers delivered classroom teaching. Sometimes she stood and monitored the action from the classroom window. On January 16, 2023, after monitoring, she returned to the office room to share her experiences with the teacher representative. She commented that Ms M (a teacher she considered to be unmotivated) was in class three's Bangla class and sitting on the chair delivering the lesson. She commented that the teacher saw her but acted like she did not care, staying seated and asking the students to copy from a book. The headteacher concluded that some students remained idle.

However, the headteacher again shared her view the next day, after finishing her monitoring of the classrooms, and shared the same view that Ms M was acting as before. This time only I was with her. I was curious to know about the classroom activities of other teachers. The headteacher replied they were performing well and following the training guidelines received from their subject-based training. I then asked why she had not asked Ms M to correct her teaching practice and follow the training guidelines. The HT explained that every Thursday, she meets to sit with the teachers to discuss the rules and regulations. I observed this as follows:

At 12.30 pm, all teachers gather in the teachers' office room. She addresses non-compliance with training norms, without singling out individuals. The HT starts her meeting emphasising that the teachers are here to serve the students effectively. She comments that teachers are paid for giving effective classroom teaching and learning to the students - that she has noticed a teacher not following the training norms during classroom practices. While speaking, the HT glares at MS M with obvious irritation. Her look at Ms. M makes it very clear to the other teachers what she means by her words. She

again instructs all teachers to use lesson plans and teaching aids during classroom sessions [observation conducted on 16 January 2023, School B teachers' room].

The above data indicates Headteacher B's exercise of disciplinary power through classroom monitoring, with a focus on ensuring the quality of teaching and learning. The headteacher is clear about her responsibility - that she is subject to DPE requirements to ensure the quality of classroom teaching and learning to make school improvements. To achieve this, she employs 'monitoring' techniques like the headteacher of School A that align with Foucault's concepts of disciplinary power (hierarchical observation, normalising judgement) and encounters resistance to her efforts to discipline Ms M towards expected norms of classroom behaviour. Ms M appears to reject norms and regulations (she has indicated her frustration over large classes, continuous classes without breaks, and a lower salary scale) and believes that whatever she is doing is sufficient.

However, headteacher B noted in a casual conversation that she was interested in Ms M's past experiences at other schools. So, she tried to speak with the previous two headteachers, who also said that Ms M frequently resisted school rules. On another occasion, it was observed that the headteacher once called Ms M to her office and suggested a transfer to another school. Ms M remained quiet during the meeting, but later expressed her frustration to her colleagues, stating that she would not change her teaching methods. Ms. M's resistance to norms was evident as she ignored the headteacher's presence and was determined when asked to consider a transfer to another school.

The above observation in School B demonstrates that the headteacher used monitoring as a form of hierarchical observation to ensure that the norms and regulations (as laid down in DPE training expectations) were followed (National Student Assessment 2022; Continuous Professional Development, 2019; Education Sector Plan for Bangladesh Fiscal Years 2020/21 – 2024/25, 2020). As Foucault reminds us, "surveillance functions permanently and mainly in silence (Foucault, 1977, p. 177). In School B, this often-included walking through the corridors or regular classroom visits by headteachers and education officers to observe teaching practices and how the students follow the instruction. However, as with the panopticon, even in the absence of direct observation the headteachers' actions (monitoring of classes in an

informal/unplanned way) can give both teachers and pupils the impression that they are subject to observation at any time.

The following observations and informal conversation in school C indicate that different approaches to monitoring were used by headteachers to sustain a focus on school improvement, a context where teachers and students felt highly accountable to 'desirable' norms:

The headteacher at school 'C' is in a meeting with the teacher's representative (TR) this morning at 10 am. The headteacher asks the TR to note the information: 1. observe students' school uniforms. The TR immediately replies that the majority of the students are appropriately dressed, but a small number are not. The headteacher then recommends that the class teachers note the reasons why those children are not wearing their school uniforms. Then she instructed the TR to write query no 2; all the class teachers for primary 2 and 3 need to provide a list of students who are not able to read Bangla and English fluently, at an age-appropriate level. For Primary 4 and 5, they need to provide a list of students who are unable to read English fluently, at an age-appropriate level. The headteacher then notes that this will be discussed in depth in the teachers' meeting on Thursday (15 January 2023).

It is Thursday afternoon. The headteacher of school C is sitting with the teachers in the teacher's room. This is a large room with two large L-shaped tables and 32 chairs surrounding them. The headteacher starts by asking to see the notes and says:

This is January. As the students will soon engage in the annual sports practice, teachers should focus on teaching them reading in Bangla and English during the first two periods. In the meantime, they should make a list of which students are not able to read and write effectively. This method should be applied in all classes until the annual sports are finished. The headteacher then changed her tone to a more authoritative one and stated, "Everyone should follow the classroom instructions to enhance students' learning; as you know, any time the education officers and the high officials from DPE can visit the school. It is a matter of respect that if any class's students cannot perform well, it could lead to different consequences. 'Then, she turned to TR and said, 'Please check if anybody has any issues regarding improving the classroom's performance that need action and let me know' (Fieldnote School C, 19 January 2023).

The above observations can be considered in the context of Foucault's surveillance, where authoritative power can normalise the behaviour of others without direct intervention as Freie and Eppley (2014, p.667) note, “the norms of the school and community setting allow the exercise of disciplinary power to be viewed as a normal or natural part of the way the institution of the school operates”. This can create a self-regulating system for the individuals being monitored – a sense of the panopticon referred to previously. In the previously mentioned setting, the headteacher of School C also monitored the teachers and students without physical engagement. For example, the headteacher establishes explicit expectations of teachers, guiding them to examine and develop students’ skills in writing and reading. By instructing teachers to focus on reading during the first two periods and making a list of students who are unable to learn the required learning.

Doing this the headteacher establishes a norm for the teachers that they are expected to meet. The headteacher established indirect monitoring, stating that education officers and high officials from DPE might monitor student progress at any moment. This fosters a sense of ongoing potential observation. This warning from the headteacher is an exercise of power that is intended to make the teachers feel as if they can be monitored at any time and so should become more diligent in their jobs to avoid negative consequences. In addition, the headteacher assigns the TR to keep an eye on student attendance, uniform details, and academic performance. As a result, a hierarchical structure is created in which the TR gathers ongoing data to support the monitoring system. The TR's involvement is important in ensuring that monitoring happens even in the absence of direct headteacher monitoring. Ultimately, by creating a setting in which teachers can self-regulate as a result of their actual effort to be observed, the headteacher’s strategy of applying power is effectively viewed through the lens of Foucault's surveillance, preserving a system of control without the need for continual physical monitoring.

According to Foucault (1995), discipline is a mechanism of power that targets individuals, aiming to shape and construct their norms and behaviour to ensure positive consequences in support of school improvement. In the above context, the headteacher of School C employed certain techniques to ensure stakeholder engagement. An example of this was evident in School C where the headteacher encouraged public gaze (from parents and other stakeholders) to influence the actions of the chairman of SMC. She organised various events and used social

media exposure (taking photos and posting on social media) to highlight the chairman's involvement in the community creating a form of visibility or surveillance. It was evident that the Chairman enjoyed the attention whilst also experiencing subtle pressure to continue supporting the school's improvement-related activities. A Foucauldian interpretation might suggest that the HT, in this case, enacted power in support of school improvement through public exposure which, in turn, encouraged self-regulation on the part of the SMC Chairman.

In an informal conversation, the headteacher of school C explained how she shared the school vision with the stakeholders and why it was important. She stated that to set up the school vision, she needed the involvement of the teacher staff because her school's vision was focused on enhancing the quality of learning. Without consulting with them, it is quite impossible to even set the target. She first recognizes the students' positions by class and subject with the help of the subject teacher. For example, she mentioned that if she works on Bengali learning in class one, she will look at expected learning outcomes like the learners learning the alphabet, and how to form words. To fulfil this vision, she arranged a meeting with the teachers and added that until March they would engage in child surveys, student admissions, annual sports and cultural programs. Every March she conducts a baseline survey to understand the students' position and according to this survey, she sets the activities that will help the students to reach the expected goal. After 3 months she again completes the baseline survey using the same sheet. She also mentioned some difficulties, she can only conduct the survey yearly two times, and at the end of the year, the teachers are engaged with a lot of paperwork given by the Education office.

However, the headteacher of school C found this action very effective as her teachers' staff is very carefully engaged. She added that every month; after attending a meeting with the Education officer, she arranges a staff meeting to review all the activities they did the previous month as well as to plan what they should do to continue for school improvement activities. She agreed that without engaging the teachers actively, it is quite impossible to fulfil the school vision. The headteacher of school C also mentioned that although her teacher is well-motivated, she still follows some techniques to keep them motivated. She gave an example of how she always keeps updated the SMC chairman about every step that she takes. Her SMC chairman is a highly educated person who has a genuine interest in enhancing education. The teachers always stay alert as they know the SMC chairman might observe the classroom to check on

students' learning outcomes. She also added that another positive aspect is that her school is frequently visited by education officers and higher authorities from the DPE. The teachers always feel that they are under surveillance, even though they are self-motivated.

The above findings indicate that the headteacher of School C shared her vision with the staff and SMC to achieve the best results for making school improvements. To accomplish this, she used Foucault's concept of disciplinary power including hierarchical observation, normalising judgement, and examination. These methods were utilised by the headteacher of School C separately and sometimes together. For instance, all the staff were informed that the student's learning outcomes could be observed at any time by the SMC chairman as well as the education officers. This surveillance indirectly motivated the teachers to perform their duties effectively. Additionally, parents were informed that their children would be examined through baseline surveys, motivating them to support their children's success. It was also observed that the headteacher exercised disciplinary power through normalising judgement by controlling the teacher staff, and students using established rules and norms to fulfil the school vision

7.5 Conclusion

This chapter uses Foucault's tools to examine the power exercised and experienced by three headteachers in Bangladeshi government primary schools when implementing school improvement initiatives. It explores headteachers' practices as they work with teachers and stakeholders to ensure school improvement. Foucault's ideas allow for the investigation of subjectivity and ethics, governmentality, and disciplinary power as observed in these schools as their headteachers seek to drive forward school improvement.

Chapter 8: Challenges and Opportunities for Headteachers when Leading School Improvement Initiatives

8.1 Introduction

This chapter examines headteachers' challenges and opportunities in leading school improvement initiatives, guided by research question 3 (see chapter 1). This study's findings are presented and discussed thematically to provide a clear and comprehensive understanding. This chapter is structured within two sections: challenges and opportunities. The first section on challenges, includes five sub-themes. The first sub-theme identifies teachers' lack of motivation as the primary challenge for headteachers in driving school improvement. The second sub-theme explores how parents' financial limitations directly or indirectly affect students' performance, thereby impacting headteachers in leading school improvement efforts. The third sub-theme highlights a common challenge in Bangladeshi primary schools- the inconsistent attendance of SMC members in meetings and school improvement activities. The fourth sub-theme indicated that a lack of parental support frustrated the headteachers as they faced challenges in achieving school improvement goals. The fifth subtheme highlights headteachers' significant challenges in primary schools dealing with education officers. Their misuse of authority undermined the purpose of primary education and made it highly challenging for head teachers to improve the schools.

The second section, Opportunities, includes three sub-themes. The first sub-theme (section 8.3.1) focuses on headteachers' resilience, commitment, and effective leadership, which are crucial in seizing opportunities to enhance their schools. The second sub-theme (section 8.3.2) explains how a shared school vision enables headteachers to generate opportunities for school improvement. Finally, section 8.3.3 underscores the importance of increased mentoring by headteachers in fostering staff accountability and dedication, ultimately creating opportunities for achieving teaching and learning goals in the classroom. Each sub-theme discussed data concerning the existing literature. By synthesising these issues thematically, this chapter offers detailed explorations of headteachers' challenges and opportunities in leading school improvement initiatives. These findings are also based on informal conversations, document reviews and observations conducted with key stakeholders from three primary schools.

8.2. Challenges for headteachers when leading school improvement initiatives

8.2.1 Teachers' motivation/demotivation and school improvement

Conversations with the stakeholders, especially headteachers, parents, SMC members and education officers, highlighted that teachers' motivation or de-motivation is the key factor for headteachers in leading school improvement. For example, the headteacher of School A made it abundantly clear that he believed motivated teachers were essential to school improvement and had a significant impact on the prospects of students in public primary schools. The following observation at school A illustrated the challenges for school improvement posed by demotivated teachers, as discussed by guest headteachers who attended the celebration of the annual sports and prize-giving ceremony (February 23, 2023):

The discussion started informally as five headteachers gathered in school A's headteacher's office room. They began talking about their schools' current activities. Gradually, the conversation shifted to the issues they addressed, the challenge of demotivated teachers. Headteacher 1 introduced the growing concern about teachers' morale, noting that some teachers seemed now to care less about engaging the students in classroom teaching. Other headteachers agreed with this concern, sharing their experiences in this regard. Headteacher 2 shared that in his school, every day, most teachers, aside from two or three, had to be reminded daily to attend classes. He voiced his concern about the class bell ringing, yet those teachers often stayed away from their classrooms, requiring his intervention. This situation led to ongoing frustration between him and the teachers, who reacted negatively when he reminded them of their duties.

Headteacher 2 added that this scenario was common across many primary schools, emphasising that only 20 to 30 per cent of teachers were self-motivated. He continued by giving another example that some teachers were sitting in their chairs and passing the time, especially when the headteacher was not in school or engaging in paperwork in the office. Headteacher 3 contributed to the discussion, explaining that when the headteacher compelled teachers to enter the classroom, they tended to sit idly, assigning students writing tasks or conversing with colleagues in corridors. They would only pay attention to teaching if they noticed the headteacher arriving. The Headteacher of School A agreed with the point and shared his opinion by saying that a similar issue occurred in his school when he was not present. However, in such behaviours, parents were always informed by the students, and in turn, some parents informed him and the chairman of the school managing committee.

Headteacher 4 participated in the conversation by saying that teachers at primary schools lack dedication and motivation, which is why they lack respect from the public. However, Headteacher A disagreed with this comment, arguing that generalising the issue was unfair. He stated that many dedicated teachers continuously worked hard, following headteachers' instructions, to improve their school. Headteacher 4 further noted that they do not use standard teaching methods, though they have training to teach using PowerPoint slides as well as related teaching aids. The headteacher of School A then added that it was very sad that teachers mostly enjoyed training not to learn a teaching strategy but for financial benefit.

The discussion ended with the headteachers of School A expressing a common concern: unmotivated teachers are a nationwide issue. The primary reasons include insufficient breaks due to a teacher shortage, low salaries, and a social perception of teaching in primary schools as a low-status profession. He then highlighted the responsibility of headteachers to implement effective leadership strategies aimed at motivating teachers, as their motivation is crucial for enhancing school performance.

The above observations highlight significant challenges faced by the headteachers of Bangladeshi Government primary schools in addressing demotivated teachers, which is crucial in promoting school improvement. The headteacher of School A, along with his four colleagues, shared their concerns about teachers not engaging the students in the classroom instruction. They reflected that teachers' demotivation hampers the students' classroom teaching and learning experience and, ultimately, school improvement. These findings are congruent with Quadir's (2021) research, which investigated teaching influences on students' perceptions of learning motivation in Bangladeshi English as a foreign language. This study revealed that teachers in the classroom were less active in explaining the lessons or addressing student enquiries. They did not engage students in pair or group activities when delivering classroom instruction. They only paid attention to the proficient students in class, making those disadvantaged feel neglected.

The observation also revealed that teachers needed to be reminded to enter the classrooms, even after the bell rang for classroom teaching. It suggests that teachers' lack of self-motivation hinders them from conducting effective norms while teaching in the classroom. They stay in the classroom but disengage from teaching and learning, reflecting a broader issue of

professional responsibilities. The observation revealed that teachers lack ethical concerns as they are more interested in attending the training for financial satisfaction than in pedagogical development. It highlights teachers' lack of professional commitment and pedagogical responsibilities. This shows that teachers engage in unethical behaviour, especially when prioritising personal and financial interests rather than professional commitment. This also supports research by Choe et al. (2013), Sommers (2013) and Prodhan (2016) reflected considerable issues since Bangladeshi teachers were more interested in private tutoring, which emphasised personal and financial interests rather than professional devotion.

These observations also revealed that teachers only kept them busy to watch if the headteachers arrived; however, students also observed the teachers' immoral activities and reported them to their parents. Ultimately, parents reported this activity to the headteacher or the members of the SMC. The field note, thus, highlights that teachers' immoral activities reflect public disrespect towards them. In the above observation, the headteacher of School A disclosed a truth that obstructs the advancement of primary education: the shortage of teachers. This shortage results in inadequate breaks for teachers, forcing them to continue teaching in the classroom, which diminishes the effectiveness of their instruction. Furthermore, teachers in government primary schools in Bangladesh are underpaid, treating them as third-class citizens in terms of social status. This situation leads to frustration, especially since many have advanced university degrees. This field note aligns with Moyer's (2014) study, which revealed that primary schools in Bangladesh face many challenges, including insufficient educational resources and low salaries for government primary school teachers. Datta and Roy (2024) also revealed that the absence of an appropriate classroom environment, combined with a large student population and limited time, forces teachers in Bangladesh to continue with a teacher-centred instructional strategy. This is due to the government-prescribed syllabus that affords them no flexibility to deviate from the curriculum to enhance their students' educational experience. Consequently, these challenges adversely affect teachers' behaviour and motivation within the classroom.

While sitting in the School A headteacher's office, I observed an unplanned meeting held with the headteacher, SMC chairman, and two parents (3 April 2023):

The parents came along with the SMC chairman to claim that a teacher who taught science in class three, according to them, was not fulfilling classroom responsibilities. One parent claimed that the teacher, Ms Ru, did not mark the Science homework properly. This parent presented her child's Science copy as evidence and showed the headteacher that the class teacher's signature was missing from the last three days' homework. This parent was informed by her child's house tutor, who claimed that Science was not being taught properly in the class. The headteacher listened carefully to the parents and assured them he would address the issue. Furthermore, he promised to ensure teachers' pay attention to classroom instruction and check students' homework. After getting reassured, both parents thanked the headteacher and the chairman before leaving the office.

After the parents left, the headteacher and the chairman continued their conversation. The chairman suggested speaking to the teacher immediately, but the headteacher preferred to handle the issue privately, allowing the teacher to get self-motivated. The chairman suggested that the headteacher monitor teachers' activities more carefully and advised engaging one SMC member to assist the headteacher by regularly observing the teachers' activities. The meeting concluded with the agreement that the headteacher would follow his advice. After the departure of the SMC chairman, the headteacher asked the office assistant to call the class three Science teacher, Ms Ru. The follow-up meeting, as observed (3 April 2023):

The headteacher offered her tea while beginning the conversation. The tone was very supportive, commenting on the teacher's overall contribution while mentioning the issue raised by the parents. After mentioning the concerns, the headteacher paused and gave her space to reply. The teacher's expression- initially, a surprise crossed her face – eyes widened, but very quickly, she composed herself. She admitted that not checking students' homework copies might have been a mistake. However, she would take it with more care. At the same time, she emphasised that the number of students in the classroom often made it challenging to check all students' copies within the limited allocated time.

The headteacher emphasised the challenge, acknowledging that it was a common issue for all primary schools where one teacher often needed to manage 45 to 50 students in a classroom or even more in some cases. To address this concern, the headteacher suggested using peer support by engaging advanced learners to check the copy, and the teacher could oversee the process by following the whole class. To ensure the expected progress, the headteacher scheduled a follow-up meeting next week to discuss if additional support

might be needed to enhance Science teaching and learning. Ms Ru agreed to follow the instructions and commit to improving before leaving the office.

The above observations highlight teachers' lack of classroom responsibility, making parents concerned about their children's education. Teachers continuously ignore observing the homework copy, which reflects teachers' lack of professional commitment and pedagogical responsibility. This finding also aligns with Quadir's (2014) study on Bangladesh, English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students' teaching factor, which found that teachers assign much homework without providing feedback. However, the above data also revealed the key challenges, including big class sizes and limited class hours, making the class teacher unable to check all students' copies. Salam (2015) conducted a study investigating the quality of teaching and learning in Bangladesh's public and private schools. The study revealed that large class sizes make it difficult for teachers in government primary schools to provide effective instruction. However, the above field notes highlighted the key dynamics of the head teacher's leadership role in navigating challenges created by the teachers and the supportive role in managing the stakeholders to address classroom teaching and learning challenges. The meeting between the headteacher, parents, and the SMC chairman underscores the importance of the headteacher and parental engagement for maintaining a consistent standard of classroom instruction by the teacher.

In the follow-up meeting with the science teacher, Ms Ru, the data revealed that the headteacher's supportive leadership approach, giving the teacher suggestions using peer support to navigate common classroom challenges (large class size), helps the teacher conduct themselves to enhance classroom engagement.

However, a different scenario was observed in School B. The headteacher of School B had to cope with a teacher, Mr K, who was assigned to the pre-primary classroom. He was not using the instructional tools and the specific communication for the pre-primary students effectively, despite being given instructions several times by the head teacher. To navigate the situation, the headteacher engaged another competent female teacher to encourage the male teacher to follow her instructions to benefit the students. Apart from this issue, school B faced severe teacher demotivation challenges, especially one female teacher who often criticised the headteacher. The observation was held in school B's teachers' room. Two teachers were sitting there as it was their break time. The bell rang to start the class, and one teacher left for the

classroom, but another female teacher (Ms M) remained sitting at her desk rather than entering the classroom (15 January 2023). The same teacher was observed another day in school B (18 January 2023):

Ms M abruptly ended the session around 10.30 am before the actual time of ending the morning shift. The first shift (pre-primary, class one, and class two) should be completed by 11 a.m. However, because of the early termination, one parent came to the school and said that his son, who was in class one, was not at home. When the headteacher questioned the female teacher about when she had ended the class, she replied that it was 10.30 a.m. It was also unexpected that the female teacher did not feel bad about it. The headteacher was worried since one of the students had gone missing. Fortunately, at 11.30 a.m., the missing student's parents called to say their son was coming home.

In an informal conversation, the head teacher at School B demonstrated her reaction after this event. She shared that this unmotivated teacher always arrived late to school and departed early, even though she was not serious about entering the classroom (also observed by the researcher). She continued saying that this teacher spoiled the school environment. Every day she (Ms M) created an issue and the whole day her (headteacher) needed to struggle with it. She kept quiet if the headteacher asked her to apply to transfer from her school. She did not show any manner of talking with the headteacher or other colleagues. She was very rude to the students and often gave them physical punishment.

The above field notes highlight the headteacher's challenges, mainly her frustration with this teacher's negligence of classroom conduct, lack of punctuality, and disregard for being active in classroom instruction. It also reflects the challenging environment of school B. Mr K demonstrates ineffectiveness in not using the instructional tools and the specific communication for pre-primary classroom teaching. On the other hand, Ms M showed the highest resistance by not applying classroom norms. Students in School B experienced corporal punishment by Ms M. Several research revealed that using corporal punishment had a long history among teachers in Bangladesh (Sommers, 2011; Malak, Sharma, and Deppeler, 2015; Sultana, Reza, and Bromfield, 2019). Though the Ministry of Education and the country's Supreme Court banned corporal punishment on January 13, 2011, newspapers and research revealed that corporate punishment is still used in Bangladeshi schools (Parvin, 2014).

However, School B's headteacher remained silent regarding teacher misconduct to the education officer and the assistant education officer instead of taking the initiative. The headteacher shared that despite complaining several times, no actions happened; their (TEO and ATEO) attitude seemed to be that she (i.e., headteacher) was the one responsible for this teacher's demotivation. The corporal punishment by Ms M and Mr K is also evident in a document, specifically an observation book dated 12.04.2022, created by the assistant education officer at School B. He noted that he received a complaint that Ms M and Mr K had applied corporal punishment to the students and that they were warned not to repeat this behaviour.

Furthermore, the headteacher should also exercise caution regarding this matter. However, the headteacher stated that the assistant education officer merely commented on this in the observation book rather than taking any initiative or issuing a written official notice. Watto et al. (2022) discovered that teachers' attitudes towards students, particularly physical punishment, were critical issues in Pakistan. Additionally, a significant obstacle to improving classroom instruction in rural areas was the absence of teachers. It is evident from observations and conversations with three school headteachers that education officers do not frequently visit the schools to improve educational quality. If the headteachers encounter problems regarding teachers' demotivation, they do not care to resolve them.

In an informal conversation, the headteacher of School C stated that she did not have demotivated teachers. She reflected that teachers are dissatisfied with teaching 6 or 7 classes every day, whilst in some classrooms, there are more than fifty students, and in classes six, seven, and eight, there are around sixty to seventy attendees. She concluded that, in this context, teachers do their best to arrive on time in the classroom. However, like other schools, student learning abilities are inadequate. She commented that she cannot expect the teachers to teach every student due to the large size of the classroom. They do not get enough time off. The school is large. As a result, one or two teachers are always on leave or in training. Thus, those classes must be covered by another teacher. They are so constantly exhausted. She said that she cannot tell them they are demotivated.

She also shared a concern that she is aware that the teachers use cell phones in the classroom, but she just ignored it. Staying on social media while in class is a prevalent issue among

teachers. Furthermore, when she advised them that both teachers and students should be more involved in the classroom, they invariably responded with the excuse that since they were underpaid, they should not put in more effort. Since they frequently complain, the headteacher said she did not want to worsen the situation. She was happy as she did not need to ask them to go to the class. However, she was not fully happy with the students' performance.

The fieldnote from School C reveals that the headteacher compromised the situation to keep the school environment from deteriorating. The field notes show that classroom teaching and learning are difficult due to large class sizes and a shortage of teachers. Despite their commitment to punctuality, teachers have been observed using social media in the classroom. The head teacher demonstrated compromise by observing that teachers were teaching nonstop since they had to cover other teachers' lessons while others were on leave or undergoing training. The headteacher stated that the students' performance was unsatisfactory, and she highlighted that the main reason was the large class size. Several studies (Milon, 2016; Masoom and Siddik, 2024; Ahmed, Adhikary, and Rahaman, 2024) identified large classroom sizes as a significant challenge for ensuring quality teaching and learning, citing several issues such as engaging students in classroom learning, assessing their knowledge, and providing feedback. Furthermore, Moghal, Kazi, and Bukhari (2019) note that teachers require significant time to engage students' attention in a large classroom, making it difficult to complete regular classroom activities on time.

8.2.2 Parents' Financial Difficulties and School Improvement

Ethnographic observation and informal conversations with the headteachers in this study revealed that low-income parents prefer to enrol their children in government primary schools. However, their low income also affects school attendance. In the office of Headteacher A on 29 April 2023, the headteacher, Ms N, Ms K, and Ms Ru were present for a meeting:

Three teachers (Ms N, Ms K, and Ms Ru) sit in the headteacher's office. The headteacher is looking at some documents with full concentration. Ms N is ready to write the notes and just waits for the headteacher's directions. The headteacher closes the documents and then turns to Ms N, instructing her to list the students who enrolled last year but did not attend school in January and February this year.

Ms K refers to the home visit form, reporting that she conducted two home visits for students in January. One student, Poly, in primary 2, left the area and returned to her village

as her parents lost their jobs during the COVID-19 pandemic. The headteacher asked Ms K if she had called them over the phone. Ms K explained that she attempted to contact Poly's parents' mobile, but the mobile was unreachable. Ms K then mentions another student, Raza, promoted to primary four this year, but started working with his mother at a small tea shop to support their family financially. Ms K noted that Raza had a 2-year-old sister, and although Raza had not wholly left school, he frequently missed classes. This teacher also mentioned that she had talked with Raza's mother, who expressed her intention to try her best to ensure her son would attend school. Unfortunately, Raza continued to be absent from school. Ms K also mentioned that Raza attended school only once last week; the previous week, he was present for two days. She also noted that Raza was very weak in reading and writing.

The headteacher then turned to Ms Ru and requested an update on the absence list of her classes. Ms Ru reported that two students had relocated to her class as their parents changed their jobs. However, both parents informed us that they had arranged for their admission to the new area's primary schools. However, one student, Maria, frequently missed school in January and February. Ms Ru explained that she visited Maria's residence last week and spoke with her mother. Maria's mother revealed that Maria's father had left them, and she was struggling to provide food for her children. She added that Maria needed to take care of her younger siblings. Ms Ru reflected that, despite this challenge, the parent was determined to ensure Maria resumed regular schooling soon. Ms Ru expressed sympathy when discussing Maria's vulnerable situation, noting that Maria was an active learner but could not attend regular classes due to a family crisis. The headteacher also expressed sadness upon hearing about student Maria's family situation and expressed his intention to visit Maria's parent soon, along with the SMC chairman.

Ms N diligently recorded all the information Ms K and Ms Ru provided and handed it to the headteacher before leaving the room.

This observation highlights the substantial obstacles that certain Bangladeshi families encounter in ensuring their children receive an education, including familial, financial, and practical barriers. The field notes reveal that the parents' fragile financial status prompted students to leave school and migrate to the village; the COVID-19 outbreak worsened the situation by causing them to lose their jobs. The teachers faced difficulties as they could not contact the parents and students because their mobile phones were unreachable.

The observation also demonstrated that their parents' financial struggles severely impacted the children's regular attendance at school because they had to look after their younger siblings. Due to his frequent absences from class, the student's reading and writing abilities continued to deteriorate, which made things challenging for the teachers. The field notes also show that poor parents regularly relocate for new employment opportunities. Sommers (2013) carried out an ethnographic study to investigate the poorest people's access, choices, and participation in Bangladeshi rural primary education and found that the earning members of poor families are often forced to migrate to different locations searching for work, which creates unsettling situations for children's education as was the case for Student Poly and the other two students in the above observation. Furthermore, the teachers and headteacher discuss the inevitable impact of non-attendance on Child Maria and Raza and the practical requirement for looking after younger siblings, who acknowledge the vulnerability of these families' circumstances.

The 2021 Annual Sector Performance Report (ASPR) highlighted that parental education and socio-economic status are significant risk factors for primary school children dropping out. This circumstance has resulted in a rise in child labour, as parents enlist their children in income-producing tasks to help support their families (Directorate of Primary Education, 2022). According to the International Labour Organisation (ILO), 17% of individuals who were employed prior to the COVID-19 pandemic have stopped working, and 42% have faced a decrease in their earnings. Consequently, this has caused more students to drop out of school, with some being forced to take on other work (Directorate of Primary Education, 2022).

The above field notes resonate with the researcher's other observations with some parents and the headteacher of School A. When the headteacher enquired about one student's absence from the neighbour's family, one parent of a pre-primary student who attended school every day explained that two families in her residential neighbourhood had left owing to financial concerns. She also mentioned the high cost of daily essentials, which made it difficult for low-income families to live. Another parent claimed that both parents had to work in factories or elsewhere to pay the rent and buy food, so the older child was frequently forced to take care of the siblings rather than go to school. This assertion was also consistent with an observation made in Headteacher A's office (April 4, 2023) during a discussion between the headteacher and the SMC chairman of school A:

The Headteacher of school A and the chairman are discussing the current school challenges. The headteacher mentions to the chairman that a common issue in primary schools across Bangladesh is the challenge posed by low-income parents. He reflects that many parents work hard all day long, returning home exhausted and preoccupied with cooking, leaving them with little time to monitor their children's academic progress. He notes that some parents even face difficulties buying basic school supplies such as notebooks and pens, and many cannot provide lunch boxes for their children. In response to the SMC chairman's query about government stipends, the headteacher doubts the funds are sufficient, noting that some parents spent this fund to buy their daily necessities. The headteacher comments that most students cannot concentrate on their studies with an empty stomach. They both looked very sad while they were discussing the financial difficulties of the student's parents.

The above fieldnote highlights the impact of parents' financial limitations on school improvement efforts. It sheds light on the challenging situations faced by many low-income families in primary education families across Bangladesh, drawing attention to how parents may prioritise their everyday struggles over their children's education. It is disheartening to observe that some parents struggle to provide for their children's lunch, notebooks, and pencils, among other essential school necessities. The reflections of the headteacher and SMC Chairman echo the study conducted by Sarker, Wu, and Hossin (2019), which indicated that, due to financial difficulties, most parents find it challenging to pay for their daily necessities, which leads their children to absences and ultimately drop out of school. The headteacher was concerned about the insufficient current government stipend offered to students, as evidenced by the Primary Education Stipend Project Implementation Operation Manual 2021 (Revised), which provides a monthly stipend of Tk. 75 BDT (0.62 US Dollars) for each pre-primary student, 150 BDT (1.23 US Dollars) for primary one to primary five, and 200 BDT (1.64 US Dollars) for primary six to primary eight (Directorate of Primary Education, 2023).

However, the primary education stipend project only allows two children per family to receive the stipend. While discussing the low socioeconomic status of the parents, the headteacher of School A commented that the government's inadequate stipend cannot meet students' requirements to survive in the school. School B's headteacher identified financial pressures on pupil attendance that directly impact school improvement. During an informal conversation,

she expressed frustration over enhancing students' reading and writing skills at the beginning of each school year because many students were irregular attendees. She noted that, as both parents were busy earning money, many students needed to care for their younger siblings, help with household work and work with parents in their shop. She attributed this lack of commitment to study to the students' low-income backgrounds, reflecting that they do not prioritise continuing study. She also mentioned that every month, teachers must complete at least one home visit and select students who are absent for more than three days. She noted that sometimes teachers visit the homes of students who are weak in learning. However, the reason parents give to explain absence is mainly fever and cough due to a lack of adequate nutrition. Headteacher B remarked that since these families struggled with poverty, education was not their priority. The following observation, made at the School B office (January 30, 2023), involving two teachers, including TR, provides additional insight:

The headteacher and two other teachers reviewed the home visit file and handed me some documents to read. The headteacher explained that they shed light on why students were frequently absent from school. Reading through the 20 home visits form, I discovered that 13 students were absent due to a common cold or cold flu, three had visited their grandparents, two had relocated, and two were engaged with household work to help the mother, primarily looking after the younger siblings. The head teacher expressed concern about the students attending school without having breakfast. She wishes schools could provide them with complimentary breakfast, noting the positive impact of the World Food Program's (WFP) nutritious biscuits before the COVID-19 pandemic.

This observation from School B's home visit report (documents) highlights the significant challenges primary schools face in Bangladesh due to parents' financial limitations. After reviewing all the home visit findings, the head teacher at School B noted that the primary reason for student absenteeism is the lack of nutrition, which was directly linked to the financial limitations of the parents. According to the headteacher, most students suffer from the flu, which is common because students do not get sufficient nutritious food. Attending school without having breakfast often leaves them tired and inclined to illness. These findings align with research by Cameron (2011), who explored primary schools in urban Dhaka's slums. He found that parents faced significant socioeconomic challenges that hindered their ability to send their children to school. Masoom and Siddik (2024) found that poverty adversely impacts

children's health by creating nutrition issues, affecting their capacity to concentrate on their studies and limiting their academic success.

Additionally, the field notes highlighted the headteacher's worries about providing a complimentary breakfast for students, as this could enhance their health and facilitate effective classroom participation. In response to these concerns, the Bangladesh Government implemented various initiatives, such as the National School Feeding policy and student stipends. The collaboration with the United Nations World Food Programme (WFP) has notably positively impacted student enrolment and attendance since 2011 (Adams et al., 2017; Ahmed, 2022). Unfortunately, this program was halted with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The field notes mentioned above are consistent with the home visit report from school C. According to the headteacher at school C, many children come from very low-income families. During a review of the December 2022 home visit file, it was noted that out of 19 home visit forms, twelve students were absent from the exam due to illness, three students had moved to their village, two were unable to attend due to their family crisis and two were identified as struggling learners, leading to resistance to attending school. In an informal conversation, the headteacher of school C explained that poverty is the main reason for students' absence, as low-income parents struggle to provide adequate food for their children. Headteacher C stated the same as Headteacher B, that many students came to school without bringing their lunchboxes. They had to spend a long time on an empty stomach. It caused them to get tired and sick quickly.

During an informal conversation, the SMS chairman of School C expressed that rising price and high rents made it difficult for low-income families to create a suitable study environment for their children. He noted that many of these families lived in a single bedroom with two or three children, often sharing the space with their parents. They lacked tables, chairs, or proper seating for their children to read. The above field notes emphasise how parents' financial constraints directly or indirectly impact pupils' academic achievement, which affects efforts to reform schools. As evidenced by the field notes, low-income families regularly relocate from one location to another in pursuit of employment. Their social status makes it difficult for them to be concerned about their children's education. This lack of awareness, mainly due to

financial limitations, causes their children to be often absent and sometimes drop out. Thus, this research's findings are consistent with the existing study (Sommers, 2013).

8.2.3 Complexities of School Management Committees

The observation and informal conversation from three schools' headteachers highlight that if the members of the school managing committee (SMC) are proactive and have a good relationship with the headteacher, they can have an impact on school improvement. However, data from the observation reveal that some SMC members struggled to balance their personal and SMC-related work. Consequently, they were frequently absent from meetings. In an informal conversation, the head teacher at School A stated that the chairman of the SMC was highly active at his school, but most of the members were unaware of their responsibilities. This also involves observing a school meeting in the School A headteacher's office with the headteacher, the SMC, two SMC members and the Teacher Representative (TR). The observation is as follows:

The school office has two large windows with blue curtains that allow enough natural light to enter the room. A prominent board displaying teachers' names, student numbers, and other information serves as the focal point. Ten chairs surround a large glass table. The discussion, accompanied by tea, focuses on today's topics presented by TR, Ms N. Cookies and fruits are set on the table. The main agenda includes organising this month's annual sports and inter-primary sports competition, along with classroom decoration. They discuss budgeting for students' annual sports prizes and other required expenses. The meeting is centred around the Headteacher pointing out issues, and the chairman concluding with possible solutions. The other two members mostly listened (School A Fieldnotes, 6 February 2023)

Following the observation, I inquired with the headteacher about the absence of other members of the managing committee. The headteacher stated that it is a typical problem in primary schools to have all eleven SMC members present at the meeting. He stated his viewpoint, adding that few SMC members with political backgrounds are too busy to attend the meeting, yet choose to remain on the committee without actively participating. He also mentioned that members from the parents' group are frequently preoccupied with their work, making it difficult to attend the meeting. In addition, this lack of engagement hinders school improvement

initiatives; conversely, to fulfil the meeting quorum, the headteacher needs to send someone to the SMC member's home for signatures.

The above observation and informal conversation demonstrate the headteacher's significant challenges in involving SMC members in school improvement activities. It was observed that only four SMC members were present at the meeting out of the eleven members. The field notes reveal that most SMC members, except the chairman, were unaware of their roles. The field note also reveals that some members from political backgrounds and parent categories were hardly present at the meeting. That deters the headteachers from navigating various school improvement activities. This field note aligns with the study by Al Mamun (2014), which investigated SMCs' role in improving the administration of Bangladeshi primary schools. This study found that most SMC members in primary schools in Bangladesh lack a clear understanding of their roles and responsibilities, and many schools do not frequently hold SMC meetings. The results also showed that primary school SMCs in Bangladesh have great potential to enhance primary school governance; however, SMCs in rural areas are not operating effectively.

The above informal conversation also highlights that following the SMC meeting, the headteacher sent them (absent SMC members) the meeting regulation copy to collect their signatures, or they might come after the meeting whenever they were available to sign. According to the Bangladesh Government Primary School Management Committee Formation, 2.9, if any member missed three consecutive meetings without the written consent of the SMC chairman, his or her membership would be terminated. That was why the headteacher sometimes, to avoid cancelling the membership, managed the members' signatures (even if they were not present at the meeting). The SMC committee's constitution states that the meeting must take place on any day of the last week of each English month following the completion of class or on a holiday [Documents; Bangladesh Government Primary School Management Committee Formation; Section 2.13]. However, research found SMC meetings held during school time before finishing the class [Documents; School A, B, C SMC meeting book]. There are eleven members of SMC, including the chairman. The quorum is complete if six members attend the SMC meeting [Bangladesh Government Primary School Management Committee Formation; Section 2.14]. However, the data suggested that the quorum was hardly complete.

However, in another informal conversation, the head teacher at School B stated that the SMC in her school was not functioning correctly. She added that most of the time, only the SMC's chairman and vice chairman were involved in the school management committee meeting, while the other members, particularly the parents' group and the high school representative, mainly remained absent. In addition, she stated that SMC's consistent attendance might help to improve teachers' classroom teaching, learning and decision-making for school improvement efforts such as securing school funds.

The above informal discussion shows that the head teacher faces various difficulties because the SMC members are not actively involved in school improvement initiatives. The headteacher displayed that only the chairman and vice chairman participated in the school meeting, while the other members were disengaged from the school improvement plan. She states that she would prefer for SMC to play a significant role in assisting school principals with improvement concerns such as decision-making, excellent classroom teaching and learning, and funding. However, these field notes are consistent with the existing literature's findings by Saha (2023), who investigated the management of Primary Education in Bangladesh, emphasising the role of Upazila Education Officers in improving quality primary education and identified significant challenges, including SMC members' inactiveness. The researcher observed that most school SMC members do not fulfil their responsibilities according to government regulations. The findings revealed that every school has SMC, but the members are not engaging well as they are unaware of their roles and responsibilities.

In another informal conversation, the headteacher of School C stated that with the help of active SMC members, she managed to involve the community in fundraising regarding cleaning and other expenses. Furthermore, the headteacher of school C stated that only 50% of members were active and curious to attend committee meetings, as observed below:

It was a monthly SMC meeting at the school's headteacher's office. The meeting consisted of the headteacher of school C, the SMC chairman, the vice chairman, Ms Lily and the TR, Ms L. The discussion mainly revolved around various issues, with a notable emphasis on the upcoming 21 February (International Mother Language Day) celebration. Ms L represented the issues by reading the agenda, and other participants attended to discuss details. Along with focusing on school reform issues, the conversation often touches on

pertinent national politics. Regardless of the friendly environment, it proved beneficial for the headteacher to address her concerns and find resolutions. However, the decision-making role highlights the SMC chairman's predominant role in leading the meeting (School C Fieldnotes, 2 January 2023).

The above observation was consistent with the SMC meetings at the other two schools. Only four SMC members attended the meeting out of the eleven members. The field notes also made clear that the SMC chairman made the decision, which is in line with the decisions made at the meetings of the other two schools.

However, some interesting information regarding the inconsistent attendance of SMC members was revealed by the Assistant District Education Officer (ADPEO), Mr T and the Thana Education Officer (TEO) of schools B and C, Ms Z, while visiting the School C pre-primary classrooms. In an informal conversation, the ADPEO stated that some primary school headteachers struggled to arrange SMC meetings as most of the members of the SMC, apart from the chairman, do not feel interested in participating in the meetings. Ms Z exposed the possible evidence behind the activity of the chairman and the inactivity of other members, commenting that when making financial transactions such as SLIP fund disbursement, the chairman of the SMC and the headteacher must both provide their written approval, and the chairman needs to sign the teachers' salary sheet. As a result, the headteacher consistently fostered a positive relationship with the chairman of the managing committee. However, she concluded that because most of the SMC members (who were often parents) were from low-income backgrounds, lacking in education, and sometimes illiterate, the headteacher tended to avoid discussing school improvement matters with them. In the above informal conversation, both education officers highlighted that the members of the SMC committee, apart from the chairman, demonstrate a lack of interest in participating in meetings and school improvement initiatives. The reason behind their inconsistent attendance, as stated by the TEO, is that the headteacher only favours the chairman, as he can disburse funds.

The field notes of this study show that in all three schools, most SMC members did not participate in scheduled meetings, and that the SMC chairman was frequently the only SMC member who consistently participated in school improvement initiatives. This is also consistent with the study conducted by Islam and Helal (2017), who examined governance in Bangladeshi

primary schools by reviewing the National Education Policy—2010 (the most recent education policy). They found that this education policy allows School Management Committee (SMC) members to get involved in the school's development and supervise the work of headteachers and other teachers. However, although the policy states that the SMC members should prepare the annual evaluation report for headteachers, it lacks a legal framework to participate in school improvement initiatives—such as rules, regulations, and jurisdiction—for the SMC. Consequently, many SMC members do not actively monitor or oversee school activities. Their lack of initiative includes social recognition, the unawareness of their roles and responsibilities, and inadequate training. Most SMC members seldom visit the schools or hold meetings. Furthermore, many SMC members feel uncomfortable visiting schools because headteachers often disregard their suggestions; in some schools, SMC members, including the chairman, lack basic seating in the school's office.

8.2.4 Lack of parental support

The participant headteachers of this study revealed that a lack of parental support left them frustrated as they faced challenges in achieving school improvement goals. The following conversation between headteacher A and TR, Ms N, on 9 February 2023, highlights one such challenge as observed:

The headteacher and Ms N discussed ways to enhance students' attendance. The headteacher planned to arrange a meeting with the parents of frequently absent students. However, they discussed that the presence of the parents was usually disappointing whenever parent meetings were called. Ms N pointed out that the absent students' parents were not very interested in receiving calls or attending the meetings when they were invited. The headteacher agreed with Ms N's statement and added that it was particularly disappointing that whenever they phoned 20 parents, only 5 or 6 responded. Furthermore, the head teacher noted that students who attended school consistently had parents who participated in the meetings consistently. In contrast, the parents of the challenging students remained mainly unavailable. As a result, the school's improvement plan remained unachievable.

The above observation underscores the challenge that School A's headteacher faced, as the parents of frequently absent students showed less concern about their children's attendance or contacting the teacher and headteacher. Data reflected that the percentage of parents'

attendance at the meeting was very low. The field notes also displayed that the students who were actively engaged in schools had parents who regularly attended school meetings. These field notes also supported the findings of a study by Kabir and Akter (2014) that examined the difficulties of parental involvement in Bangladeshi secondary schools. The study revealed that schools used phones and email to connect with the parents; however, the lack of parents' awareness hinders them from attending various school improvement meetings arranged by the schools. The study found that most rural parents believe their only obligation is to send their children to school and that teachers must educate them. The study also found that parents were reluctant to attend; one participant stated that a maximum of 40 out of 900 parents attended the parents' meeting.

In an informal conversation, the same concern was shared by Headteacher B, stating that without the cooperation of parents, it was difficult for her to ensure students' classroom achievement. She stressed that it would be wonderful if the parents became even more interested in their children's studies. Unfortunately, most parents working in factories departed for work around seven in the morning and got home at seven or eight at night. After returning to work, they continue to be preoccupied with meal preparation and eating, without time to monitor their children's academic progress. However, the children had been playing outside all day, and when their parents returned, they ate their dinner and went to bed. It is, therefore, insufficient for these students to improve their educational level to study in school. She also said that a few mothers were housewives who attended school daily with their children, and those children were doing well in schoolwork. However, these fractions have a ratio of about 20%. Fifty per cent of parents only attended the school once a year after their child had been admitted.

The above informal conversation highlighted the challenges the headteacher of School B faced from the working parents. As noted by the headteacher, enhancing classroom achievement could be achieved by involving the parents in their children's studies. However, the underprivileged students' parents mostly worked early in the morning till night; they could barely manage their time to look after their children's academic progress. The finding also reflected the same as school A; the active students found their parents frequently visiting the school. However, the data reflected that this percentage is only 20%.

These circumstances align with a study by Hasnat (2016), which examined parents' perceptions of their involvement in the schooling of rural secondary school students in Bangladesh. The study's findings indicate that rural parents often do not know their children's roll numbers or the classes in which they are enrolled. Additionally, they neglect their children's academic performance, showing little interest in school activities or results. Parents expressed a lack of curiosity regarding their children's progress reports. Moreover, they conveyed that they feel disconnected from their children's education, believing it is solely the teachers' responsibility to ensure quality learning. This context leaves parents with a limited understanding of how they might contribute to their children's education, resulting in little motivation to visit the school or engage with teachers.

This fieldnote aligns with an observation made at the School B meeting during teatime on January 15, 2023, between two teachers and the headteacher.

The discussion was about children's academic performance in the final exam, as eight students' progress was so poor that the class teacher declined to promote them to class five. The head teacher shared that all eight parents visited her to request their children's promotion. The class teacher stated they were unreachable throughout the year, even though teachers tried to contact them. The headteacher and teachers unanimously agreed on one point: most unsuccessful students' parents always contacted them at the end of the school year; however, during parents' meetings, they remained pretty unreachable. Those parents explained that they were working and could not attend the meeting.

The above field notes emphasised the importance of parental involvement to students' academic success. Parents are found unable to attend parent meetings and have little concern about their children's progress throughout the year. In addition, they are preoccupied with their jobs, which makes them unable to attend the parent meetings. As a result, they failed to be aware of their children's educational development. When their children struggled at the end of the year, they came to the school solely to speak with the headteacher about their children's promotion. Ultimately, the headteacher faced substantial challenges in maintaining quality education. The 2021 Annual Sector Performance Report (ASPR) revealed that student attendance rates were considerably lower in areas with high parental poverty. It also identified a significant correlation between students' reduced classroom achievement and the number of days they

missed school, showing that when student attendance decreased, their classroom performance also decreased (Directorate of Primary Education, 2022).

In an informal conversation, the headteacher of School C stated that parental engagement was important in ensuring children's classroom progress; nevertheless, her school had substantial challenges due to parents' lack of attendance at school meetings. She mentioned that most of her parents were struggling financially, but that was not the only problem; occasionally, they showed negligence when interacting with teachers. The headteacher also stated that most of her teachers complained that parents did not verify their children's homework copies and did not give water bottles or tiffin. She also mentioned that a few pupils frequently leave school after the tiffin period. Therefore, teachers called parents to meet with the headteacher to inform them of their children's circumstances, but parents hardly answered. The headteacher's remarks also support the viewpoint of school C's SMS chairman, who stated that government primary school headteachers found it difficult to uphold teaching standards due to a lack of parental involvement.

The above informal conversation highlighted the parental lack of engagement in school improvement activities and its adverse effect on primary education. The headteacher's statement made it evident that their lack of participation was due to their socioeconomic circumstances and their neglect of their children's educational needs. Teachers struggled as the students did not bring water bottles and tiffin and left the school before finishing the school's original break. In addition, when teachers called them to meet the headteacher, most did not respond. The field notes highlighted that the headteacher and the chairman found effective classroom teaching and learning very challenging. These field notes correspond with the systematic review by Uddin and Jahan (2023), examining the influence of parents' socioeconomic status on their children's academic success and English proficiency in Bangladeshi primary schools. The research emphasised that parents in lower socioeconomic positions offer less support for their children's educational growth, particularly in the primary education phase.

The Bangladesh National Education Policy of 2010 highlights the importance of parents' involvement in school improvement efforts (Ministry of Education, 2010). The Final Report of the Bangladesh Annual Primary School Census 2023 reinforces the need for parental

participation in primary education, advocating for awareness programs and community-based educational initiatives to minimise dropout rates (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2023). Nevertheless, there has been limited research on effective strategies for headteachers to engage parents in reform initiatives within Bangladeshi primary schools.

8.2.5 Power complexities: headteachers' engagement with government officials

Observations and informal conversations with headteachers in the three schools found that high authorities consistently put pressure on them. The participants' head teachers expressed their belief that the primary responsibility of the education officers was to assist the head teachers in effectively running their schools. Nonetheless, they typically pressure head teachers by giving them more work and making them nervous to accept unwelcome facilities.

An informal conversation with the headteacher of School A stated that headteachers often faced challenges in dealing with education officers. He also mentioned that as the leader of the headteachers' association, he had never encountered any issues with education officers. Both the UEO and AUEO always strived to maintain positive relationships with the teachers and headteachers, who are the leaders. However, as a leader, he was informed about numerous incidents by the teachers who were victims of the education officers. He gave some examples; sometimes, when education officers went for sudden school visits, they found issues, like teachers without teaching aids or lesson plans in the classrooms, or late coming or sitting in the restroom instead of teaching. Alternatively, they found some issues that could be solved easily or could be under-processed, giving the teachers a warning. However, instead of solving the issue, they intentionally hold it and instil fear in the teachers to take unauthorised economic advantage. In this case, they used headteachers and told them they were not working correctly. It was a mental pressure that most of the headteachers have always faced.

The field note above highlights head teachers' significant challenges in primary school. The research revealed that corruption among education officers frequently undermines leadership positions and administrative systems that could serve to improve school performance. Their lack of professionalism is evident when the education officers only count the leaders. It is also disappointing that their misuse of authority undermined the purpose of primary education and made it highly challenging for head teachers to improve the schools. It came to light that they established initiatives to advance primary education to improve their reputation, but they just

considered their own benefit. These unethical activities by education officers make the head teacher feel threatened, frustrated, unsupported, and vulnerable, which creates severe challenges for reforming schools.

The fieldnotes from School A and School C found that when schools arranged the annual sports, both headteachers bought expensive gifts for the TEO/UEO and ATEO/AUEO. I also observed during their visits that the schools used to provide entertainment, planning expensive entertainment for guests from the Thana/ Upazila Education Office and the District Education Office. The following observation further underscores headteachers' dissatisfaction with spending funds for inappropriate purposes. On January 16, 2023, the headteacher and the TR, Ms R, collaborated on specific official paperwork in the headteacher's office at School B:

The headteachers looked irritated and busy writing notes and talking with the TR. They always needed to pay unnoticed bills when any government allocation came. She gave an example showing some evidence that last year (2022), the School Level Improvement Plan (SLIP) had a budget of 85,000 BDT. She paid the VAT of 15000 BDT. She said she must pay for photocopies and transportation. In addition, she noted that this year's (2023) SLIP allocation was reduced from 85,000 BDT to 70,000 BDT. She also added that last year, she received 150,000 BDT in paper for minor repairs, but she received only 129000 BDT. She claimed that to obtain this money, she paid the Engineer Office 5000 BDT (without receipt) to collect the required signature for check clearing, the TEO Office for Accountant General Offices (AG Office), 3000 BDT for transportation, 500 BDT for photocopy, and the Workers Tiffin 1000 BDT. She also stated that she spent 125,000 BDT on repair fees. Her expenses totalled 137,000 BDT (125000+ 5000 + 3000 + 3000 + 500+ 1000). So, her subsidy is 137000 BDT minus 129000 BDT, which equals 8000 BDT.

In an informal conversation, the headteacher said she must wait until the following allotment to return this money. As a result, she must pay her own money for school improvements every time. She was asked why she had paid the engineers and TEO offices without a receipt. She replied that if she did not pay the extra money, her school's name would be removed from the allotment, and the infrastructure development would be questioned. Several repairs are required yearly, such as student toilets, stairs, painting, fan repair, table, chair, bench repair, and water pump replacement.

The above fieldnotes highlighted the vulnerability of the headteachers, as they are bound to engage in activities they disapprove of. The research indicates that it is a tradition to offer gifts to education officers during annual sports events and entertain them whenever they visit. It was also found that headteachers experience frustration because these expenses sometimes compel them to collect money unlawfully from children. Even the consequences of such actions can be severe, as local journalists might uncover this evidence, which could result in disciplinary actions against the headteachers. The study also found that headteachers must pay extra money to the education office, which, according to the TEO, is essential for processing the bills. This unauthorised money is mandatory to pay the education officer; otherwise, headteachers risk disqualification from receiving small repayment bills.

The above field notes also supported the statement made by School C's head teacher. She mentioned one of Thana's Education Officers' names, Ms B. She stated that her school did not receive any small repair bills for nearly four years (2014-2018) because Ms B never paid any outstanding bills to this TEO, and as a result, her school did not receive any allotment. She further stated that this year (2023), the new TEO, Ms Z, asked each school to pay 1000 BDT before receiving SLIP bills. Thana's education comprises 42 schools, and TEO obtained 42,000 BDT from her office assistant. Additionally, no receipt was provided. TEO stated that these funds were necessary for bill processing.

Both the headteachers of Schools B and C believed that instead of assisting the headteacher in classroom improvement and teacher motivation, the ATEO was more interested in school income and expenditure. However, the study discovered that schools B and C did not get adequate classroom monitoring from the education officers (TEO and ATEO). While observing school B, the researcher found that TEO and ATEO visited school B. However, they just went to the classroom for a few minutes before sitting in the office to talk about the issue of an unmotivated teacher. The study revealed, through reviewing documents, that the same TEO served at School B and visited once in 2021 and once in 2022. The same TEO also visited school C, and the scenario was repeated there once a year from 2021 to 2023.

The above field note highlights the lack of education officers' roles and responsibilities, which should assist the headteacher's classroom monitoring and motivating teachers to enhance classroom practices. However, the study revealed that the ATEO mainly focuses on school

funds rather than improving classroom activities. It is demonstrated by the document review that the education officer did not visit the school frequently, which is another challenge for the headteacher in managing unmotivated teachers to keep on track.

The following observation, taken by headteacher C's office room with TR, Ms L and another senior teacher, Ms Ruby on 23 January 2023, highlights their annoying feelings toward the education officers.

The headteacher of School C was very busy writing some documents. Ms L and Ms Ruby were assisting her as well. They spoke annoyedly, sharing their frustration that the education officers never checked the letters received from the District Primary Education Office (DPEO) on time. So, when they needed to provide the information to the DPEO, they rushed and sent the letters to the school and were ordered to provide all the information within a few hours. However, it was pressure for the headteacher to provide the information at once. Whenever the headteacher ordered the teachers to provide the information as soon as possible, they got annoyed and needed to stop taking the class and doing the paperwork. As a result, teachers became annoyed with doing too much paperwork and with their classroom teaching and marking.

The above field note illustrates education officers' lack of support for the headteacher's leadership responsibilities. The last-minute demand frustrated the headteacher because the teachers felt pressured to finish the paperwork, which prevented them from focussing on their primary responsibility, classroom teaching and learning. Additionally, it makes the relationship between the teachers and the headteacher uncomfortable. The failure of the education officers to process the paperwork to the school on time highlighted their improper and inefficient role practices, which frequently increased the headteacher's responsibility of running the teachers smoothly.

The following is another example demonstrating headteachers' significant challenges in dealing with education officers. The observation was made during a meeting in the School B teacher's room with the SMC chairman and headteacher on January 19, 2023:

Following a parent meeting, the School B SMC chairman sat with the headteacher in the teacher's room, having tea. They were discussing the common challenges school

headteachers face in managing their schools. The chairman pointed out that primary teachers are frequently mistreated by their upper management. They (education officers; TEO/ ATEO) simply told them to complete the act without providing adequate resources. He gave an example: two months ago, ATEO Mr Rh instructed the headteacher to provide food to entertain their high officials in a programme. It was probably a teaching aid fair. So, the headteacher organised this food for them; imagine the headteacher needing money to buy the food, putting in the effort to prepare it, and finally needing transportation costs to get them to the venue. It is unfortunate for primary education, in his opinion.

The above field notes again highlight the education officers' inappropriate behaviour, lack of professionalism, and honesty, making the headteachers vulnerable. The data revealed that education officers exploit their power negatively, making unethical demands. For instance, asking the headteachers to arrange food for the official programme at their own expense indicates that education officers prioritise their self-interest over professional responsibilities. On the other hand, this unethical practice creates an economic burden, mental stress, and physical effort for the headteacher.

Research regarding the unethical behaviour of education officers in Bangladesh is limited. In my experience, teachers expressed discomfort in discussing these issues, fearing potential repercussions such as transfers or even more severe consequences. However, UNESCO (2004) reports that a survey on Transparency in education found that approximately one-third of participating headteachers in Bangladesh admitted to bribing education officers in government primary schools. The bribe amount varies based on the required service. Headteachers must offer bribes during school inspections to prevent issues with education officers. Additionally, it is common practice for schools to provide hospitality to visiting officers from the primary education offices, such as the Upazila Education Officer or the Assistant Education Officer, during inspections. Teachers and school management committees believe properly entertaining the officer will positively evaluate their school. Some government officers even expect lavish hospitality, which aligns with observations noted in the current study.

8.3 Opportunities for headteachers when undertaking school improvement initiatives

8.3.1 Resilience, commitment and effective leadership

Resilience is the capacity to overcome challenges and seize opportunities. Field notes from three schools' headteachers and stakeholders highlighted that headteachers in primary schools

face significant challenges in managing their schools. These challenges are primarily focused on when headteachers contend with insufficient school funding, insufficient skilled and motivated staff, ineffective managing committees and parents, and less cooperative education officers. Ethnographic observations and informal conversations with headteachers indicate that their resilience, including exhibiting clarity, managing stress, building relationships, and applying effective leadership, is important in their ability to take opportunities to improve the schools.

This perspective was also evident during a meeting between the SMC chairman and the headteacher of School A, where they discussed the expenditure of the SLIP fund. It was observed that the headteacher was creating a detailed list of 2022-2023 SLIP expenditures to display on the wall for everyone to observe. The list includes funds from private and government sources. The headteacher explained that this practice was essential for maintaining clarity, which he identified as an essential keystone in school improvement initiatives. He claimed that this unique quality made him a successful head teacher. This approach aligns.... All management committee members, teachers, parents, and even community members were aware of how much he correctly utilised the SLIP fund and the funds obtained from the community on occasion.

Subsequently, he expounded on his extensive experience, observing that head teachers frequently encountered conflicts about how best to use the SLIP funds with other teachers and management committee members. Additionally, this issue caused the teacher's dissatisfaction and led to ineffective teaching in the classroom. Although it is stressful, to maintain a healthy school environment, headteachers must manage stress through effective leadership. He further stated that one or two teachers in every school were always ready to raise concerns with the headteacher. Moreover, these one or two teachers had the potential to undermine the school's overall positive atmosphere. Headteachers had no option but to maintain transparency regarding how they allocated funds received from public or private sources. Additionally, he emphasised that clarity enhanced the headteacher's professional image and created more opportunities to address challenges that could hinder the school's progress.

The above field notes demonstrated the School A headteacher's resilience by exhibiting SLIP expenditure transparency. This study found that headteachers display the list of expenditures

for 2022-2023 so that any visitors can easily observe. Displaying the detailed expenditure reports ensured his accountability with greater clarity and a trusted relationship with staff and SMC. Indirectly, it fosters a healthy environment for teaching and learning in schools, and it also secures funding from the community for future development. This behaviour reflects Hallinger's (2011) concept of 'strategic resourcing', which emphasises aligning the selection and allocation of resources, such as funds and staffing, to priority teaching and learning goals. By ensuring transparent financial management and maintaining quality staffing, the headteacher demonstrated effective instructional leadership that supports school improvement.

The field notes emphasised the importance of transparency in SLIP expenditures. Many headteachers face issues such as teacher dissatisfaction, which increases their stress levels and hampers effective teaching in the classroom. The notes pointed out that improved clarity enhances a headteacher's professional standing and provides more significant opportunities to tackle school improvement challenges. This observation aligns with the research by Sardar and Galdames (2018), which indicated that resilient traits in school leaders empower them to manage stress, face challenges, and achieve their goals. The authors highlighted that key concepts for headteachers and teachers in the educational landscape are fostering resilience, maintaining a work-life balance, and promoting well-being.

Since School B and School C- are in the same Education Thana, everyone is aware of the difficulties experienced by School B's head teacher.

Once, in an informal conversation, the headteacher of School C shared her opinion that transparency is the best option to create a strong position for the headteacher among the teachers. She mentioned that she has an extensive teaching staff, three times larger than school B's teaching staff. She continued that she did not face any challenges in managing her teachers because trust was established through transparency. In an informal conversation, she mentioned that she always involves the teachers not only in collecting money but also in spending money. When she distributed the duties, she ensured no divisions among her teachers. She focused on building good relationships with the staff. Every year, with their contribution, she arranges an annual picnic where all teachers participate with their spouses and children. The participation was not mandatory; however, they participated with greater joy.

The fieldnote highlighted that when a headteacher demonstrates clarity in school activities, it builds trust, enabling teachers to work collaboratively towards school improvement. The headteacher's strong leadership skills allowed her to foster positive relationships by organising various entertainment events for staff and their families, significantly enhancing school improvement efforts. This exemplifies instructional leadership, as she set up participatory processes that improved collaboration and shared responsibility among the staff for reaching the expected instructional goals (Hallinger, 2011). It was also observed that the head teacher's effective leadership helped her manage the challenges arising from the community. The following observation took place at School C's headteacher's office room on 18 January 2023:

The headteacher reviewed official files while having tea and looked at the registration book for the school's managing committee meetings. Suddenly, a community leader approached the headteacher and greeted her. The headteacher appeared visibly disturbed by his presence. She tried to ignore the person sitting in front of her. She tried to focus more on the registration book than she had before. The community leader then asked her if she could give him some time. Following that, he did not wait for the reply and directly asked her to tell him about her decision to admit the students to class seven, which he had already proposed three times. Without looking at him, the headteacher replied that there were already 70 students in that class and no seats available for new students, which he had already been informed about. The man insisted that the headteacher do her best to accommodate the student. He then began to exert his political influence. The headteacher appeared annoyed by his behaviour, but the man was firm in his request. He threatened the headteacher, stating he would escalate the matter to the current education minister and the DG (Directorate General, Primary Education). After a moment, the headteacher asked the man to return later, explaining that she needed to consult other teachers to see if they could admit the new student. Before leaving, he warned the headteacher that he expected a favourable decision upon his return the following day.

When the man left her office, she phoned the managing committee chairman to discuss the situation. She explained the situation, emphasising that class seven had no extra seats. As someone threatened her, which was no longer expected, the headteacher admitted it was stressful. Following the conversation with the Chairman, the headteacher clicked the bell button, and the office assistant arrived. The headteacher instructed her to call Ms L and bring three cups of tea.

Ms L arrived in her room in less than two minutes. The headteacher explained that Mr X, the community leader, had returned and threatened her again to admit the student to class seven. Ms L listened attentively, nodding in agreement. The head teacher urged her to try to get the student admitted after speaking with the other assistant teachers. We three recommended drinking the tea as soon as it arrived. The headteacher's face reflected stressless after deciding on this admission. The next day, 19 January 2023, another observation was made at the School C headteacher's office, highlighting the headteacher's resilience in managing stress while ensuring a healthy educational environment.

At 11 o'clock, the same community leader returned to the headteacher's office, skipping any formalities greetings; he asked the head teacher about her decision regarding the student's admission. Without turning to face him, the head teacher replied that she would admit the student, but she did not have any books for the student; as a result, he would need to manage the books from somewhere else. The man nodded in agreement and thanked the headteacher before leaving the room.

After that person's departure, the headteacher started discussing with Ms L. The head teacher continued to say that one additional student out of the 70 could be managed. It is not a big issue, but the fact that she accepted it did not imply that the man had a relationship with the education minister and would go to her and report against the headteacher. Even this man was making an incorrect appeal. However, if the headteacher did not listen to the man, the man would remain behind her school, and anytime he discovered any hidden information about the school, he would report it to higher authorities. She believed that no school was completely free from issues. There were some secrets in every school. The headteacher concluded that to prevent a future unexpected crisis, she made a deal with Mr X's illegal wants. Ms L remarks that they had nothing negative to say against political authority. She further stated that even though these people were not directly associated with central politics, they were not decent individuals. As a result, they could often be detrimental to maintaining prestige.

The above field notes highlight the headteacher's strong personality, exceptional leadership skills, and notable resilience, which are essential for controlling stress, managing challenges, and maintaining a healthy school environment. It was observed that the headteacher was initially determined to stay lawful by refusing to admit the student due to the lack of additional seats in the mentioned class. Additionally, her decision to share the issue with the SMC

chairman demonstrated a commitment to shared responsibility, fostering a strong professional bond between the school management and the headteacher.

However, faced with community pressure, which could develop into a significant challenge in the future, such as losing the school's reputation, the headteacher ultimately compromised her power/authority to improve the school environment. This exemplifies the headteacher's effective leadership and resilience in building relationships among the staff, the SMC and the community. This field note supports the findings of Hamid et al. (2021) in Malaysia, which indicated that primary school headteachers must make numerous decisions that require effective communication, implementation, and management skills, necessitating a strong capacity for resilience. The study highlights the importance of headteachers cultivating resilience to effectively oversee the school, staff, and various initiatives for school improvement.

This viewpoint was also aligned with the education officer's statement. While discussing School B's demotivated teachers' issue, in an informal conversation, she replied that the headteacher's adequate leadership capacity is essential to making the school effective. She emphasised the headteacher's being unbiased and demonstrated clarity in school activities, including spending funds. The ability of an impartial headteacher to motivate a group of teachers is a great way to increase the quality of education. She highlighted the head teacher's transparency about their financial situation. Choosing how best to use funding for school development makes the process easier. As a result, teachers, too, cannot be demotivated.

The above field notes reflected that a headteacher's effective leadership is significant in facing school improvement challenges. It is also observed that through exhibiting clarity and impartiality, the headteacher can face the teacher's unmotivated challenge, as the ability of an impartial headteacher to motivate a group of teachers is a great way to increase the quality of education. In addition, the field notes of this study reflect that building a good relationship between the headteacher, teacher staff, and the members of SMC can create a positive teaching and learning school environment, which ultimately helps the headteacher to fulfil the school vision.

8.3.2 Sharing School Vision

The participants revealed that sharing the school vision with relevant stakeholders helps headteachers address various school improvement challenges, especially when the school funds are limited. All the headteachers agreed that a shared vision creates a significant opportunity to achieve the school's goals. In an informal conversation, the headteacher of School A referred to documents outlining the SLIP policy (DPE-2023), which aims to align with the vision and mission of primary education by creating a child-friendly environment to ensure quality primary education. He emphasised that sharing the school vision is significant, as the guidelines strongly advocate for the involvement of teachers, students, parents and local people in school improvement activities.

In an informal conversation, he stated what he meant by the vision and its importance for school improvement. He detailed that the school has three development plans: a short-term plan for 01-12 months, a medium-term plan (01-05 years) and a long-term plan (more than 5 years). This plan outlines how the school will achieve its student achievement goal and ensure a child-friendly environment. The headteacher primarily prepares this plan according to the policy provided by the Directorate of Primary Education (DPE). The headteacher emphasised that making a school improvement plan successful requires collaborative action. He mentioned an example: this year (January 2023- December 2023), his school created a vision for primary school students. The goal is for students to recognise all Alphabets within three months, identify Bengali and English alphabets and count and write numbers from 1 to 20 by March. The plan continues until November, aiming for students to read two-letter words without struggling. This action can only be accomplished with the cooperation of the class teacher by providing the proper guidelines for successful implementation.

Then he continued stating that to achieve this vision, he needs to ensure students' regular attendance, then needs effective teaching aids and then needs teachers' effective classroom teaching and learning. Organising all these requirements requires a proper connection with parents so that they can ensure that their children are sent to school. Also, parents must talk with the headteacher about whether their children received proper teaching. Additionally, ensuring classroom decoration and teaching aids requires funds (private and public) that can

be provided through SMC, the local community, and education officers. Overall, all stakeholders need to be actively involved in this collaborative activity.

The headteacher of School A also provided another example of how a shared vision can help fulfil school goals. Recalling from memory, he shared that it had long been his cherished goal to establish a well-resourced library at his school. To fulfil his desire, he often shared this vision with the stakeholders involved in any school program, including community people. He added that he had continuously fostered the establishment of a school library once a wealthy person in his school area responded positively. With this person's more significant contribution and the mutual participation of other stakeholders, he fulfilled this vision. As observed:

It was observed that School A has an extensive library and consists of a wide variety of books. During this observation of the book library, the headteacher mentioned that around 2.5 lakhs BDT was spent on purchasing these books and constructing the bookshelves. The books are impressive, and the shelves holding the books are also eye-catching. The headteacher noted that the vast collection of books was acquired through the community's support, and he motivated rich people to engage in this activity. He has named this library the 'Anondo Library (School A Fieldnotes, February 28, 2023).

The above field notes highlight that sharing the school vision is the best way to implement school goals. In the above informal conversation, the headteacher's statement emphasised that the success of school improvement activities depends on collaboration among stakeholders, including teachers, parents, the local community, and education officers. The headteacher provided two examples to illustrate the importance of shared vision: the first is a short-term plan to improve class one students' foundational skills, such as letter recognition, number counting and reading two-letter words without struggling. He also emphasises that the success of his vision depends on the collaboration of all stakeholders, including parents, teachers, SMC and education officers. Secondly, the headteacher provided another example of a shared vision that helped him to establish a well-resourced library at his school. The headteacher mentioned only sharing his vision; he successfully articulated all the relevant stakeholders to fulfil the vision and established the 'Anondo Library' in his school.

The country's education policy underscores that each school must feature a library with essential books for students (Ministry of Education, 2010). According to the Continuous

Professional Development (CPD) Framework and Action Plan, head teachers in Bangladesh must plan school improvement projects involving local stakeholders (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2019). Additionally, the CPD framework stresses the necessity for headteachers to take part in quarterly meetings with stakeholders such as the School Management Committee (SMC), parents, and members of the local school community to discuss government policies and guidelines, as well as to garner support for fulfilling the school's vision.

This practice also aligns with the activities of the headteacher of School C. In an informal conversation, the headteacher of School C explained how she shares the school vision with stakeholders and why it is important. She stated that to establish the school vision, she requires the involvement of the teaching staff, as it focuses on classroom enhancement. Without consulting them, it would be impossible to set any targets. She first assesses the students' levels by class and subject with the help of the subject teachers. For example, she mentioned that if she focuses on Bengali learning in Class One, she will look at expected learning outcomes, such as students learning the alphabet and understanding how to form words. To fulfil this vision, she arranged a meeting with the teachers and noted that until March, they would engage in child surveys, student admissions, and annual sports and cultural programs. She conducts a baseline survey every March to assess the students' progress. Based on this survey, she sets activities to help students achieve the expected goals.

The above data show that the head teacher at school C communicated her goal to SMC and the staff to get the best outcomes for school improvement. This field note is consistent with research by Morshed (2016) that examined the leadership role of head teachers in incorporating ICT tools in secondary school classrooms in Bangladesh. This study reveals that to establish effective technology-based classrooms, headteachers collaborated with teachers to create a vision. Headteachers and teachers communicated and shared these visions with the relevant stakeholders to implement the determined vision. These shared visions serve as the foundation for future stakeholder interactions and cooperation. This study also found that almost all the participants agreed that their vision was to see ICT-based classrooms succeed since they shared the vision and were committed to making it a reality. The study also demonstrated that all teachers receive continuous support from head teachers, peers, pupils, and parents as they carry out the vision.

8.3.3 Increase Mentoring

From the field notes, stakeholders in this study emphasised that mentoring can be an excellent opportunity for the headteachers to motivate the teachers, thereby ensuring effective classroom teaching and learning. In an informal conversation, the headteacher of School A stated that he and all the headteachers who received newly appointed teachers had undertaken mentorship training from the Thana Resource Centre. This training taught him a lot about ‘mentor and mentee’. He believes mentoring is an excellent idea for headteachers to make both newly appointed teachers and teachers with long-term experience effective. He added that, in his school, he emphasises being a mentor for his teachers. Accordingly, after monitoring the classroom teaching and learning, he always helps them to develop the classroom activities by identifying the issues he (mentor) and his teacher (mentee) find the best solutions. The headteacher also mentioned that he consistently follows the principles learned from the training and provides teachers with constructive feedback and recommendations.

The above informal conversation demonstrated that mentoring is a key technique that the headteacher uses to provide feedback after assessing teachers' classroom performance. The field notes highlighted the headteacher's efforts to improve classroom teaching and learning. While observing the classroom, his mentoring aimed to inspire his teaching team to adopt his critical feedback and recommendations. This approach aligns with Hallinger's (2011) dimensions of instructional leadership, especially in planning, organising, and evaluating classroom teaching and learning, where headteachers directly observe and support teachers' classroom practices and provide feedback to them. Additionally, his active role in mentoring reflects Hallinger's (2011) concept of fostering teacher learning, as the headteacher collaborates with teachers in ongoing professional development to improve instruction quality.

The headteacher was a mentor, ultimately motivating the teachers to deliver the highest classroom performance. This field note was in line with a study by Moyer (2014) that examines the efficacy of teacher preparation programs and instructional strategies employed in Bangladeshi government primary schools. According to the study, headteachers' mentoring

helps new teachers better understand classroom dynamics and deal with the difficulties of their first few years of teaching.

In an informal conversation, the Thana Education Officer (TEO) also emphasised that headteachers' mentoring can be one of the best tools to ensure a positive school learning environment. She also mentioned the mentoring training provided by the DPE. She stated that, alongside supervision and managing the schools, it is also the headteacher's role to mentor the staff to improve classroom teaching and learning. The TEO also highlighted that some headteachers manage their schools by following mentoring principles. These headteachers primarily focused on monitoring the classroom and, like mentors, providing essential feedback to the teachers. She also shared that some school headteachers discuss classroom issues with the ATEO to get education officers' advice about the mentoring strategy.

The informal conversation above highlighted that headteachers' mentoring is essential for effective classroom teaching and learning. The fieldnote highlighted that the education officer found mentoring very effective, as some headteachers successfully involved the teachers in classroom activities using mentoring. In addition, the data also revealed that the headteachers were interested in getting more information from education officers to enhance their mentorship. This viewpoint aligns with the CPD Framework and Action Plan, which explains that since mentoring is an essential component of teachers' classroom preparation programs around the world, Bangladeshi head teachers encourage teachers to provide a supportive, child-friendly learning environment to improve classroom learning by using mentorship (Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, 2019).

In an informal conversation, the headteacher of School C revealed the same viewpoint. She stated that in her school, while observing the classroom, she enjoys seeing herself as a mentor more than a supervisor. She also stated that in every aspect of the educational setting, all individuals should act as mentors or mentees. It helps to set school goals, identify the possible challenges, develop a plan, and then practice, which strengthens the shared recommendations of everyone involved. She added that mentoring is the best way to achieve school goals by providing extensive feedback and strengthening teachers' capacity.

The above conversation also underlined that mentoring is an excellent opportunity to improve classroom practice, ultimately contributing to achieving the school's goal. The field note showed that the headteacher's flexibility as a mentor strengthened teachers' ability to enhance teaching methods. This field note is consistent with one study conducted in primary schools in Nepal by Choeda (2023) to examine school headteachers' roles in boosting teachers' professional progress. This study aimed to look into how Bhutanese school leaders support and guide their teachers' professional development. In addition, it explains that school leaders' active participation in teacher professional development impacts both leaders' and teachers' professional progress.

8.4 Conclusion

The findings in this chapter showed that headteachers in three government primary schools faced significant challenges when they endeavoured to implement school improvement initiatives. The observation and informal conversation report showed that multiple challenges, such as teachers' de-motivation, parents' financial limitations, lack of SMC members, parental support and education officers' abusive authority, frustrate the headteacher in leading school improvement initiatives. However, data revealed that headteachers' resilience, commitment and effective leadership play an important role in their ability to take opportunities to improve the schools.

Chapter 9: Conclusion

9.1 Introduction

This chapter aims to provide a general conclusion for the research. It is organised into seven sections. The first section (9.2) succinctly summarises the key findings and recommendations in relation to the research questions. The second section (9.3) discusses the study's contributions to knowledge, followed by the work's limitations in section three (9.4). In section four (9.5), the implications of the study are described. Section five (9.6) identifies areas for further research based on the findings. Finally, section six (9.7) offers my reflections on the PhD journey throughout this research.

9.2 Key Findings and resulting Recommendations

This educational ethnographic study explores the experiences of primary school headteachers in three government schools in the Dhaka district of Bangladesh as they navigate the complex school improvement process. To achieve this aim, data were collected through ethnographic observation, informal conversation, and document reviews. In this section, the findings are summarised and presented in alignment with each research question.

RQ1: How do stakeholders explain the role of the headteacher in leading school improvement initiatives?

The findings revealed different understandings of 'school improvement' in the Bangladeshi context. Overall, the data from the three schools highlighted that stakeholder, especially headteachers, teachers, parents, members of the school managing committee, and government officials, perceive the headteacher as playing a key role in school improvement by providing a quality learning environment, funds and resources, ensuring student attendance and academic success, fostering active parental engagement, and supporting well-prepared, trained, and motivated teachers. All stakeholders emphasised that the role of headteachers in managing and monitoring the quality of learning is central to school improvement. A recommendation resulting from this finding could be that headteachers recognise and are active in this role of monitoring learning to ensure good student outcomes. They should be encouraged to seek support and training to ensure their effectiveness in this respect, should that be necessary.

When referring to the quality of the 'learning environment' stakeholders explained that the headteachers' role and responsibilities were to ensure the quality of the school campus, including school gates, boundary walls, school fields, and gardens, as well as ensuring that

classrooms were well-decorated, had adequate teaching aids, and pupils had access to a multimedia classroom. Stakeholders also highlighted the importance of classrooms with enough light and electric fans, clean drinking water, and hygienic toilets. A key recommendation from this finding is for stakeholders and headteachers to collaborate closely to create a high-quality learning environment. This encompasses enhancing schools' physical infrastructure and establishing child-friendly classrooms with sufficient teaching aids. By working together, they can create a quality learning environment that fosters effective classroom teaching and learning.

In addition, observing and speaking with headteachers in the three schools indicated that securing funds and resources was seen as one of their essential roles in ensuring school improvement. Their proactive engagement with the community and the ability to leverage the limited government fund underscore their practical leadership skills, particularly in arranging various school events and building relationships with the local community, partly in pursuit of funding. The findings of this study revealed that the Headteachers focused on improving the learning environment by implementing various strategies to manage funds (public and private), including encouraging stakeholders' shared responsibility. However, the study found that headteachers in government primary schools are confronted with inadequate government allocation/funding. Thus, headteachers must play a proactive role in administration and as community mobilisers, fundraisers, and advocates for their students. A recommendation arising from this finding would be that schools are sufficiently well-resourced through central funding, allowing headteachers to dedicate their time to improving teaching and learning rather than seeking additional funding elsewhere.

Moreover, this study's findings suggest that headteachers' regular monitoring of the classroom and assembly, along with constructive feedback, can enhance students' attendance and academic performance, which is essential for school improvement. The findings also suggest that active parental involvement in school activities was noted as one of the headteacher's roles supporting school improvement. In the three schools, headteachers were seen to play a key role in encouraging parents to participate actively in school activities, thereby helping to educate their children. A recommendation based on teachers is that headteachers should regularly monitor classroom teaching and learning, check students' attendance through assemblies and from class teachers, and provide essential feedback to teachers and students to improve

attendance and classroom teaching and learning. Headteachers should also continue to engage parents and guardians in school activities by organising regular meetings. This collaboration can foster a robust relationship between teachers and parents, ultimately enhancing students' success both at school and at home.

This study's findings also indicate that the role of headteachers in keeping teachers motivated was a vital component of school improvement. Headteachers were observed seeking to ensure teachers were effectively motivated, as motivated teachers are likely to be professional and, therefore, well-prepared when planning and teaching. It is recommended that headteachers adopt structured and evidence-informed strategies to sustain and enhance teacher motivation, with particular focus on professional development, recognition of effort, and supportive leadership practices that directly contribute to teaching quality and school improvement.

However, the findings also reveal that some teachers feel demotivated primarily due to common issues such as long class hours, insufficient breaks, inadequate pay, and large class sizes. In this respect, it is recommended that the Directorate of Primary Education review the policy regarding appropriate class sizes and hours, teacher pay, and professionalisation in response to the impact of these factors on teacher motivation.

RQ2: In what ways do headteachers experience the enactment of power in their leadership of school improvement?

Findings related to research question 2 were identified using Foucault's concept of power to shed light on how power operates within the headteachers' leadership of school improvement. The chapter starts by using Foucault's key concepts related to power, especially subjectivity and ethics, governmentality, and disciplinary power, focusing on surveillance (monitoring) to analyse the participant headteachers' enactment of school improvement activities. Through a Foucauldian lens, the chapter considers how the headteachers in Bangladeshi government primary schools exercise and experience power, not as something inert, but as something enacted in pursuit of school improvement.

Findings from the contexts of the three schools reveal that subjectivity and ethics refer to the headteachers' experience, self-knowledge, values, and beliefs, which help them successfully foster good relationships with staff, parents, and the broader community to achieve school improvement. The headteachers are observed exercising government power to shape the conduct of both the teachers and students when seeking to improve classroom activities. In the

case of school leadership, governmentality refers to using the headteachers as the vehicle to govern the teachers, staff, and students to run the school successfully.

Foucault explained how the institute (in the case of this research, the school) normalises behaviour through disciplinary instruments - hierarchical observation, normalising judgement and the examination.

The findings of this study suggest that the headteachers recognise that monitoring of the classroom establishes norms within the school and exercises power in a way that encourages teachers and students to ensure the standards and regulations are meticulously followed. The headteachers consider monitoring of classroom activities as a key component of school improvement, acknowledging that frequent monitoring from the headteacher increases both teacher and student attention. This exercise of power gives the head teacher certain control over the behaviour of teachers and students, and it is observed that the head teacher's direct monitoring and repeated messages positively influence the students' immediate behaviour, even when they were not present in the school. This study reveals that normalising judgment helps leaders promote actions that improve schools. It shows that the headteacher sets a norm for teachers to meet by fostering an environment where they can self-regulate through monitoring. The headteacher's actions reflect Foucault's concept of surveillance, maintaining influence without constant physical monitoring. This guidance from school leaders is primarily intended to facilitate positive pupil outcomes by engaging teachers and stakeholders in supporting school improvement.

RQ3: What are the challenges and opportunities for Headteachers in leading school improvement initiatives?

The ethnographic field notes in Chapter Eight indicate that headteachers in these three government primary schools faced significant challenges, such as teacher demotivation. The study's findings suggest that teachers' lack of professional commitment to pedagogical obligations can lead to unethical action and prioritising personal and financial interests over professional commitment.

A recommendation for this finding is that headteachers should support teachers in addressing their demotivation by expecting professionalism aligned with support and training. Headteachers' regular training, monitoring, focused feedback, and clear expectation setting for classroom actions can play a key role in enhancing teachers' commitment to their classroom

teaching and helping them stay dutiful and ethical in their professional roles. This, of course, assumes that teachers' ability to fulfil their professional obligations is adequately funded (see concluding point in RQ1 above).

In addition, the findings shed light on the significant challenges primary school headteachers face in Bangladesh due to parents' financial limitations, which, in turn, influence students' absence. The study also found that a lack of parental support, especially from parents of frequently absent students, frustrated headteachers' attempts to achieve school improvement goals.

This research might recommend that headteachers seek to make the most of the rich community support available to assist financially struggling parents in supporting their children's education. Furthermore, if schools and the wider community are able to work together to raise awareness of the importance of regular attendance find ways to support the families so that their children can attend school regularly, this in turn can have a positive impact on pupils' abilities to do well in school.

Findings also show that a lack of SMC members' presence in meetings and school improvement activities is another challenge for school headteachers, as their presence could help the head teacher secure funds and support teachers to effectively engage with school improvement initiatives. Based on these findings, a recommendation could be made that the formation of SMCs be reviewed and strengthened, through District-level orientation and training, so that all the SMC members understand and are able to effectively assume their responsibilities. The Directorate of Primary Education (DPE) should assume responsibility for leading this.

The study findings highlight a significant challenge for headteachers in Bangladesh: the complex power dynamics with education officers. Corruption among education officers undermines leadership and administrative systems that could enhance school performance. Their misuse of authority hampers primary education efforts, making it difficult for headteachers to effect improvements. The participant HTs reflected that education officers' interactions with their schools were often focused on enhancing the officers' own reputation rather than on school development. Infrequent visits to schools compounded the challenge of managing unmotivated teachers. Traditionally, gifts must be given to education officers during annual sports events, and headteachers must pay additional fees to the education office, which

the TEO claims are necessary for processing bills. These unethical practices leave headteachers feeling threatened, frustrated, unsupported, and vulnerable, posing severe challenges to school improvement. A recommendation for this finding is that DPE provide clear guidelines for education officers with respect to expectations of conduct so that these officers can support headteachers with respect and professionalism. This effort could help headteachers with a framework of clear expectations, so that they can focus all of their efforts on school improvement.

Finally, the findings suggest that the headteachers' resilience, commitment, and effective leadership, along with their ability to share the school vision and provide mentoring, can contribute to their capacity to capitalise on opportunities for school improvement. This finding recommends that headteachers should be encouraged and supported to strengthen their leadership skills, including sharing a clear school vision, mentoring staff, and staying committed even during challenges. The DPE should provide ongoing school leadership training and professional development programs that focus on building these qualities to help headteachers lead school improvement more effectively.

9.3 Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes knowledge in three ways: research context, methodology, and findings. First, the context is an important contribution to the school leadership research. Whilst some studies have investigated Bangladeshi headteachers' vital role in securing quality primary schools (Kabir, Green, and Chowdhury, 2020) and the importance of creating a joyful learning environment (Kamal and Chowdhury, 2019; KAMAL, 2018), others have focussed on headteachers' transformational, managerial and instructional leadership (Islam, Rahman, and Islam, 2023; Ananda, 2021; Ali, 2011; Uddin, Akhter, and Hena, 2018; Hoque, 2007). However, no studies have focussed on the headteacher's role in driving forward school improvement.

In doing so, the current study applied the educational ethnography research method discussed in Chapter Five. This method included in-depth ethnographic observation, informal discussion, and document review. This is the first attempt to investigate headteacher leadership of school improvement in Bangladesh through an ethnographic study. This ethnographic data sought to

present the richness of the participants' voices and experiences and highlight the uniqueness of my research.

Finally, while acknowledging the study's limitations (section 9.4), its final contribution is its findings, which show that the headteachers of Bangladeshi primary schools enacted noteworthy school improvement responsibilities and encountered significant challenges, as acknowledged by key stakeholders. This study's key contributions help interested researchers and professionals to understand better challenges headteachers encounter. Concurrently, it shares some practical strategies the participant headteachers used to address these challenges and the initiatives they implemented to enhance their schools.

9.4 Limitations of the Study

Limitations are part of the research that might influence answers to the research questions and the study's findings. Limitations concern potential weaknesses for any study, even those that are out of the researcher's control. The first limitation of this study is the sample size. It is already stated in section 5.4 that this study has collected rich data from natural settings within three government primary schools in Dhaka (the capital city of Bangladesh) to investigate headteachers' leadership in school improvement. The richness of the data is a strength of the study. However, as discussed in Section 2, factors such as geographical location and socioeconomic status are known to impact school improvement and student learning outcomes. Around 17.38% (22,993) of Bangladesh's schools are in remote areas where government services can access a little. Therefore, the participants from only three primary schools nationwide will not fully capture the diversity and complexity of the broader educational landscape.

In addition, the study's limitations (especially in qualitative research) are related to generalisability, subjectivity, small sample size, inability to elicit sincere responses from participants, and logistics and resources, including time and money (Patton, 2002). The limited duration of participant meetings and data collection, a total of 5 months (75 working days), presents one of the study's limitations. An ideal ethnographic study requires six months of research within an eighteen-month period to collect extensive data (Jeffrey and Troman, 2004), thereby enhancing the understanding of headteachers' leadership for school improvement. Although I could have gathered more data with a longer time in the field, my position as an

insider allowed me to quickly absorb the experiences I observed. However, the COVID-19 pandemic during 2021/2022, coupled with the researcher's status as an international PhD student, limited the feasibility of extended data collection at the research site.

9.5 Implications of the Study

This study investigates the leadership roles of the Bangladeshi government primary school headteachers in school improvement. While examining how they led, this study discovered considerable school improvement responsibilities that headteachers are required to undertake, and they experienced numerous challenges while doing so. As previously stated, little research in Bangladesh has previously focussed on headteacher's role in leadership of school improvement; however, the current study provides valuable insights from the participant headteachers and their stakeholders. Therefore, this study has implications for supporting other school headteachers to reflect on their leadership roles and practices.

In addition, the findings will assist Bangladeshi policymakers in understanding, in some detail, the present concerns confronting headteachers, including the obstacles they encounter in the leadership of school improvement. Policymakers can use these insights to begin to address challenges and support headteachers in leadership development.

The findings also highlighted headteachers' effective leadership strategies, in leading school improvement. Other headteachers can learn from these.

Another implication of this study's findings is that it provides some further groundwork for research into the school improvement-focussed leadership roles of school head teachers in Bangladeshi Government primary schools. Researchers may use the results of this study to inform their research if they wish to further understand headteachers' leadership, school improvement challenges and how the participant headteachers sought to overcome such challenges.

9.6 Suggestions for Future Research

While conducting this study, several issues that needed further investigation, but were not connected to the current, study emerged. The current study focused only on three primary schools in Dhaka's capital city. During the research, some participants recalled numerous challenges outside the Dhaka district's schools. Within Bangladesh's geographical location,

some schools are located in particular regions (hard-to-reach areas). Similarly, more studies are needed to emphasise the leadership of rural school headteachers and the leadership initiatives of schools in hard-to-reach locations to improve their schools. Since headteachers face stress and conflict within their roles, additional research is needed to investigate the influence of stress and role conflict on their leadership performance and initiatives to reduce this stress and role conflict. Finally, as previously stated, headteachers carry out their responsibilities in partnership with essential stakeholders such as teachers and the school SMC. Consequently, further study is required to explore the professional development of school headteachers, improve communication with the School Management Committee, and work with teachers to generate ideas for enhanced leadership practices in primary education. Research is needed to understand better how headteachers may take ownership of school improvement initiatives. This might involve an examination of the headteacher's leadership position and the policymakers' duty to strengthen their influence in improving primary education in Bangladesh. It could also involve discussing power decentralisation to empower educational leaders' and policymakers' perspectives, or how government officials might help improve head teachers' instructional leadership applications.

9.7 Concluding Remarks: Ending the PhD Journey, Personal Reflection, and Leadership Philosophy

In conclusion, this study's findings establish a significant step forward in understanding the role of school leadership in Bangladeshi primary schools. This educational ethnographic study investigated Bangladeshi primary school headteachers' roles and leadership practices in support of school improvement. In addition, this study explores the significant challenges that Bangladeshi primary school headteachers' experienced when they attempted to drive forward school improvement initiatives. Despite its small sample size, the findings of this study can significantly contribute to assisting policymakers in creating interventions to better support headteachers' in these efforts. Thus, the implications of this research extend beyond the scholarly community and will benefit both practitioners and policymakers. Notwithstanding the limitations of the study, the findings will be helpful for future scholars looking to analyse and investigate school leadership in developing countries' primary schools.

This research has significantly shaped my identity as a researcher, as I have become more aware of the important concepts related to this research. Despite being a headteacher in

Bangladesh for 12 years, I was introduced to new school leadership experiences daily at the research site. I was surprised to see new issues daily and to observe how headteachers addressed these in support of school improvement. I noticed that each school faced different issues and opportunities, and each headteacher uniquely responded to these challenges.

My leadership philosophy has evolved through the combination of instructional and transformational leadership. I believe effective school leadership begins with a strong instructional focus, as culture builders, fostering high standards and expectations for both teachers and students (Hallinger, 2005). This means aligning the schools' academic vision and mission with various practical strategies that support teaching and learning. This involves supporting staff, ensuring a child-friendly classroom environment, improving instructional practices, and mentoring teachers; thus, instructional leaders are goal-oriented for school improvement.

At the same time, transformational leadership encourages school headteachers to use facilitative power to implement second-order changes within their schools. School headteachers emphasise motivating teachers to work smarter and more collaboratively to achieve meaningful and sustainable change in schools (Leithwood and Jantzi, 2005).

However, drawing on Foucault's (1977) concept of power, I also recognise that leadership exists within wider social and institutional structures that can both enable and constrain action. Leaders do not simply possess power; they also circulate it through relationships, routines, and policies. Therefore, my philosophy emphasises empowerment, collaboration, and shared decision-making, while maintaining a critical awareness of how authority and policy shape the autonomy of teachers and headteachers.

Also, as a novice researcher, I undertook my PhD far from my country. During that time, I faced various challenges, including the COVID-19 pandemic; I was able to overcome them with the unlimited support of my supervisors. Through their support, I have gained in-depth knowledge and completed my educational ethnographic research.

Berg (2001, referenced in Saha, 2023) asserts that even once the research is completed, it is not considered complete until the findings are disseminated. I have already presented some of my research findings at the PGR Teach Meet, Research Festival, and Research Seminar Series at

my university. I also presented some of my research findings at the ECER 2024 conference, where I received helpful feedback which enabled me to further refine my thinking. My next step will be to report from the findings of this study in an academic journal.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Participant Information Sheet

School of Education & Social Sciences
Paisley Campus

Participant Information Sheet

Title of Project: Headteachers' Leadership of School Improvement in Bangladeshi Government Primary Schools: An Ethnographic Study

Researcher: Nasrin Sultana

I want to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide, you need to understand why the research is being done and what it involves. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Please feel free to ask questions if anything you read is unclear or would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you want to take part. The Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland, School of Education and Social Sciences granted this research ethical approval.

Thank you for reading this.

My name is Nasrin Sultana. I am a doctoral candidate at the University of the West of Scotland. For my research project, I have chosen to investigate headteachers' leadership in school improvement in Bangladeshi government primary schools. The School of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland is supporting me with this project.

What is the purpose of this investigation?

The purpose of the study is to explore how Bangladeshi primary school headteachers deal with contested issues related to school improvement initiatives. This study seeks to understand how school headteachers deal with the challenges that arise when implementing these initiatives between them and the stakeholders, including parents, community leaders, education officials and school committees.

Research Objectives

The study will address the following objectives:

- To investigate primary school headteachers' understanding of school improvement and their role as leaders within this.
- To provide insights into how headteachers understand their devolved powers in relation to school improvement.
- To investigate what leadership challenges headteachers in Bangladesh face when seeking to drive forward school improvement.
- To investigate what leadership opportunities headteachers in Bangladesh identify as being supportive to school improvement.
- To investigate how headteachers navigate contested leadership spaces (i.e. spaces where there is a tension between their own and others' expectations of leadership) when leading school improvement.

Do you have to take part?

Participation in this study is voluntary. This information sheet will describe the study to you. I will then ask you to sign a consent form showing you agree to participate. At any time, you are free to withdraw without giving a reason. This will not affect the standard of care you receive.

What will you do in the project?

For this part of the study, I will visit your workplace and observe how you interact with your students, staff, high officials, parents, and the management committee while discussing school improvement initiatives. During the observation period, I will also collect information using informal conversation.

Individual information will not be reported back to your institution's authority. I will sit or stand somewhere out of the way to avoid interfering with your work and observe and take notes. You can ask me if you have any questions or concerns before or during the observation period. You can ask me to stop observing or move to a different location anytime. I may have questions to ask you to follow up on observations. I will check with you before doing so if this is convenient for you. Please do not hesitate to ask me any questions you may have about the observation or the study.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been chosen because you are a head teacher and have experience related to school improvement. Your experience may be helpful in improving the primary school, as you can offer insights into how Bangladeshi primary head teachers deal with leadership challenges when attempting to implement school improvement initiatives.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause disadvantages or discomfort.

What happens to the information in the project?

Any data collected as part of this research will be stored securely for 3 years following the publication of the results. Only the primary researcher, the person employed to type up interview transcripts, and the supervision team will have access to the data collected. This data will be anonymised prior to sharing with the supervisory team and stored on a secure server that is password protected.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office, which implements the Data Protection Act 1998. All personal data of participants will be processed in accordance with the provisions of the Data Protection Act 1998.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in this project, please sign the consent form to confirm this. If you do not wish to be involved, thank you for your time.

If desired, a summary of the research findings can be sent once the investigation is complete.

If you have any questions/concerns during or after the investigation or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or from whom further information may be sought, please contact my supervisors:

Supervisors Details:

Dr. Carole Bignell

E-mail: [REDACTED]

Dr. Yonah Matemba

E-mail: [REDACTED]

Researcher contact:

Nasrin Sultana

[REDACTED]

Appendix B: Headteacher Information Sheet

School of Education and Social Sciences

Paisley Campus

Research Informed Consent Form

Title of Project: Headteachers' Leadership of School Improvement in Bangladeshi Government Primary Schools: An Ethnographic Study

Ethics Approval Number: 15431

Name of the Researcher: Nasrin Sultana

Researcher Email: nasrin.sultana@uws.ac.uk

This is a participant consent form for a PhD research that is investigating how Bangladeshi primary school headteachers navigate leadership spaces when leading school improvement initiatives. By completing this form, you are agreeing to take part in this study and that you have given permission for your views to be included in this study. Following ethical principles, you will not be identified by name nor will information that can identify you be used. You are also free to withdraw from taking in the study anytime.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, put your initials against the corresponding boxes below:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and an instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to one month after participating in the research without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I consent to the processing of my personal information (<i>age, sex, and work experience</i>) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such	

information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to have my voice digitally recorded (audio and video).	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Name of participant:

Name of researcher: Nasrin Sultana

Signatures:

Signatures:

Date:

Date:

If you have any questions about the research, please contact my lead supervisor:

Dr Carole Bignell

Email: [REDACTED]

Appendix C: Gatekeeper Letter

Government of People's Republic of Bangladesh
Directorate of Primary Education
Mirpur 2, Dhaka 1216

Memo no: 38.01.0000.346.99.001.16 - 787

Date: 27 July 2022

In response to your application, we are very glad to let you know that your proposal of the research topic on *“Headteachers Leadership of School Improvement in Bangladeshi Government Primary Schools: An Ethnographic Study”* will enhance our Primary Head Teachers’ leadership quality. The Directorate of Primary Education has approved your proposal to collect data from Government Primary Schools in Dhaka district.

Therefore, we hope that your research activities will be successful and effective for the future leader of primary school.

Monish Chakma

Director (Policy & Operation)
Directorate of Primary Education

Mirpur-2, Dhaka-1216

Nasrin Sultana
Researcher
University of the West of Scotland
Email: [Redacted]

cc

1. Dr. Carole Bignell
Email: [Redacted]
University of the West of Scotland
2. District Primary Education Officer
Dhaka District
3. Office Copy

Appendix D: 1. Manual Coding Example

19/01 12.30 pm

Today is Thursday. HT organises a meeting for parents to discuss student admission rules and funding for cleaners. Approximately 12 parents, 4 PTA members, and three managing committee members are at this meeting, which is being held in one classroom. It is for the school of Primary 2. Students in Primary Class 2 finish their classes in the morning shifts. Most of them know that I am here to collect research data.

RQ 1
SI

HT states, 'Dear all, you know January is significant because our students' new classes begin that month. First, I request that everyone kindly assist us by providing information about any students still not enrolled for pre- or primary one. We must ensure that children aged five and up in our catchment area do not remain unenrolled.'

RQ-1, SI
Enrollment at
Self governing power

'Dear all, greetings,' says the chairman of School Manging Committee. Please send your child to school on time every day. Also, make sure that they complete their homework task perfectly. And if you have any problems, please get in touch with me and I will do my best to solve them.' One parent responds, 'it would be helpful if the students finished the learning task in the classroom with the guidance of the teachers.' HT responds, "I have already provided guidance to the teachers to help the students complete the tasks in the classroom." Some of my teachers have already begun this act; I expect the rest will do so soon. 'Teachers should begin home visits to find any students who have not been enrolled,' says one managing committee member. HT responds, 'Yes, teachers began home visits last week, and I divided the area with them.'

RQ-1
Students
attendance
an d home
work - relat
SI
RQ-3 Mentoring

RQ-2
Monitoring

After their meeting, I managed an informal conversation with a few. I tried to discuss my research questions. When I ask the chairman what he means by "school improvement," he says, "School improvement is a type of activity that is closely related to the improvement of students' academic and ethical performance," he responds. In primary school, students develop their moral character to create a beautiful society. As a result, teachers take on the protagonist role to assist students in becoming the true heroes. And I believe that skilled teachers are the most important factor in school improvement.'

RQ-1
Students
academic
success
SI

RQ-1 → skilled teacher (SI)

Appendix D: 2. From extracts to codes and themes

Extracts	Codes	Themes/Subthemes	RQ
<p>Another parent, who is also a managing committee member, says, " Only the headteacher can ensure a school is effective and constantly improving. Qualified and caring teachers are vital components of school enhancement. Headteachers can cultivate caring attitudes in teachers, which, of course, contributes to student success. Students' success means the students' classroom's best performance, which depends on good care by the headteacher and the staff.</p>	<p>Headteacher's role, Qualified teachers, Caring teachers, Students' success, Students' classroom performance, good care by the head teacher</p>	<p>The role of the headteacher is to ensure that teachers are well-prepared and caring to ensure students' classroom performance.</p>	<p>RQ1</p>
<p>The headteacher is in the assembly class on the school field to monitor all students (pre-primary to class Five) assembly. Every student is very disciplined during the assembly. The headteacher delivers a short speech before finishing the assembly, emphasising the importance of punctuality, discipline, self-respect, school norms and good news for staff and students. In this session, students are closely monitored.</p>	<p>Headteachers monitoring the assembly class, headteachers' speech, emphasise students' discipline and school norms, monitor students' uniform</p>	<p>Monitoring the students during assembly and exercising 'Disciplinary Power' as a tool for school improvement.</p>	<p>RQ2</p>

<p>They are wearing complete school uniforms are not.</p>			
<p>The Headteacher of school A and the chairman are discussing the current school challenges. The headteacher mentions to the chairman that a common issue in primary schools across Bangladesh is the challenge posed by low-income parents. He reflects that many parents work hard all day long, returning home exhausted and preoccupied with cooking, leaving them with little time to monitor their children's academic progress. He notes that some parents even face difficulties buying basic school supplies such as notebooks and pens, and many cannot provide lunch boxes for their children.</p>	<p>School challenges, the headteacher's concern, the chairman's concern, low-income parents, parents who are preoccupied, and parents who overlook children's academic progress due to poverty.</p>	<p>Parents' Financial Difficulties and School Improvement / Lack of Parental Support</p>	<p>RQ3</p>

Appendix E: Fieldnote

Example of Fieldnote:

Subject: Field note School A Date: _____

Time	Notes	Ref (Power)	Ask HT (In ed)
9:00 am	<p>parent meeting, place: pre-primary classroom. 20 benches, 6 chairs, one large table, 22 parents.</p> <p>HT speaker: Attendance, some students attendance are very low. HT was frustrated. HT named 13 students who did not bring homework often, specially last month did not any.</p> <p>HT - The students as well as parents seem to never open the school diary.</p> <p>HT - Next month those students would be monitored and if the situation does not improve, all of the students would be punished.</p> <p>HT then named 5 students who are often absent in the school and fought with other students - another 9 students polluted the school by straining paper and waste in the classroom.</p>	<p>School I</p> <p>Exercising disciplinary power</p> <p>(Surveillance)</p> <p>Q1 + 2</p>	<p>✓</p>
11:00 am	<p>Informal conversation with five parents: pre-primary classroom</p> <p>S1: Well decorated classrooms, students reading proficiency, classroom achievement.</p> <p>P2 - Headteacher is caring but some teachers are not good caring at classroom.</p> <p>P3 - Qualified teachers are very important for SI</p> <p>P4 - Head teacher supervision, skilled teachers, students performance → SI</p>	<p>Q1</p> <p>SI</p>	

